

**Acta of the
International Symposia on
Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes**

**ISMEC 2022
International Symposium on
Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes**

València, June 5th-8th, 2022

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

International Group for the Thermodynamics of Complexes

Acta of the International Symposia on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes

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Foreword

ISMEC 2022 will be the 50th edition of a series of meetings that begun in Parma in 1973 as the annual congress of the Italian group of “Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes” followed by a meeting in Florence in 1974. In 1989 in Modena it became an Italian-Spanish (or Spanish-Italian) congress with annual meetings starting in Peñíscola (Spain) in 1990 and from then on alternating between Italy and Spain. From the 2010 meeting held in Bilbao, the participation was widened at an international level and took the name of International Symposium on Metal Complexes.

The scientific program will be organised in lectures, oral communications and poster sessions, focused on recent scientific advances in the thermodynamics and the kinetics of complexes in the fields of Analytical, Biomedical, Environmental, Inorganic and Physical Chemistry. Main topics include, but are not limited to:

- Complexation thermodynamics and kinetics
- Solution equilibria and coordination chemistry
- Complexation processes in supramolecular chemistry
- Metal-based reactivity and catalysis
- Metal-complex interactions with biomolecules
- Metals in diseases: transport, homeostasis and toxicity
- Metal-based drugs: diagnosis and therapy
- Metal complexes of environmental and biological interests
- Nanostructured metal complexes
- Analytical methods and sensors based on complexation equilibria
- Computer methods for equilibrium analysis

The Symposium aims to provide a valuable discussion forum on the above areas, fostering new collaborations among researchers from diverse backgrounds with complementary skills and goals. In addition to lectures, covering a wide range of topics, a poster session will provide multiple opportunities for informal discussions in a friendly atmosphere. The presentation of oral communications by young researches will be promoted.

The Symposium venue is ideally located in the city centre of València, with easy access to public transport, hotels, restaurants and bars, pedestrian shopping areas, museums, parks and gardens.

We look forward to welcoming you in València in June 2022.

Enrique García-España
President of the Organizing Committee ISMEC 2022
València, June 2022

International Scientific Committee

Demetrio Milea

Università degli Studi di Messina, Italy
President of ISMEC Group

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Former President of ISMEC Group

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ISMEC Acta webpage: www.ismecgroup.org/ismec-acta/

	Sunday 5 th	Monday 6 th	Tuesday 7 th	Wednesday 8 th
9:00 - 9:30		PL2-Dominik Weiss	PL4-João Carlos Lima	KN5-Carmen E. Castillo
9:30 - 9:45				OC26-Álvaro Martínez-Camarena
9:45 - 10:00				
10:00 - 10:15		KN1-Teresa Doménech	KN3-Katalin Várnagy	OC28-Rosita Cappai
10:15 - 10:30				OC29-Luca Mancini
10:30 - 11:00		Coffee break		
11:00 - 11:15		OC4-Josselin Gorny	OC12-Belén Altava	OC30-Přemysl Luba
11:15 - 11:30		OC5-Jose Luis Barriada	OC13-Csilla Kállay	OC31-Andrea Melchior
11:30 - 11:45		OC6-Dong Han	OC14-Agnieszka Szebesczyk	OC32-Ariadna Gil
11:45 - 12:00		OC7-Emanuele Zanda	OC15-Denise Bellotti	OC33-Orsolya Dömötör
12:00 - 12:15		OC8-Vladimir Sladkov	OC16-Éva Enyedi	OC34-David Fabra
12:15 - 12:30		OC9-Lorenzo Castellino	OC17-Joanna Wątył	OC35-Thomas Scattolin
12:30 - 12:45		OC10-Lisa Rita Mangnaghi	OC18-Francesca Binacchi	OC36- Leonor Côrte-Real
12:45 - 13:00		OC11-Alejandro Gracia Regueiro	OC19-Magdalena Rowińska-Żyrek	OC37-Natalia Busto
13:00 - 15:00		Lunch		
15:00 - 15:15	ISMEC meeting	KN4-Mauro Formica	OC38-Laura Rodríguez	
15:15 - 15:30			OC39-Giampaolo Barone	
15:30 - 15:45		OC20-Vojtěch Kubíček	OC40-Erika Ferrari	
15:45 - 16:00		OC21-Sławomir Potocki	Pulidori Award Martina Sanadar/Adriana Miller	
16:00 - 16:15	Poster session + coffee break	OC22-Giuseppina Santonoceta		
16:15 - 16:30		OC23-Carmen Rosales		
16:30 - 16:45		OC24-Homa Mousavi	Closing	
16:45 - 17:00	Op. Ceremony	Op. UV-125 Aniversario	OC25-Nicolás Veiga	Free time
17:00 - 17:15				
17:15 - 17:30	OC1-Raffaela Biesuz	KN2-Nataliia Shtemenko	OC22-Giuseppina Santonoceta	
17:30 - 17:45	OC2-Gyula Tircsó			
17:45 - 18:00	OC3-Elżbieta Gumienna-Kontecka			
18:00 - 19:00	PL1-Tarita Biver	PL3-Jean Marie Lehn		
19:00	Wine			
21:00			Gala Dinner + poster awards	

Scientific Program

Sunday 5th

16:00 - 17:00 **Registration**

17:00 - 17:15 **Opening Ceremony**

Chairman: Demetrio Milea

17:15 - 17:30 **OC1-Raffaella Biesuz**

“Modelling of Fe(III) and Zr(IV) sorption equilibria from water media into a DFO-based resin”

17:30 - 17:45 **OC2- Gyula Tircsó**

“Synthesis and physico chemical characterization of Mn(II) complexes formed with bifunctional ligands derived from PC2A for the efficient labelling of vector biomolecules”

17:45 - 18:00 **OC3-Elżbieta Gumienna-Kontecka**

“CLATHROPROBES: chiroptical probes for protein sensing and cages stabilising high oxidation states of metal ions”

18:00 - 19:00 **PL1-Tarita Biver**

“On the mechanism of the binding of metal complexes to biosubstrates: the spectroscopic contribution”

19:00 **WINE OF HONOR**

Monday 6th

Chairman: Manuel Valiente

09:00 - 10:00

PL2-Dominik Weiss

"The non-traditional role of siderophores in the plant soil environment"

10:00 - 10:30

KN1-Teresa Doménech

"Metal Complex Chemistry and Conservation of Cultural Heritage"

10:30 - 11:00

Coffee break

Chairman: Michel Meyer

11:00 - 11:15

OC4-Josselin Gorny

"Improving the performances of Diffusive Gradient in Thin-films (DGT) technique to measure the labile uranyl concentration in environmental waters by employing the chelating properties of siderochelates"

11:15 - 11:30

OC5-José Luis Barriada

"Sustainable hybrid materials to achieve high Cr(VI) removals in one-step processes"

11:30 - 11:45

OC6-Dong Han

"Complexation-extraction and spectrophotometric determination of trace levels cytostatics (tetrachloroplatinate and cis-diamminedichloroplatinum(II)) with o-phenylenediamine"

11:45 - 12:00

OC7-Emanuele Zanda

"Complexation of Tetravalent Thorium and Uranium with Dihydroxamic Acids"

Chairman: Salvador Blasco

12:00 - 12:15

OC8-Vladimir Sladkov

"Metal-ion Complex Formation Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions by Affinity Capillary Electrophoresis"

- 12:15 - 12:30** **OC9-Lorenzo Castellino**
“PyES – an open source software for the computation of in solution and precipitation equilibria”
- 12:30 - 12:45** **OC10-Lisa Rita Magnaghi**
“Chemometric-minded approach for the comprehension and rationalisation of neuromelanin’s synthesis first steps”
- 12:45 - 13:00** **OC11-Alejandro García Regueiro**
“Design of chiral spin crossover molecules for multifunctional compounds and surfaces”
- 13:00 - 15:00** **LUNCH**
- 15:00 – 16:00** **ISMEC Meeting**
- 16:00 - 17:00** **Poster session + Coffee break**
- 17:00 - 17:30** **Academic Opening** (125th Anniversary of the Beginning of the Studies in Chemistry at the University of Valencia)
- Chairman: Enrique García-España*
- 17:30 - 18:00** **KN2-Nataliia Shtemenko**
“Anticancer, antioxidant and nucleotide-binding activity of the dirhenium(III) clusters”
- 18:00 - 19:00** **PL3-Jean Marie Lehn**
“Perspectives in Chemistry: From Supramolecular Chemistry towards Adaptive Chemistry”

Tuesday 7th

Chairman: Antonio Bianchi

- 09:00 - 10:00** **PL4-João Carlos Lima**
“Gold(I) luminescent complexes: new perspectives on supramolecular assemblies and sensing”
- 10:00 - 10:30** **KN3- Katalin Várnagy**
“Modelling of metal binding sites of natural proteins with oligopeptide-metal complexes”

10:30 - 11:00 **Coffee break**

Chairwoman: Elzbieta Gumienna-Kontecka

- 11:00 - 11:15** **OC12-Belén Altava**
“Enantioselective Cycloaddition of CO₂ to Epoxides using bimetallic Zn pseudopeptidic macrocycle complexes”
- 11:15 - 11:30** **OC13-Csilla Kállay**
“Factors affecting the oxidation of prion protein fragments”
- 11:30 - 11:45** **OC14-Agnieszka Szebesczyk**
“Interaction of peptide fragments of HSPB1 with iron ions”
- 11:45 - 12:00** **OC15-Denise Bellotti**
“Calcitermin and its peptide derivatives as promising antimicrobial agents with metal chelating ability”

Chairman: Carmelo Sgarlata

- 12:00 - 12:15** **OC16-Éva A. Enyedi**
“Insight into the effect of the coordination modes of tridentate thiosemicarbazones on their solution chemical properties and cytotoxicity”

- 12:15 - 12:30** OC17-**Joanna Wątył**
"An ordinary plant with unusual peptides – could metal-shepherin complexes fight pathogens?"
- 12:30 - 12:45** OC18-**Francesca Binacchi**
"1,10-Phenanthroline/Pd(II) complexes bearing arene ligands with N or O coordinating groups: synthesis and bioactivity tests"
- 12:45 - 13:00** OC19 **Magdalena Rowińska-Żyrek**
"Metal ion coordination – the eminence grise of antimicrobial peptides"
- 13:00 - 15:00** **LUNCH**
Chairman: Juan Niclós
- 15:00 – 15:30** KN4-**Mauro Formica**
"Playing with fluorophores in sensing metal cations and anions"
- 15:30 – 15:45** OC20-**Vojtěch Kubíček**
"Copper(II) complexes with cyclam derivatives bearing phosphinato-bis(phosphonate) pendant arm"
- 15:45 – 16:00** OC21-**Sławomir Potocki**
"Mycobacterial SmtB/BigR4 α 5 domain in zinc and nickel systems"
Chairwoman: Raffaella Biesuz
- 16:00 - 16:15** OC22-**Giuseppina Santonoceta**
"Metal-coordinated assemblies containing quercetin: a solution equilibria study for the development of pH-responsive drug delivery systems"
- 16:15 - 16:30** OC23-**Carmen Rosales**
"Molecular recognition between the copper(II)-thiodiacetate chelate and a synthetic adenine nucleoside"
- 16:30 - 16:45** OC24-**Homa Mousavi**
"Tetranuclear complex built by the molecular recognition between the Cu₂(μ -EGTA) chelate and μ -N7,N9-H(N3)-2,6-diaminopurine"

ISMEC 2022

International Symposium on Metal Complexes

16:45 - 17:00

OC25-Nicolás Veiga

“Iron complex imprinted polymers as heterogeneous catalysts for the green degradation of dye pollutants”

17:00 - 18:00

Poster session + Coffee break

Wednesday 8th

Chairman: Vieri Fusi

- 09:00 - 09:30** **KN5-Carmen E. Castillo**
"Reaction kinetics of Iron(II) complexes and their relevance to catalytic oxidation processes"
- 09:30 - 09:45** **OC26-Álvaro Martínez-Camarena**
"An antioxidant boehmite amino-nanozyme able to disaggregate Huntington's inclusion bodies"
- 09:45 - 10:00** **OC27-Matteo Savastano**
"A Simple Tripodal Ligand for Surface Decoration of Carbon-based Materials with Pd(II) Catalytic Centres"
- 10:00 - 10:15** **OC28-Rosita Cappai**
"Effect of functionalization of kojic acid on metal ions complexation"
- 10:15 - 10:30** **OC29-Luca Mancini**
"A biphenol tail-tied double scorpiand pyridinophane polyamine for the detection of anions and metal ions"
- 10:30 - 11:00** **Coffee break**

Chairwoman: Maria Amélia Santos

- 11:00 - 11:15** **OC30-Přemysl Lubal**
"Thermodynamic, Kinetic and Structural Study of Cu(II) Complex of an Ethylene Cross-bridged Cyclam Ligand with Two Pyridine Pendant Arms"
- 11:15 - 11:30** **OC31-Andrea Melchior**
"Thermodynamics of Co(II) Complexation with Nitrate and Chloride in the [C4mim][Tf2N] Ionic Liquid"

- 11:30 - 11:45** **OC32-Ariadna Gil**
“Investigation of the ligand topology for targeting multimedia G-Quadruplex DNA”
- 11:45 - 12:00** **OC33-Orsolya Dömötör**
“Anticancer activity and biospeciation of ruthenium(II) polypyridyl complexes”
- Chairman: Jorge González*
- 12:00 - 12:15** **OC34-David Fabra**
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- 12:15 - 12:30** **OC35-Thomas Scattolin**
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- 12:30 - 12:45** **OC36-Leonor Côte-Real**
“New Zn(II) and Cu(II) Schiff base metal complexes based on 8-hydroxyquinoline scaffold designed for efficient cancer therapy”
- 12:45- 13:00** **OC37-Natalia Busto**
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- 13:00 - 15:00** **LUNCH**
- Chairwoman: Teresa Albelda*
- 15:00 – 15:15** **OC38-Laura Rodríguez**
“Playing with gold(I) aggregates: phosphorescence emission vs singlet oxygen production”
- 15:15 – 15:30** **OC39- Giampaolo Barone**
“Guanine oxidation catalysed by Schiff base metal complexes: Effects “of” and “on” the DNA structure”

15:30 – 15:45

OC40-Erika Ferrari

“From direct labelling to the bifunctional chelator approach the story so far: the development of curcumin-based PET-radiotracers”

Chairman: Maurizio Remelli

15:45 - 16:30

PULIDORI AWARDS

Adriana Miller

“Clavanins: where minor differences in structure cause major changes in antimicrobial efficiency”

Martina Sanadar

“Isoquinoline-based Eu(III) luminescent probes for citrate sensing in complex matrix”

16:30 - 16:45

CLOSING

20:00

GALA DINNER

ISMEC 2022

VALÈNCIA, 5th - 8th June 2022

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PL2- “THE NON-TRADITIONAL ROLE OF SIDEROPHORES IN THE PLANT SOIL ENVIRONMENT”

Dominik Weiss

PL3- “PERSPECTIVES IN CHEMISTRY: FROM SUPRAMOLECULAR CHEMISTRY TOWARDS ADAPTIVE CHEMISTRY”

Jean Marie Lehn

PL4- “GOLD(I) LUMINESCENT COMPLEXES: NEW PERSPECTIVES ON SUPRAMOLECULAR ASSEMBLIES AND SENSING”

João Carlos Lima

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KN2- “ANTICANCER, ANTIOXIDANT AND NUCLEOTIDE-BINDING ACTIVITY OF THE DIRHENIUM(III) CLUSTERS”

Nataliia Shtemenko

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Katalin Várnagy

KN4- “PLAYING WITH FLUOROPHORES IN SENSING METAL CATIONS AND ANIONS”

Mauro Formica

KN5- “REACTION KINETICS OF IRON(II) COMPLEXES AND THEIR RELEVANCE TO CATALYTIC OXIDATION PROCESSES”

Carmen E. Castillo

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Raffaella Biesuz

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Elżbieta Gumienna-Kontecka

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Francesca Binacchi

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Magdalena Rowińska-Żyrek

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Vojtěch Kubíček

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Sławomir Potocki

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Carmen Rosales

OC24- “TETRANUCLEAR COMPLEX BUILT BY THE MOLECULAR RECOGNITION BETWEEN THE $\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-EGTA})$ CHELATE AND $\mu\text{-N7,N9-H(N3)-2,6-DIAMINOPURINE}$ ”

Homa Mousavi

OC25- “IRON COMPLEX IMPRINTED POLYMERS AS HETEROGENEOUS CATALYSTS FOR THE GREEN DEGRADATION OF DYE POLLUTANTS”

Nicolás Veiga

OC26- “AN ANTIOXIDANT BOEHMITE AMINO-NANOZYME ABLE TO DISAGGREGATE HUNTINGTON'S INCLUSION BODIES”

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Matteo Savastano

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Rosita Cappai

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Přemysl Lubal

OC31- “THERMODYNAMICS OF Co(II) COMPLEXATION WITH NITRATE AND CHLORIDE IN THE $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ IONIC LIQUID”

Andrea Melchior

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Ariadna Gil

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Paulina Haller, Julia Torres, Ignacio Machado, **Nicolás Veiga**

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Emanuele Zanda, Veronika Zinovyeva, Stéphane Brandes, Michel Meyer, Vladimir Sladkov

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PLENARY LECTURES

On the mechanism of the binding of metal complexes to biosubstrates: the spectroscopic contribution

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The mechanistic analysis of the binding of a target molecule (often a metal complex to be tested as a drug) to a biosubstrate may be done by absorbance and fluorescence titrations, coupled with other techniques or other spectroscopic tests such as melting experiments. Titrations are basic approaches that may wrongly appear old-fashioned. However, this is not the case. They are powerful tools that might hold nasty surprises despite their apparent simplicity [1,2]. This contribution will, on one side, discuss some recent findings on the different binding modes driven by metal centres (Au(I)/Ag(I), Pd(II)/Pt(II)/Au(III)) and ligands (series of Ru(II)-arene-a-diimine) towards different biosubstrates, the latter ranging from proteins to natural DNA and RNA polynucleotides including peculiar oligo-forms such as four-way junctions. On the other side, it will highlight some tricky aspects of the spectroscopic analysis of these complex systems.

Figure 1 Bovine serum albumin (BSA) binding tests: the target molecule acts as a quencher (Q) and induces a decrease in protein emission (ΔF). Example of the effect of using an iterative procedure for the correct $[Q_{\text{free}}]$ evaluation on the subsequent value of the binding constant (K) [2].

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- [2] F. Macii, T. Biver, *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **2021**, 216, 111305.

The non-traditional role of siderophores in the plant soil environment

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There is an increased recognition of the central role siderophores play in the biogeochemical cycling of trace metals in the environment, leading for example to increased mobility of uranium around nuclear waste repositories [1] or enabling access to micronutrients under deficient conditions [2].

One type of siderophore of particular interest to plant nutrition are mugineic acids (MAs) which are a family of amino acids with varying number of alcohol functional groups. The structural characteristics of these amino acids are three carboxylic groups and an azetidine ring (4-membered ring with nitrogen as its heteroatom). All mugineic acids bind transition metals in a pseudo-octahedral geometry where the azetidine nitrogen, secondary amine nitrogen and oxygens of both terminal carboxylic acids coordinate as basal planar donors while the hydroxyl oxygen and intermediate carboxylate oxygen coordinate to the metal in the axial positions.

It long has been understood that the principal role of siderophores is to chelate Fe³⁺ from the surrounding environment and making it available to Gramineae crops like barley. What remains unclear, however, is their role in the uptake of other trace elements, such as Zn²⁺, in rice plants as well as their cycling in the rhizosphere.

In this presentation we first present strong evidence for the involvement of mugineic acid in the uptake of Zn²⁺ in rice using metal isotope signatures [3, 4]. We then present a first conceptual model that explains how siderophores access and deliver zinc to the plants [5]. To this end, we determine accurate intrinsic logK values for a range of weak and strong organic ligands [6, 7]. Finally, we present evidence using density functional theory that ligand-to-metal charge transfer acts as an indicator for the stability of late first row transition metal – DMA complexes.

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Perspectives in Chemistry: From Supramolecular Chemistry towards Adaptive Chemistry

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Supramolecular chemistry is intrinsically a dynamic chemistry in view of the lability of the interactions connecting the molecular components of a supramolecular species and the resulting ability to exchange components. The same holds for molecular chemistry when the molecular entity contains covalent bonds that may form and break reversibly. These features allow for a continuous change in constitution by reorganization and exchange of building blocks and define a Constitutional Dynamic Chemistry (CDC) covering both the molecular and supramolecular levels.

CDC introduces a paradigm shift with respect to constitutionally static chemistry. It takes advantage of dynamic diversity to allow variation and selection and operates on dynamic constitutional diversity in response to either internal or external factors to achieve adaptation.

CDC generates networks of dynamically interconverting constituents, constitutional dynamic networks, presenting agonistic and antagonistic relationships between their constituents that may respond to perturbations by physical stimuli or to chemical effectors.

In materials science, it leads in particular to the generation of dynamic polymers, dynamers, and biopolymers.

The implementation of these concepts points to the emergence of adaptive and evolutive chemistry, towards systems of increasing complexity.).

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Gold(I) luminescent complexes: new perspectives on supramolecular assemblies and sensing

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The formation of gold(I) supramolecular aggregates is an important tool from different perspectives and the modulation of the possible assemblies with different size and shape starting from single molecules is still a challenge for the chemistry community. In the last years we have developed different series of gold(I) complexes that have been explored on this topic. We have managed to obtain very long fibers, rods and vesicles [1] and have also been able to modulate the reversibility of the assembly through the addition of an external metal cation that can be removed by a sequestrant agent.[2] We have observed that the self-assembling of the complexes occurs through π - π , Au- π and Au-Au intermolecular interactions, with direct effects on the resulting shapes, luminescence intensity and color, which has great potential for sensing applications.[3] The wide variety of shapes and optical properties is achieved using a modular approach inspired by the linear coordination of gold(I) where the first coordination site can be occupied by different types of chromophores modulating the electronic properties and the second coordination can be occupied by different types of phosphines which are ideal ligands to modulate the solubility in media of different polarity.

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ISMEC 2022

VALÈNCIA, 5th - 8th June 2022

KEYNOTES LECTURES

“Metal Complex Chemistry and Conservation of Cultural Heritage”

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In this presentation is provided an overview of the contribution of metal complex chemistry to the field of conservation of cultural heritage. The importance of metal complexes in different areas of activity and research that involve cultural heritage is shown through several examples that are organized in four parts in the presentation: artists' materials, alteration of materials, analysis of cultural heritage, and conservation treatments

Anticancer, antioxidant and nucleotide-binding activity of the dirhenium(III) clusters

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Dirhenium(III) cluster compounds contain an unique quadruple Re-Re bond that supports the lower valence state +3 of the metal. Dirhenium(III) quadruple-bonded compound of 6 classes with organic, haloid or phosphate ligands: dichlorotetra- μ -carboxylates, trichlorotri- μ -carboxylates, *cis*-tetrachlorodi- μ -carboxylates, *trans*-tetrachlorodi- μ -carboxylates, tetra- μ -phosphates of dirhenium(III) and octachlorodirhenate(III)-ion are presented [1].

Quadruple bond with δ -component is able to scavenge an unpaired electron that was shown *in vitro* in reactions with stable radicals. The **reactions of dirhenium(III) carboxylates with stable radicals** were more effective than that of some known antioxidants and showed the dependence of the reaction rate from the structure of the dirhenium(III) complex: interaction of a radical with tetracarboxylates took 30–35 days; with tricarboxylates - several days; *cis*-tetrahalogenodi-carboxylates - a day and *trans*-dicarboxylates - several seconds. To our knowledge no any range of metal-containing compounds could present so diverse group of “traps of radicals” differing so much in capacity. A lot of efforts were aimed by us to apply **nano-technological approach** to enhance biological activity of the substances. Encapsulation of dirhenium(III) compounds to lipid coating led to protection of the quadruple bond against hydrolysis. Preparation of liposomes or solid nanoparticles, where a rhenium compound together with cisplatin was displaced inside (so called “nanobins”) was shown to have not only protective but activation significance for the quadruple bond [2].

Dirhenium(III) compounds have their own **anticancer activity** that depended on the nature of the ligands and on structural type [1,3] was shown *in vivo* in animal models and in experiments with some human cancer cells. The synergistic or additive effect of cisplatin and dirhenium(III) cluster compounds showed very high efficacy, leading to elimination of tumor growth (so called Re-Pt antitumor system). Combination of two metal based drugs led not only to significant anticancer effects, but also to lowering of cisplatin toxicity and to overcoming the resistance to cisplatin. Some experiments with human cancer cells showed proapoptotic activity of the compounds. Dirhenium(III) compounds as mighty **antioxidants** were shown to diminish oxidative stress in several animal models, where peroxide oxidation of lipids was called by different reasons, behaved themselves as antihemolytics, hepato- and nephroprotectors [3], that allowed us to present a new type of antioxidants - **δ -antioxidants**. These supporting effects could be associated with repair of renal proximal tubular apparatus, where erythropoietin is synthesized, as some antioxidants made. Our research in experiments with **nucleobases, oligo- and polynucleotides** with different structural organization [3, 4] showed that dirhenium(III) clusters interacted with these molecules in another mechanism than cisplatin and that these interactions were redox – activated. These data explained the efficacy of the Re-Pt antitumor system. Recently together with Spanish scientists we have shown that some dirhenium(III) *cis*-dicarboxylates were selective G4 – binders [5] which suggests unique mechanisms of molecular DNA recognition for these complexes.

Several aspects of the dirhenium(III) compounds activity are discussing: use of combinational therapy and nanomaterials; involvement of some biologically active ligands and redox-activation strategy, maintenance of the drug ratios; regulation of the redox-state of tissues; red blood and bone marrow system defense; lowering of the cisplatin toxicity; nephro- and hepato-protection; overcome of the cisplatin-induced resistance, etc.

Acknowledgements

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Modelling of metal binding sites of natural proteins with oligopeptide-metal complexes

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It is well known that essential metal ions play important roles in the biosynthesis and transport of biomolecules or the catalysis of acid-base and redox processes of biological systems. It is also obvious that among the organic compounds the proteins, through their side chain donor atoms play the most important role in the metal ion binding. The N(1)/N(3) donor atoms of histidine are especially preferred binding sites of metalloproteins and metalloenzymes. One field of our present research work is the synthesis and investigation of polypeptides containing various side chain donor groups, in which the coordination of side chain donor atoms comes to the front and their sequences serve as the models of different metalloproteins. These molecules include peptide fragments of Cu,Zn-superoxide dismutase enzyme and tau protein which may also play a significant role in the development of Alzheimer's disease and/or other neurodegenerative disorders.

The systematic studies of the protected histidine containing peptides with sequences mimicking metal binding sites of CuZnSOD or potential binding site of tau protein were performed. The results on the one hand gave information about the metal ion and protein interaction and on the other hand made it possible to conclude general trends in the factors affected the coordination of metal complexes and metal binding affinity of histidine containing peptides. The results strongly suggest that metal complexes of those multihistidine peptides may be good models for the CuZnSOD enzymes that contain large number of amino acids, more histidine residues at different position in their sequences and both their exclusively imidazole coordinated complexes and the amide nitrogen bounded species have distorted geometry.[1,2] On the other hand the stability of the metal complexes significantly depend on the position of histidines and the quality of amino acids which are present in the neighbourhood of the histidine amino acids, also. This could be well demonstrated by metal binding ability of tau fragments (tau(9-16), tau(26-33) and tau(326-333) containing the His14, His32 and His329,His330 residue, respectively (see Figure).[3-5]

pH = 8.5

Figure: Distribution of metal ions between the His32 and His329,His330 in equimolar solution containing Cu(II)-Zn(II)-tau(26-33) (Gln/Lys)-tau(326-333) (a) and Ni(II)-Zn(II)-tau(26-33) (Gln/Lys)-tau(326-333) (b) ($c(M) = c(L) = 1 \text{ mM}$)

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Playing with fluorophores in sensing metal cations and anions.

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The development of chemosensors able to selectively respond to specific metal ions or anions is an important challenge in chemistry.

The molecular devices converting metal ions recognition in physical recordable signal are continuously growing. To reach this aim, research needs to be performed on the design and synthesis of ligands able to selectively bind a specific substrate and undergo concomitant changes in light absorption and/or emission properties. Fluorescence is a fast, simple and non-invasive analytical method that offer many advantages in terms of sensitivity, response time and costs with respect to other detection methods, thus resulting particularly suitable for in vivo applications. For such reasons, fluorescent systems received great attention in the last years and many versatile fluorescent chemosensors were developed. Generally, these systems interact with the metal ion in solution signaling its presence by changing fluorescence properties, as the wavelength or emission intensity, as well as by the appearance of a new fluorescence band different from those of the free sensor.

Classical sensors generally contain one or more fluorophores linked to a coordinating active moiety through a spacer. The coordinating active part usually contains functions able to

coordinate a metal ion and the choice of donor-functions (polyamines or other binding units) and molecular framework (macrocyclic or open-chain structures) is determined by the metal ion which has to be coordinated. [1]

Alternatively, systems designed to bind and sense anionic species commonly exploit weaker binding forces as H-bonding or charge-charge interactions [2], and in these cases the preorganization of the framework is crucial to achieve selectivity and strong binding of the target. Metal complexes can also bind anionic species when the metal centre show an unsaturated or labile coordination environment; the binding of the anion can be exploited to gain a photochemical response thus the metal complex behaves as chemosensors for anions. [3]

In the last years we have been working on the design and synthesis of a number of fluorescent sensors having different fluorophores together with different binding unit, thus achieving several fluorescent molecular frameworks. These systems revealed to be effective in sensing several guests ranging from metal ions to biologically important anions.

This contribution will focus on some of the most representative examples with the results obtained lately in this field.

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The kinetic of reactions of Iron(II) complexes and their relevance to catalytic oxidation processes

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Transformation of non-activated C-H and C=C bonds is crucial for industrial processes. Particularly interesting is the incorporation of oxygenated functional groups that allow them to be transformed into a wide selection of functional groups of interest in almost all branches of chemical industry. Regarding the interest of these transformations, accomplishing them under mild conditions and with high yields and selectivity is of capital relevance. In nature oxygenase metalloenzymes are responsible of many of these transformations fulfilling all these catalytic features. Therefore, they have been taken as inspiration in the development of bioinspired iron complexes where mechanistic understanding is imperative in the design of efficient catalysts. The mechanistic information is relevant not only about the reaction mechanism of the iron complex with the different oxidants but also the mechanism of reaction of the different intermediates with the organic compound to be oxidized. In the last decades an increasing number of model complexes, heme and non-heme, have been developed.

Most of the bio-inspired non-heme iron(II) complexes are supported by tetradentate N4 ligands, which lead to the formation of different high-valent metal-oxo intermediates formed from different oxidants (typically H₂O₂, ^tBuOOH, peracids, IO₄⁻, etc.). One of the most interesting complexes reported in the last years is [Fe^{II}(CF₃SO₃)₂(PyNMe₃)] (Figure 1) for which Fe^{III}-OOH, Fe^{IV}=O and Fe^V=O intermediates have been generated.

Figure 1: [Fe^{II}(CF₃SO₃)₂(PyNMe₃)] catalyst **R1**, R= OMe, H, Cl, Br, CO₂Me, CF₃.

A deep kinetico-mechanistic study has been conducted with this system leading to a deep knowledge of the mechanisms involved in the generation of these intermediates and the mechanism through which different organic compounds are oxidized. In this communication, it will be shown a full mechanistic picture about the reactivity of these complexes. It will be evaluated how the different intermediates are generated, how their formation can be optimized using kinetic studies, how the reactivity of two active geometric isomers can be evaluated, how Hammett plots can provide mechanistic details of the processes, etc. Ultimately, the amazing usefulness of these studies in the understanding not only of the mechanisms but also the parameters controlling their efficiency and their selectivity will be discussed.

Scheme 1

The reaction of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2(\text{PyNMe}_3)]$ with peracetic acid in acetonitrile solution leads to the formation of an equilibrium mixture of two species: $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{OOAc})(\text{PyNMe}_3)]$ and $[\text{Fe}^{\text{V}}(\text{O})(\text{OAc})(\text{PyNMe}_3)]$, being the last one the active in the oxidation process.[1,2] However, when the complex reacts with hydrogen peroxide it leads to the formation of a $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-OOH}$ species unable to activate strong C-H bonds but able to form an active intermediate, $\text{Fe}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$, by reaction with H^+ and following an heterolytic rupture of the O-O bond.[3]

On the other hand, the reaction of the complex with Bu_4NIO_4 leads to the formation of another high-valent metal-oxo intermediates. In this case a mixture of two $\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ isomers is formed, and their reactivity has been evaluated from a kinetic point of view. Regarding this last oxidant a deep kinetic-mechanistic study has been conducted where the effect of different substituents R at the pyridine has been evaluated not only in the isomerization process but also in hydrogen atom transfer and oxygen atom transfer reactions.

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ORAL COMUNICATIONS

Modelling of the Fe(III) and Zr(IV) sorption equilibria from water media onto a DFO-based resin

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The outstanding complexing ability of desferrioxamine B, DFO, has been efficiently exploited for designing a large variety of optical and electrochemical sensors allowing the qualitative and/or quantitative detection of different metal cations, including Fe(III), V(V), or Ga(III) [1, 2]. Thanks to the terminal amino group of DFO, several strategies have been proposed to functionalize different solid supports, such as nylon, cellulose, sepharose, acrylate polymers, or silica-based materials [3-5].

We are presenting a novel DFO-based solid phase, coined DFO@Purolite, obtained by covalent grafting of DFO on the commercial Epoxy Purolite[®] resin. Relying on the nitrogen content of the modified material, the ligand loading was 0.20 mmol g⁻¹. The characterization of the sorption reactions followed a well-established procedure, and a thermodynamic model, based on the existence of the Donnan equilibrium at the water solution/resin interface, was employed. Accordingly, measurement of the exchange coefficients enabled to derive the intrinsic complexation or protonation constants, which are independent of the experimental conditions and thus characterize univocally the metal uptake equilibria. Acid-base titrations and fitting of the iron(III) and zirconium(IV) sorption isotherms by the Langmuir equation confirmed the DFO loading of 0.20 mmol g⁻¹, while the intrinsic protonation constant associated to equilibrium (1) was found to be in very good agreement with that of free H₃DFO in solution.

Under the employed experimental conditions, the kinetics of Fe(III) and Zr(IV) sorption followed a pseudo-first-order rate law. Although Fe(III) was taken up more rapidly than Zr(IV), the equilibrium was reached within one hour for both cations, as found previously for related materials [5].

Sorption profiles as a function of pH have been recorded using different experimental conditions, as shown in Figures 1 and 2 in the case of Zr(IV). Upon varying the ionic strength that strongly affects the sorption in the case of a Donnan equilibrium, or adding a competitive ligand to the solution that hinders the complex formation with the resin-bound chelator, it was possible to define the reactions and the corresponding intrinsic complexation constants that describe univocally the sorption under any experimental conditions.

Figure 1 Sorption profiles of Zr(IV) onto DFO@Purolite. 0.05 g of resin was contacted with 10 mL of 50 μ M Zr(IV) solutions in 0.1 M NaCl (blue dots), 1.0 M NaCl (yellow dots), 1.0 M NaCl + 0.1 mM DFO (red dots), and 1.0 M NaCl + 1 mM DFO (green dots).

Figure 2 Sorption profiles of Zr(IV) onto DFO@Purolite. 0.05 g of resin was contacted with 10 mL of 50 μ M Zr(IV) solutions in 0.1 M NaCl (blue dots), 1.0 M NaCl (yellow dots), 0.1 M NaCl + 0.5 mM EDTA (black dots), and 0.1 M NaCl + 5 mM EDTA (violet dots).

Figure 3 Desorption profiles of Zr(IV) at pH 2 as a function of the total DFO concentration. Discontinuous procedure: Zr(IV) enriched DFO@Purolite (0.05 g) was suspended in 10 mL of 0.1 M NaCl at pH 2 (HCl) until reaching equilibrium.

The validity of the proposed set of reactions and the accuracy of the sorption equilibrium constants were further ascertained by numerical analysis of the DFO or EDTA-assisted desorption profiles at pH 2 of Zr- (Figure 3) or Fe-loaded resin, respectively.

Remarkably, the solid/liquid extraction equilibria that best fit all acquired data sets were the same as those describing the speciation of unbound DFO in homogeneous solution reported in Ref. [6] for Zr(IV) and Ref. [7] for Fe(III), while the refined intrinsic sorption equilibrium constants are very close to those available in the literature. These findings suggest that covalent immobilization of a receptor onto a solid support enables the investigation of complexation processes that are difficult to study otherwise in homogeneous solution, for instances when complexes are too stable or scarcely soluble.

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Synthesis and physico chemical characterization of Mn(II) complexes formed with bifunctional ligands derived from PC2A for the efficient labeling of vector biomolecules

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Mn(II) is an essential metal ion and has attracted significant interest in molecular imaging probe development for Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), and MRI/PET diagnostic applications.^[1] Mn(II) contrast agent candidates (CAs) are suitable alternatives for Gd(III)-based CAs, with similar relaxometric properties but potentially lower toxicity, thus increased biocompatibility. ⁵²Mn is an excellent isotope for positron emission tomography (PET) with a half-life of 5.59 days and is chemically well-suited for radiolabeling of biomolecules (e.g. antibodies, affibodies etc). On the other hand labeling taxi molecules require appropriately designed bifunctional chelators (BFCs) forming stable and inert complex with the selected radioisotope. Our approach to Mn(II)-based MRI/PET CA candidates is based on the rigid pycLEN derivative PC2A platform (PC2A = pycLEN-3,9-diacetate) as it forms stable mono-aquated complex with Mn(II) endowed resistance to metal release.^[2] In the current project we have synthesized three BFC chelators (Fig. 1) possessing acetate (PC2ABn^{pCO₂H}), alpha-methyl acetate (PC2MABn^{pCO₂H}) and amide moieties (PC2AM^{Pip}Bn^{pCO₂H}) and evaluated their complexation properties by studying equilibrium, dissociation kinetic and relaxometric properties of their Mn(II) complexes. Radiolabeling of the ligands with ⁵²Mn are also performed in order to assess the applicability of these platforms in ⁵²Mn(II)-based PET applications.

Fig. 1 Formulae of the PC2A derivative BFC ligands synthesized and studied.

Based on equilibrium studies, the diacetate derivative (PC2ABn^{pCO2H}) appears to be the best candidate for the complexation of Mn(II) ($\log K_{MnL}=14.76(2)$) which translates to a pMn of 8.37 when $c_{Mn^{2+}}=c_L=0.01$ mM at pH=7.4). At the same time Mn(II) chelate formed with the the bis(amide) derivative ligand was found to form the most inert Mn(II) complex based on the rates of metal exchange reactions occurring with the essential Zn(II) ion. However, for the the Cu(II) complexes formed with amide derivative chelators hydrolysis of the amide pendant arm was evidenced under labelling conditions in the literature^[3] which was also observed under our experimental conditions for the [Mn(PC2AM^{pip}Bn^{pCO2H})] chelate. Since the Mn(II) chelate of PC2MABn^{pCO2H} was found to form conditionally slightly less stable Mn(II) chelate ($pMn=7.93$) dissociating four times faster than the [Mn(PC2ABn^{pCO2H})] we have selected the later system for its conjugation with HER-2 receptor selective affibody, aiming at targeted preclinical imaging of breast cancer.

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CLATHROPROBES: chiroptical probes for protein sensing and cages stabilising high oxidation states of metal ions

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Clathrochelates, or cage compounds, constitute a special type of complexes containing a metal ion in a three-dimensional ligand cavity [1]. As encapsulated in the macropolycyclic cage, the coordinatively saturated metal ion is shielded to a great extent from various external factors, including effects of solvents and exo-coordination that precludes the occurrence of redox processes by inner-sphere mechanisms and ligand substitution reactions [1]. For this reason, clathrochelates often exhibit a number of unusual properties; for example, they frequently attain enormous chemical and electrochemical stability, or have been recently recognized as prospective biological effectors using their three-dimensional structure as rigid scaffold for macromolecular binding.

The specific recognition of protein surface elements seem to be undoubtedly important for the development of various biochemical and biomedical tools, such as sensors, affinity tags, protein-based materials or novel immobilization techniques [3]. Upon interaction, the host protein molecules exhibiting inherent chirality are able to induce asymmetry of achiral organic and coordination compounds, and therefore may cause an appearance of a signal in their CD spectra. These induced CD (ICD) bands are very sensitive to the arrangement of the binding sites of hosting proteins and may reflect both the structural alterations and the conformation transitions of proteins. Various organic compounds and metal complexes have been reported to be ICD probes due to their binding to proteins and sensitivity to their structural alterations.

Here we will present our recent results on iron(II) clathrochelates as macrobicyclic cage metal complexes able to form multicentered supramolecular interactions in the vacant cavities or at the surface of protein macromolecules and/or their macromolecular complexes [3-5].

Moreover, we will discuss unprecedentedly stable Fe(IV) clathrochelates which are based on the hexahydrazide cage ligand and formed in aqueous solution under atmospheric conditions [6, 7].

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Improving the performances of Diffusive Gradient in Thin-films (DGT) technique to measure the labile uranyl concentration in environmental waters by employing the chelating properties of siderochelates

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Uranium (U) presents a unique challenge for ecological risk assessments around installations related to the nuclear fuel cycle because of both chemical and radiological toxicity. Their relative importance depends on the chemical speciation and isotopic composition of the radionuclide, the latter being strongly correlated to its natural or anthropogenic origin (enriched or depleted U) [1]. In this framework, the Diffusive Gradient in Thin-films (DGT) technique is an appealing tool for monitoring the water quality around uranium processing plants, nuclear facilities or mining areas. Indeed, the DGT sampling allows to preconcentrate *in situ* the labile U(VI) species, allowing to simultaneously characterize the labile UO_2^{2+} fraction in aqueous phase (*i.e.*, this provides qualitative information on the "available stock of UO_2^{2+} for the aquatic organisms") and the isotopic composition at trace levels [2]. Among the eleven DGT methods developed for UO_2^{2+} [3], the ones containing Chelex-100[®] (an ion-exchange resin with iminodiacetic acid functional groups) or Metsorb[®] (a TiO_2 -based adsorbent) are the most employed due to their commercial availability. Nevertheless, their performances can be significantly degraded by high concentration levels of competing ions like Ca^{2+} in the deployment solution, which results in the underestimation of the overall concentration of labile U(VI) species in environmental waters [3, 4]. To improve the reliability of measurements, further analytical developments are therefore required. One important research direction includes the design of more selective UO_2^{2+} sorbent materials.

In this study, we propose new DGT samplers for labile UO_2^{2+} species that incorporate novel complexing materials obtained by the covalent grafting of siderophore-like chelators on a hydrophilic organic resin. Siderophores are well-known to exhibit a high affinity for strong Lewis acids, such as Fe(III) and actinide cations [5-7]. Rigorous laboratory validation of the new DGT devices was conducted, confirming the suitability of the samplers to quantitatively measure all UO_2^{2+} species in simple matrices in which UO_2^{2+} - CO_3^{2-} complexes dominate the speciation of U. In addition, cross-tests were performed with commercial Chelex-100[®] and Metsorb[®] based-DGT devices on several types of moderately basic waters ($\text{pH} \approx 8$), either in the laboratory (*i.e.*, soft and hard mineral waters and seawater) or during field tests. DGT probes were deployed in the alkaline surface water of the Œuf River, a tributary to the Seine River (France), in which Ca^{2+} - UO_2^{2+} - CO_3^{2-} complexes are the dominant U species according to speciation modelling calculations. These experiments highlighted the superiority of the new DGT devices over those incorporating either Chelex-100[®] or Metsorb[®] sorbents. Finally, thermodynamic speciation calculations were performed as a first approach to better understand the functioning and potential limitations of our new and Chelex-100[®]-based DGT samplers in different deployment conditions.

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Sustainable hybrid materials to achieve high Cr(VI) removals in one-step processes

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Rising manufacturing costs resulting from the current global situation make it necessary to economize in all stages of production, including waste management. In this study, inorganic polymeric materials have been synthesised, based on abundant raw materials worldwide, and were further treated to obtain hybrid materials suitable to perform pollutant removal studies. Hybrid materials with pellet form were obtained from these polymeric materials by iron doping and subsequently transformation with a natural extract obtained from eucalyptus leaves [1, 2]. The different materials prepared were used for chemical decontamination of Cr(VI). Two different pellet sizes have been studied in the experiments. The hybrid material provides the best results, achieving high Cr(VI) removals ($1.7 \text{ g Cr(VI)} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \text{ Fe}$) by a one-step process combining different chemical processes (reduction and adsorption). Reaction kinetics studies were conducted under different experimental conditions (pH, initial Cr(VI) concentration), and their influence on the reaction processes have been analysed. Two adsorption models, (Langmuir-Freundlich and a model based on statistical thermodynamics [3]) together with removal rates, were used to study the processes (Iron sorption on the inorganic polymeric base, Cr(VI) sorption, Cr(VI) removal and Total Chromium sorption).

Figure 1. a) TGA of iron-doped silicate treated with eucalyptus extract. b) Fe(II) adsorption onto polymeric silicate for large (3mm diameter, red symbols) and small (2mm diameter, black symbols) pellets.

High adsorption energies have been found, especially in the adsorption of Fe(II) on the polymeric base ($33.2 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). All materials were characterised by SEM and EDS analysis. TGA and gas IR analyses were performed to identify and quantify the organic matter present in the hybrid materials.

Figure 2. a) Cr(VI) elimination percentages by GSLP-Fe(0) D3 (●) and D2 (◆). Cr(VI) elimination percentages by GSLP-Fe D3 (■) and D2 (◆). b) Cr(VI) adsorption by GSLP-Fe D3 (■). Cr(VI) adsorption by GSLP-Fe D2 (◆). Cr(VI) maximum elimination by GSLP-Fe(0) D3 (●). Cr(VI) maximum elimination by GSLP-Fe(0) D2 (◆). Total chromium adsorption by GSLP-Fe(0) D3 (▲). Total chromium adsorption by GSLP-Fe(0) D2 (▼)

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Complexation-extraction and spectrophotometric determination of trace levels cytostatics (tetrachloroplatinate and cis-diamminedichloroplatinum(II)) with o-phenylenediamine

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The increasing consumption of cytostatic agents such as platinum-based anticancer drugs raised serious concerns, as platinum compounds that are not fully metabolized may be excreted via the urine of patients receiving chemotherapy [1]. It has been detected at low total platinum concentrations from tens of ng L⁻¹ to a few hundred µg L⁻¹ in hospital wastewater [2]. Pt residues can still cause potentially severe side-effects like cytotoxic, genotoxic, mutagenic, carcinogenic, and/or teratogen effects on living organisms even at low concentrations [3]. In this concern, a rapid, simple, and accurate spectrophotometric method has been developed by the complexation of either tetrachloroplatinate (PtCl₄²⁻) or cis-diamminedichloroplatinum (cisplatin) with o-phenylenediamine (OPDA), the complex [Pt(C₆H₄N₂H₂)₂] formed was extracted and concentrated by methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK), presenting a strong absorbance signal at 705 nm with long-term stability. The method demonstrated good linearity over the range from 2.5 to 50 µg L⁻¹. The system shows a high molar absorption coefficient of 8.09×10⁴ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 705 nm, a low limit of detection (LOD) and a low limit of quantification (LOQ). This study provides a promising method for the precise determination of cisplatin at the part per billion (ppb) level in aqueous samples.

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Complexation of Tetravalent Thorium and Uranium with Dihydroxamic Acids

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Actinides are harmful contaminants for the environments due to their chemical toxicity and radiotoxicity affecting living organisms. The presence of radioelements, such as U, Th, or Pu, as a result of accidental discharges raises the question of their transfer in the environment and the resulting risk of food chain contamination. Their transfer in soils and sediments is not only controlled by geological and physico-chemical parameters (clay and organic matter contents, pH, Eh, etc.) but also by microorganisms. The latter take part in the mobilization/immobilization of trace metals [1].

As natural iron-specific chelators, siderophores have to be considered in this context [2]. These low molecular weight, water-soluble compounds are excreted by bacteria and fungi to overcome the limited bioavailability of iron under aerobic conditions (ca. 10^{-18} M at neutral pH) by dissolving iron oxohydroxides present in the soils. Recently, they have also been recognized as effective actinide(IV) chelators and transporters, promoting the migration of plutonium in contaminated soils [3]. Because of their high affinity for hard Lewis acid cations, like Fe(III), hydroxamic siderophores are also able to effectively bind actinides (U, Th, Pu) [2,4,5]. The development of high affinity chelators for f-elements and the understanding of their coordination chemistry is of fundamental interest for the management and remediation of contaminated fields or the disposal of nuclear wastes in geological repositories [5].

This work is devoted to the complexation study of Th(IV) and U(IV) with dihydroxamic acids (Figure 1). For Th(IV), we used affinity capillary electrophoresis (ACE), which requires only a few μL of solutions, with UV detection. ACE is based on the change in the electrophoretic mobility of the detected species due to the interaction with other species present in the electrolyte. Four sets of runs were performed using (H,Na)ClO₄ mixtures at two different pH values but constant ionic strength. In a first approach, the background electrolyte (BGE) contained varying amounts of Th(IV), while the second approach consisted in analysing solutions containing increasing amounts of ligand in the BGE. The electrophoretic mobility changes with the increasing concentrations of the reagent dissolved in the BGE solution was used to assess the speciation and equilibrium constants.

In contrast to thorium that exists only in the +IV oxidation state, the manipulation of tetravalent uranium in aqueous solution is not an easy task because of its instability to air and

high tendency to hydrolyse. In practice, U(IV) is usually manipulated in glove boxes to keep inert conditions, while highly acidic conditions prevent hydrolysis in aqueous media. However, one advantageous feature of this $5f^2$ cation is its light absorption properties in the visible region, which allows to study the U(IV) complexation equilibria by classical absorption spectrophotometry. Having no wet glove box at our hands, we have developed a reliable experimental protocol for performing spectrophotometric titrations using simple tools, while starting from an air-stable UO_2^{2+} solution. Relying on cyclic voltammetry studies in 1 M $HClO_4$ under an argon atmosphere, the quantitative electrolysis of U(VI) to U(IV) was successfully achieved in a classical electrochemical cell. The progression of the reduction was monitored by UV-Vis spectrophotometry. Finally, the U(IV) solution was transferred in a thermostated gas-tight cell equipped with an argon inlet and outlet and which allows the insertion of a quartz dip probe for the registration of spectra. The entire setup was placed in a typical laboratory fume hood.

The ACE and spectrophotometric methods were successfully applied for studying the Th(IV) and U(IV) complex formation equilibria with various dihydroxamic acids. Both techniques provide valuable information for further modelling of their behaviour under environmental conditions [6].

Figure 1. General structure of the studied dihydroxamic acids

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Metal-ion Complex Formation Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions by Affinity Capillary Electrophoresis

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Thermodynamic data on complex equilibria of metal ions are very important, not only for fundamental knowledge, but in many diverse fields, such as toxicology, clinical and biological chemistry, geochemistry and environmental chemistry, analytics and industrial processes...[1]. The affinity capillary electrophoresis (ACE) is gaining more and more important place for the metal ion equilibrium studies for the kinetically rapid systems [2, 3]. ACE is successfully used not only for the complex species stability constant determination, but also for revealing of these complex formation equilibria and identifying the complexed species, for example, by ascertaining its charge and protonation state [2]. Moreover, ACE also has a potential for thermodynamic parameter determinations. Besides the molar Gibbs energy ($\Delta_r G_m$), we have as well an access to the molar enthalpy ($\Delta_r H_m$) and the molar entropy ($\Delta_r S_m$) of complex formation reactions. It should be noted too, that the ACE study requires only a small quantity of analyte. It is especially important, when we work with the highly toxic, radiotoxic substances or precious ligands.

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PyES – an open source software for the computation of in solution and precipitation equilibria

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Nowadays chemist can escape the necessity of interfacing himself/herself with a multiplicity of software and computer tools, moving from simple spreadsheets applications, such as Microsoft Excel, to more elaborate instruments for solving complex computation tasks that need to be tailored peculiarly.

Among all the fields where chemistry intersects with informatics, analytical chemistry is certainly of particular interest.

From a survey conducted among the participants of the Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research, COST ACTION – NECTAR CA18202[1], an European network of researchers dedicated to the study of thermodynamic equilibria, it has been noted how scarce and inadequate the available software is.

It was therefore decided to re-write ES4, a freeware computer program originally written by Prof. Silvio Sammartano from the Università degli Studi di Messina and his co-workers in the last century using the BASIC programming language [2-6], created with the aim of solving chemical equilibria in solutions.

Our main goal was to produce PyES: a new, open-source, practical, modern and multi-platform Python application.

Currently the software has two work modes: titration simulation and species distribution at different concentration of one of the component present (such as at different pH values). It is also able to manage solid species and to account for variable ionic strength of the medium, refining the formation constants by an expanded Debye-Hückel equation. Both these features are quite desirable features that many modern software lack.

The original terminal-based interface has been recreated in a more modern graphical form with graphing capabilities and the possibility of exporting the obtained results in Excel and .csv format, allowing interoperability with other applications that the end users may desire to use in their works for further data elaboration.

Various tests on the software were conducted to verify the coherence between the obtained results and experimental data collected from real chemical systems.

Figure. PyES main window and graphing interface.

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Dedication:

PyES and this work are in memory of Prof. Silvio Sammartano, for his invaluable contribution to the development of computer programs for solution equilibria.

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Chemometric-minded approach for the comprehension and rationalisation of neuromelanin's synthesis first steps

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Melanins are a class of pigments originated by oxidation of catecholic compounds in animals; among the different melanins classes, we focus our attention on neuromelanins (NMs), which are mainly found in human's pigmented neurons of *substantia nigra* (SN) and *locus coeruleus* (LC), where they exert a protecting role sequestering the reactive species derived from oxidation of dopamine (DA) or norepinephrine (NE) and toxic metal ions, such as iron and copper.[1-3] First link between NMs and Parkinson's Disease was assessed a century ago by K. N. Tretiakoff, when he reported the depletion of dopaminergic neurons of SN in brains of PD patients.[4] Moving forward, dying neurons can release NMs, promoting the microglia activation, [5] which, in turn, can disrupt NMs causing the release of toxic metals and compounds bound to NM, leading to a vicious cycle of chronic inflammation.[1] Since NMs is originated from metal-catalysed oxidation of catecholamines such as DA, our goal is to understand how this process is affected by chemical-physical parameters and medium composition.

With the aim of having further insights regarding the NMs synthesis, the reactivity studies have been performed following the DA oxidation by UV-Vis spectroscopy, changing the parameters listed above. To overcome the difficulties related to DA chemistry, such as precipitation of oligomers, spectral band overlap, changes in the LMCT bands of metal ion complexes and baseline drift, a stepwise multivariate approach was followed in the analysis of the spectra and their first derivative. These methods are powerful data reduction tools that allow to handle and interpret large datasets, such as full spectra, without any data manipulation or extrapolation and, moreover, to extract valuable information from spectra with several overlapped bands or baseline related problems.

Firstly, Design of Experiments was applied to highlight the parameters, among those listed above, that exert a significant influence on NMs synthesis. [6] Secondly, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was exploited to rationalise the overall process and extract information from the data acquired. Thirdly, 3Way-PCA allowed a clear and simple comprehension of the effect of the investigated parameters on both DA oxidation and NMs synthesis kinetic. [7-8] Figure 1 reports, as an example, the typical outputs of these last two techniques. The interesting results achieved gave us the idea of an explorative application of Data Fusion to jointly analyse data acquired with different techniques at given times, namely UV-Vis spectra, spectra first derivatives and metal consumption by NMs in formation, monitored by ICP-OES.

Figure 1: Example of PCA score plot (a) and 3-WAY PCA objects and conditions loading plots used for the data elaboration and interpretation.

Thank to this data treatment, the effect of metal ions is clearly manifested: copper is more reactive than iron in melanin formation; when both metal ions are present, the oxidation rate and the type of product are in between of the situation with the two metals taken alone and no significant cooperation is observed. Following the absorbance changes with time, it is possible to assess whether the reaction is driven by iron, copper or the two metal ions together in the medium. As for the effect of ionic strength of the medium and buffer type, the rate of DA oxidation decreases with the increase of the ionic strength and by switching from inorganic to organic type of buffer. As far as metal consumption is concerned, iron complete removal occurs between 6 and 24 h, depending on the I value, while copper is completely removed only at high I values. It is also evident from results and worth noting that iron binding is preferred, with respect to copper, by NMs in formation, over copper, in line with the higher affinity of the metal towards oxygenated ligands.

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Design of chiral spin crossover molecules for multifunctional compounds and surfaces

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When electrons are injected through chiral molecules, one electronic spin is preferably transmitted. This fascinating outcome was called **Chiral Induced Spin Selectivity (CISS) effect**^[1]. Unfortunately, the magnitude of the effect is weak and difficult to measure^[2]. Different approaches to overcome this limitation include the controlled orientation of the molecules by their assembly on a surface, the use of helicoidal molecules or the inclusion of metal atoms in the molecular structure.

One step forward, our previous work based on helical polypeptides coordinating lanthanide ions showed an enhanced spin selectivity when a paramagnetic instead of a diamagnetic cation was used^[3]. However, the different nature of the metallic atoms avoided a clear understanding of the role played by the unpaired electrons of the metallic centre. In this context, the use of transition metal atoms that can exhibit the **spin-crossover phenomenon (SCO)** in the chiral structure are highly interesting. These systems can undergo a spin transition from a diamagnetic to a paramagnetic state^[4], which could directly influence the spin filtering efficiency, as a function of the spin state while keeping the same metal centre.

Herein, we present our preliminary results about the synthesis of metal-organic complexes of iron (II) based on the use of two different kind of ligands: chiral inorganic ligands and polypeptides. On the first approach we have used (R,R)- and (S,S)- bis(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)cyclohexane-1,2-diamine^[5] promoting the isolation of both enantiomers of the coordination compound, while the chemical structure of the ligand is modified (Fig 1). On other attempt we have used polypeptidic sequences that include ATCUN binding unit^[6] to coordinate Fe²⁺, such as Gly-Gly-His (GGH) and Asn-Asn-His (NNH) sequences.

Figure 1. Crystalline structure of Δ -SS-complex (left) and Λ -RR-complex (right).

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Enantioselective Cycloaddition of CO₂ to Epoxides using bimetallic Zn pseudopeptidic macrocycle complexes.

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The growing emissions of carbon dioxide to the atmosphere have triggered the blossoming of technologies for its capture, activation, and conversion into added value chemicals [1]. Among the different carbon dioxide transformation technologies established to date, many efforts are being devoted for the development of efficient catalysts for the production of added-value cyclic carbonates [2]. In this regard, the most efficient approaches operate in the presence of huge excess of co-catalysts, namely organic salts, acting as the nucleophilic source and high reaction conditions i.e., temperatures ≥ 100 °C and pressures ≥ 1 MPa [3]. Herein, we report the synthesis of novel bimetallic complexes derived from different pseudopeptidic macrocycles (Figure 1). These complexes promoted remarkable activities in the cycloaddition of CO₂ to epoxides even at mild conditions and the system did not require the introduction of auxiliar co-catalysts, decreasing the chemical waste generated in the transformation. The intrinsic chirality of the pseudopeptides, together with the presence of conformationally constrained sites involved in supramolecular interactions, have proved to be responsible for the kinetic resolution of styrene oxide, resulting in the highest s factor value reported to date for such a substrate [4].

Figure 1. General structure of the macrocyclic organometallic complexes

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Factors affecting the oxidation of prion protein fragments

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Protein oxidation represents a major pathway of protein degradation. Oxidation reactions are significantly affected by protein sequence and structure. Additional complexities are introduced when oxidation reactions are catalyzed by transition metals. Such reactions may predominantly affect amino acid residues directly involved in metal binding or located in the close vicinity of the metal-binding site. Metal catalyzed oxidation (MCO) can lead to damaged bio-molecules and this is implicated in oxidative stress, biological aging and neurodegenerative diseases. MCO of proteins is mainly a site-specific process in which only one or a few amino acids at the metal-binding sites of the protein are preferentially oxidized.

The oxidation of PrP has been widely studied in our research group. Cu(II) interaction with the Human Prion 103-112 fragment (Ac-SKPKTNMKHM-NH₂) and its mutants has been studied with various techniques. The oxidation was carried out by the Cu(II)/H₂O₂ system. It was shown that the mutant peptide which does not contain methionine did not undergo oxidation, only the fragmentation of the peptide chain was perceived. However, in the case of methionine containing peptides, the peptide chain was not cleaved; instead, the oxidation of methionine to methionine sulfoxide occurred. The results revealed that methionine residues of the PrP can play a role as ROS scavengers; the presence of methionine residues protects the peptides from fragmentation. In these cases, Cu(II) ions catalyze the oxidation of methionine to methionine sulfoxide [1].

Cu(II) interaction with the Ac-PHAAAGTHSMKHM-NH₂ tridecapeptide, which contains the His85, His96 and His111 binding sites of the human PrP, has been also studied [2]. The order of Cu(II) binding affinity of the various histidyl sites is His111 ~ His96 > His85 according to our earlier results, while the order of oxidation activity is His96 > His85 >> His111 (Figure). The metal binding ability of the histidine residues outside the octarepeat region is almost comparable, but the susceptibility for oxidation differs. The order of binding affinity can be explained by the fact that the coordination mode at the -GTHS- and -MKHM- domain is the same, (N_{im}, N⁻, N⁻, N⁻) in the form of (6,5,5)-membered fused chelate rings, which is preferred over the (7,5,5)-membered one. The difference in oxidation susceptibility, catalyzed by the Cu(II) ions, may be due to the steric arrangement of the peptide. The Cu(II) ion is easily available for the hydrogen peroxide in the case of the -GTHS- domain, where the

side chains are relatively small. However, owing to the axial interactions of the larger side chains in the -MKHM- domain, the Cu(II) ion is locked, and therefore the oxidation at that position occurs to a smaller extent.

Figure: The order of copper(II) binding affinity and oxidation activity of various histidyl sites.

The effect of ascorbic acid on the metal catalyzed oxidation of a human PrP model peptide has also been studied, where the ambivalent role of ascorbic acid was proved [3]. The results indicated that the presence of ascorbic acid has significant effects on both the site of oxidation and the amount of products. The ascorbic acid hinders the oxidation of methionine but promotes the oxidation of histidine. Besides ascorbic acid, the effect of metal-protein attenuating compounds (MPACs) such as aroylhydrazones and 'Salan based' ligands were also studied [4-6]. MPACs are an emerging class of therapeutic agents that may delay or even prevent the progression of AD. These compounds showed protective effect towards the oxidation of methionine and histidine, processes that are related to both physiological and pathological aging.

Our studies may help to determine the factors which influence the oxidation of proteins, and can contribute to the understanding of the potential role of trace metal ions in these processes. Moreover, the results may provide a sufficient base for further research to design effective drugs and therapies.

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Interaction of peptide fragments of HSPB1 with iron ions

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Regulated cell death is a phenomenon that accompanies us practically from the first moments of life, allowing, for example, the separation of fingers during the prenatal life. One of the types of programmed cell death is ferroptosis, which is dependent on iron [1]. Ferroptosis was found to be distinct and disparate from other processes of cell death, both morphologically and biochemically [2].

As iron is transported into the cell mainly by transferrin (Tf) via transferrin receptor 1 (TfR1), through the receptor-mediated endocytosis of Tf-TfR1 complex, blockage of this process leads to inhibition of ferroptosis. It was shown that recycling of TfR1, which normally follows the release of iron ions and the hydrolysis of transferrin from the complex, is inhibited by HSPB1, along with iron concentration reduction [2-4].

Heat shock protein B1 (HSPB1, also known as Hsp27) is an ATP-independent chaperone, which belongs to the family of small heat shock proteins (sHsp). Its expression is increased during heat shock, oxidative stress or stimulation by cytokines [2]. Interestingly, in the amino-acid sequence of HSPB1, the same motif as in heavy chain of ferritin (an iron storage protein, FTH1) can be found (Fig. 1), and this motif is responsible for iron binding in FTH1 - the middle Glu (E) residue of HEERE motif is involved in binding of two iron ions. Therefore, a series of analogues of peptides including this motif were designed to check, if they are able to bind metal ions - iron, and additionally copper and zinc.

Figure 1. Amino acid sequences of HSPB1 (left) and FTH1 (right) with marked similar motif.

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Calcitermin and its peptide derivatives as promising antimicrobial agents with metal chelating ability

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The phenomenon of antimicrobial resistance is a global major concern and the necessity of new antimicrobial agents represents a scientific challenge that urgently needs to be solved. Thanks to the broad spectrum of activity and scarce attitude to induce antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) represent a rational chance to overcome the current drug-resistance crisis. Among several uncharacterized molecules that contribute to the overall antimicrobial activity of human nasal fluid, a 15-mer antimicrobial peptide named calcitermin (VAIALKAAHYHTHKE) has been isolated [1]. Calcitermin contains a metal-binding domain with three alternated histidine residues (His9, His11 and His13) and the free terminal amino and carboxyl groups. Based on our preliminary studies, it exhibits an improved microbicidal activity in presence of Zn²⁺ or Cu²⁺ ions. Moreover, calcitermin His-to-Ala mutants – where each histidine residue is replaced with one alanine – have different metal coordination modes, resulting in significant changes of the antimicrobial properties [2].

These promising results prompted us to focus on calcitermin derivatives where the peptide structure is modified to confer higher proteolytic stability and to study the impact of metal coordination on the antimicrobial efficacy of the peptide, in order to propose and design new therapeutic antimicrobial strategies. C- and/or N- terminal modifications have been introduced to obtain calcitermin derivatives resistant to proteases [3]. The terminal protection, however, can affect calcitermin metal-binding behaviour and therefore further investigations on the metal interaction with the synthesized protected peptides have been performed, in order to connect the antimicrobial activity with the complex-formation ability. The characterization of metal complexes has been performed by means of several techniques, including potentiometry, high-resolution mass spectrometry, UV-Vis, circular dichroism and EPR.

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Insight into the effect of the coordination modes of tridentate thiosemicarbazones on their solution chemical properties and cytotoxicity

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Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are promising chemotherapeutic drug candidates and their mechanisms of action are often linked to their ability to form stable and redox active complexes with essential metal ions such as iron and copper [1,2]. 3-Aminopyridine-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (triapine) is the most well-known representative of the α -*N*-heterocyclic TSC compound family. It has been studied in *ca.* 30 phase I and II clinical trials in both solid and haematological tumours, and a phase III trial is recruiting patients to test the combination of triapine with cisplatin during radiation therapy for cancer treatment [2,3]. Also other two orally available TSCs (code names: COTI-2, DpC) have entered clinical trials rekindling the research interest in this compound family [2].

The tridentate α -*N*-pyridyl TSCs (Scheme 1) possess a {N_{pyridyl},N,S} donor set, whereas the salicylaldehyde derivatives (Scheme 1) can offer an {O_{phenolato},N,S} binding mode. Triapine, as an α -*N*-pyridyl TSCs, is the effective inhibitor of the ribonucleotide reductase, an iron-containing enzyme, involved in the rate-limiting step of DNA synthesis. Its mechanism of action is reported to be strongly related to complex formation with iron ions.

Scheme 1. Chemical structure of the simplest a) α -*N*-pyridyl TSC and b) salicylaldehyde TSC

The {N_{pyridyl},N,S} donor set provides the possibility to form stable complex with both iron(II) and iron(III) ions, which seems to be a crucial factor in the anticancer effect [4]. On the other hand, complex formation with copper(II) ions has been recently suggested to be involved in the collateral sensitivity of multidrug-resistant cancer cells to the nanomolar-active TSCs such as the terminal *N*-disubstituted DpC or Dp44mT [5,6]. Additionally, intracellularly formed copper complexes of the tetramethylated triapine derivative were suggested to be responsible for the increased cytotoxicity as well as the potential to induce paraptosis, a caspase-independent form of cell death [6]. In contrast, the salicylaldehyde TSC derivatives generally display weaker cytotoxic activity in comparison to the α -*N*-pyridyl TSCs, most probably due to the presence of the harder Lewis base phenolato oxygen resulting

in a much stronger iron(III) preference over iron(II). However, their copper(II) complexes often are more cytotoxic than the ligands alone. Therefore, the actual donor set strongly influences the anticancer activity and the mode of action.

Herein, I am going to present an overview on how the structural diversity of the TSC ligands can affect the cytotoxic activity, the proton dissociation processes, lipophilicity, the stability and redox properties of the complexes formed with copper(II) and iron(II/III) ions based on our results obtained in the last years. It was also pointed out that not merely the exchange of the {N_{pyridyl},N,S} donor set to {O_{phenolato},N,S} has an impact on all these parameters, but variation of the chalcogen atom (S, O, Se), the substituents at the various positions or the combination with other pharmacophore subunit such as the sterane backbone can also alter the physical-chemical properties and the biological action.

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An ordinary plant with unusual peptides – could metal-shepherin complexes fight pathogens?

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The need to change conventional antibiotic therapy increases the interest in antimicrobial peptides (AMPs). Shepherins are very interesting examples of AMPs are shepherins – His-rich and Gly-rich peptides isolated from *Capsella bursa-pastoris* roots, which show antifungal, antibacterial and antiviral properties (Table 1) [1]. Shep I is characterized by six repeats of the Gly-Gly-His (GGH) motif, which is a good chelating ligand for Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions [2]. The most characteristic fragment of the Shep II sequence is the presence of the ATCUN motif [3, 4].

Table 1. Comparison of sequences and antimicrobial effects of shepherins

Name	Amino acids sequence	Activity
Shepherin I (Shep I)	GYGGHGGHGGHGGHGGHGGHGGHGGHGGGGHG	G(-) bacteria, fungi
Shepherin II (Shep II)	GYHGGHGGHGGGYNGGGGHGGHGGGYNGGGHHGGGGHG	G(-) bacteria, fungi, viruses

The experimental results showed that shepherins bind Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions very effectively, forming equimolar complexes. Metal ion binding affinity, secondary structure formation and the coordination mode strongly depend on the pH of the environment of a given system. Shep I binds Cu(II) ions by so-called "polymorphic" states that may compete with the ATCUN motif present in the Shep II peptide sequence. In addition, a tendency to form a β -sheet in an acidic environment were observed (both for ligand and complexes) with the greatest conformation changes in case of the Zn(II)-Shep II complex formation.

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1,10-Phenanthroline/Pd(II) complexes bearing arene ligands with N or O coordinating groups: synthesis and bioactivity tests

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Despite the clinical success of cisplatin, mediated by DNA binding [1], several drawbacks prompted the development of other Pt-based analogues and novel metal-containing drugs [2]. Due to the many similarities between Pt(II) and Pd(II), there is much interest in studying Pd(II) complexes as potential anticancer drugs. However, Pd(II) complexes do hydrolyse much faster than the Pt(II) analogues; thus, there is the need for strong nitrogen ligands, able to ensure the reaching of the biological target. Compounds with chelate or strongly coordinating nitrogen ligands obviate this rapid hydrolysis reaction [3,4].

In this contribution, we present three Pd(II) complexes that share the same bidentate ligand (1,10-phenanthroline) but differ for the second ligand (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of the studied Pd(II) metal complexes

First, the three compounds were synthesised and characterised. Second, they were tested for their stability and possible binding to biosubstrates. We analysed the interaction with natural DNA plasmid pUC18 with horizontal gel electrophoresis and the interaction with BSA with vertical gel electrophoresis. Absorbance and fluorescence tests were also done. Regarding their anticancer potential, MTT assays with selected cancer cell lines and cellular uptake, evaluated with ICP-MS, with lung cancer cells (A549) have been performed. The obtained results will be compared and discussed.

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Metal ion coordination – the eminence grise of antimicrobial peptides

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There are several ways in which biologically indispensable metal ions, such as Zn(II) and Cu(II), can impact the biological action of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs): (i) AMPs can either bind them, so that microbes cannot get enough metals essential for their life and virulence (removal of metal ions, nutritional immunity) or (ii) AMPs need the given metal ion to boost their antimicrobial activity – metal coordination can change the charge and the structure of the peptide, thus affecting (and hopefully enhancing) the AMPs mode of action *via* membrane disruption, production of reactive oxygen species, inhibition of cell wall or nucleic acid and protein synthesis [1,2].

To the best of our knowledge, up to date, although AMPs have been intensively studied for more than a decade, no data have been reported to demonstrate a clear relationship between the metal binding ability, structure, stability, and mode of action.

We focused on several families of metal binding AMPs, showing the effect of the preorganisation of the Zn(II) binding site of marine clavanins on their antifungal activity [3], the needle-like mode of action of the Zn(II)-pramlintide (amylin analogue) complex [4], the effect of charge on the activity of ovine SAAP complexes [5] and the impact of the local change of structure of calcitermin (human airways AMP) complexes on their antibacterial activity [6].

The most efficient complexes will serve as templates for a rational design of novel, more potent AMP-based therapeutics. Further improvement will be reached through the modification of the most promising AMP complexes using (i) chimeric compounds comprising AMPs bound to conventional antibiotics or antifungal drugs or (ii) specifically targeted antimicrobial peptides, in which the AMPs will be covalently linked to a targeting peptide.

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Copper(II) complexes with cyclam derivatives bearing phosphinato-bis(phosphonate) pendant arm

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Copper radioisotopes are perspective candidates for radiodiagnostic and radiotherapeutic applications due to their improving availability. Cyclam derivatives are often used and studied as Cu^{II} ion carriers as their complexes show a high thermodynamic stability and kinetic inertness. Here we introduce a new cyclam derivative bearing a phosphinato-bis(phosphonate) pendant as potential copper isotope carrier for radionuclide-based imaging and for treating bone metastases associated with several cancers. The ligand showed a high selectivity to Cu^{II} over Zn^{II} and Ni^{II} ions, and the bis(phosphonate) group was not coordinated in the Cu^{II} complex, strongly interacting with other metal ions in solution. The Cu^{II} complex formed quickly, in 1 s, at pH 5 and at a millimolar scale. The complexation rates significantly differed under a ligand or metal ion excess due to the formation of reaction intermediates differing in their metal-to-ligand ratio and protonation state, respectively. The Cu^{II} complex also showed a high resistance to acid-assisted hydrolysis ($t_{1/2}$ 2.7 h; 1 M HClO₄, 25 °C) and was effectively adsorbed on the hydroxyapatite surface. Radiolabeling with ⁶⁴Cu was fast and efficient and the complex showed high affinity for active bone compartments as shown by small animal PET/CT in mice.

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Mycobacterial SmtB/BigR4 $\alpha 5$ domain in zinc and nickel systems

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One of the possible mammalian immune system responses to mycobacterial infection is the increase of Zn(II) or other divalent metals concentration in phagosomes to a toxic level [1, 2]. The mycobacterial SmtB protein is a transcription regulator that in the presence of high concentrations of metals, dissociates from DNA and activates the expression of metal efflux proteins.

We focused our studies on $\alpha 5$ Zn(II) binding domains of SmtB/BigR4 proteins, looking at the coordination modes and thermodynamics of their Zn(II) and Ni(II) complexes as well as on the structure of whole, native protein [2, 3]. The study points out the specificity of metal-ligand interactions, the effect of His-mutations on the coordination properties of studied systems and interesting features of dimeric protein structure. The project can be considered as a bioinorganic introduction to the discovery of the new strategies in *M. tuberculosis* infection treatment based on Zn(II) and Ni(II)-sensitive mechanisms.

Figure 1. Proposed coordination sphere for a nickel(II)- $\alpha 5$ of BigR4 protein at pH 7.4.

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Metal-coordinated assemblies containing quercetin: a solution equilibria study for the development of pH-responsive drug delivery systems

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Stimuli-responsive drug-delivery systems (DDSs) have been developed to overcome the drawbacks of some chemotherapy drugs (low solubility, poor permeability and short biological half-life) as well as to achieve their site- and time-controlled release [1,2]. Among these, carriers based on polymeric systems have increasingly gained attention as polymers are characterized by flexibility and diversity in terms of composition and properties and they can be easily functionalized to respond to specific stimuli [3]. Moreover, “smart polymers” can change their structural and conformational features as well as their properties in response to external and/or physiological signals reducing drug leaking into the healthy physiological environment [4].

Although drug and carrier interactions are of paramount significance for the efficiency of the resulting delivery systems, a quantitative characterization of the molecular interactions occurring between drugs and carriers in solution has been rarely addressed.

In this work, the study of multiple equilibria in solution is proposed as a valuable strategy for the design and development of delivery platforms obtained by the assembly of polyacrylic acid (PAA), a biocompatible and pH-responsive polymer, metal ions of biological interest (Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) and quercetin (Que), to optimize stability, drug loading and release capability of the resulting assembly (**Figure 1**). It is well known that the pharmacological application of quercetin, a flavonoid with neuro/cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory and anticancer effects, is severely confined due to its low water solubility and *in vivo* bioavailability [5,6].

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the metal-coordinated assembly

The flavonoid capacity to complex either the metal ions or the polymer, as well as the interaction of the quercetin-metal complexes with PAA, have been investigated in aqueous solution at 25 °C and neutral pH by combining spectrophotometric and ITC calorimetric experiments to determine the speciation models and the energetics of the interactions [7,8]. Interestingly, although free Que and PAA were found unable to interact, the presence of the metal ion allowed them to bind and thus its features resulted to be crucial for the formation of the final assembly.

Kinetic stability studies have been carried out to evaluate the stability of the metal-coordinated assemblies: Que-M²⁺-PAA systems have a longer half-life than Que alone emphasizing that the formation of the final assemblies valuably improves Que stability.

Que release from metal-coordinated assemblies was investigated at 37 °C under different pH conditions, using dialysis and UV-Vis spectroscopy, to assess the ability of the metal-coordinated assemblies to promote the drug release in the acidic tumor microenvironment and to determine the release mechanism.

Overall, the results provided a detailed picture of the assemblies species formation, thermodynamics and mechanisms (involving multiple non-covalent, weak interactions) as well as the experimental conditions which are essential for the rational design and efficient application of these metal-based assemblies in solution. The strategy of examining multiple solution equilibria including different species can help to design efficient drug-delivery platforms able to simultaneously enhance the loading and the targeted release of drugs.

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Molecular recognition between the copper(II)-thiodiacetate chelate and a synthetic adenine nucleoside.

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We become working on molecular recognition between first-row transition metals and selected purine synthetic nucleosides, such as acyclovir [1] or N9-(2-hydroxyethyl)adenine (9heade) [2]. This work focuses our aims on the molecular recognition metal chelate-synthetic nucleoside featured in the novel compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{tda})(9\text{heade})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where tda = thiodiacetate(2-) anion (Figure 1).

Figure 1. H-bonded pairs of molecules in the crystal of $[\text{Cu}(\text{tda})(9\text{heade})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

This compound exhibits the following structural insights: a) An asymmetrical elongated Cu(II) coordination, type 4+1+1*, where * represents the very weak contact $\text{Cu1} \cdots \text{O2}^a$ of 3.062(2) Å ($a = -1+x, y, z$), close to the sum of Van der Waals radii of Cu (1.40 Å) and O (1.52 Å). b) The *fac*-SO+O(distal) conformation of tda. c) The rather unusual single Cu(II)-N21 bond from 9heade. d) The absence of a direct cooperation between the Cu-N21(9heade) bond with an unobserved N26-H \cdots O(coordinated carboxylate) interligand interaction. In fact ignoring such $\text{Cu1} \cdots \text{O2}(\text{aqua})$ interaction, the penta-coordination of Cu(II) fits very well to its typical square-based pyramidal coordination, type 4+1, where the Cu1-O8(tda) distal bond

length is only of 2.36 Å. But deepening in finest details we must observe that in the here reported crystal structure an O2-aqua ligand is involved in a water-mediated interligand interaction thorough two H-bonding interactions: (9heade)N26-H26A \cdots O2^a [2.757(4) Å, 154.2°] and O2^a \cdots O4(coordinated, tda) [3.107(4) Å, 129.7°]. This water-mediated interligand interaction leads to the observed perpendicularity between the purine-9heade plane and the mean-basal Cu(II) coordination plane, which define a dihedral angle of 85.2°

The *fac*-SO+O(distal) tda conformation was previously reported for the close similar compound [Cu(tda)(H(N27)hyp)(H₂O)]·2H₂O [H(N27)hyp = the tautomer H(N27)-hypoxanthine - Figure 2] [3], that is bound to the Cu(II) by its N29 donor atom. That makes it impossible an intra-molecular H-bonding interligand interaction with the Cu-N29 (Hhyp) bond. Consequently, the dihedral angle between the Hhyp and the mean-basal Cu(II) coordination planes (53.6°) is also far away from the perpendicularity.

Figure 2. Complex molecule in the crystal of [Cu(tda)(H(N27)hyp)(H₂O)]·2H₂O.

The main difference between both compounds consists in the coordination site occupied by the N-purine ligand. That occurs in trans to the Cu-S(tda) bond in the here reported compound, but in trans to the Cu-O(proximal) bond in the Hhyp derivative. Interestingly both complexes also have a Cu- proximal aqua ligand.

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Tetranuclear complex built by the molecular recognition between the Cu₂(μ-EGTA) chelate and μ-N7,N9-H(N3)-2,6-diaminopurine

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Reactions between the chelate Cu(NBzIDA) (NBzIDA = N-benzyliminodiacetate(2-) ion) with adenine (Hade) or its base pair with thymine (Hthy) afford two different compounds, [Cu(NBzIDA)(H(N9)ade)(H₂O)]·H₂O [1] or [Cu₂(NBzIDA)₂(H₂O)₂(μ-H(N3)-N7,N9-ade)]·3H₂O [2]. The role of Hthy of the base pair has not definitively enlightened, but seems to act controlling the available amount of free Hade in the reaction mixture.

This work start studies on molecular recognition between de dinuclear chelate Cu₂(μ-EGTA) (EGTA = ethylene glycol-bis(β-aminoethyl ether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetate(4-) ion) with purine nucleic bases, as 2,6-diaminopurine (Hdap) (see Scheme I).

At this moment, we are able to contribute with the structure of [Cu₄(μ-EGTA)₂(μ-H(N3)dap)₂(H₂O)₂]·7H₂O (**1**), which has been obtained as green crystals from reaction mixtures with ratio Hdap/Cu 2/2 and 1/2, the latter being the ratio found in the novel product.

Scheme I. Structural formulas of the H₄EGTA acid (left) and the tautomer H(N9)dap (right).

The chemical formula of **1** is in accordance with its crystalline structure (298(2) K, triclinic system, space group $P\bar{1}$) which has been refined to a value of $R_1 = 0.035$. The uncoordinated water molecules are significantly disordered. However, the structural resolution clearly reveals the most interesting aspects of the complex molecule (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structural representation of the tetranuclear molecule $[\text{Cu}_4(\mu\text{-EGTA})_2(\mu\text{-H(N3)dap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. For clarity, atoms coordinated to metal centres have been highlighted.

First, each semi- μ -EGTA acts as a tripodal tetradentate chelator for a Cu(II) centre, adopting the mer- $\text{NO}_2+\text{O}(\text{ether, distal})$ conformation, reported for various compounds in literature. Secondly, Hdap adopts the tautomer H(N3)dap, therefore with its dissociable H-atom linked to the less basic N-heterocyclic-(purine) atom. We can anticipate [2] that this tautomer favours a bridging dinucleating role, as reported for Co(II) [3], Cu(II) [4] or Zn(II) [5] compounds. This H(N3)dap tautomer also allows an efficient cooperation of Cu-N7 and Cu-N9 coordination bonds with N6-H \cdots O and N3-H \cdots O interligand interactions respectively, involving O-carboxylate EGTA donors. Thirdly we highlight the penta-coordination (type 4+1) for Cu1 and Cu2, in contrast to Cu3 and Cu4 centres that exhibit elongated octahedral coordination's (type 4+1+1) due to the additional aqua-distal ligand of their surroundings. Fourth, each $\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-EGTA})$ moiety bind N7 and N9 donors belonging to different μ -Hdap ligand. On all these insights we conclude that the bridging role of both EGTA and H(N3)dap ligands determine the tetranuclear dimensionality of the reported complex molecule.

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Iron complex imprinted polymers as heterogeneous catalysts for the green degradation of dye pollutants

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In recent times, there has been a sharp increase in the need for consumer products, leading to a flourishing of industries. This has led to a sustained increase in the pollution of ecosystems, mostly due to the discharge of effluents containing harmful compounds. Among the latter, dyes from textile wastewaters have become a major environmental issue [1]. In the quest for novel green methodologies of effluent treatment, the advanced oxidation processes catalyzed by iron complexes have become a promising technology. Nowadays, the state of the art in this field involves the development of heterogeneous iron-containing catalysts [2], which can be removed and stored after operation, as well as easily coupled to water treatment systems. This has proved to be challenging, though, since some of the catalysts display medium-to-low conversions and/or have high production costs.

In the development of new inexpensive and green effluent treatment alternatives, in this work we aimed to imprint polymers with iron(III) complexes to produce efficient Fenton-like heterogeneous catalysts for the green oxidative degradation of the methyl orange (MO) dye pollutant. Different metal complexes bearing commercial and low-cost ligands were assayed and their catalytic activity levels towards the discoloration of MO by H₂O₂ were assessed (Figure 1a). The best candidates were Fe(III)-BMIPA (BMIPA = di-(2-picolyl)amine) and Fe(III)-NTP (NTP = 3,3',3''-nitriлотripropionic acid), displaying above 70% MO degradation in 3 h. Fe(III)-BMIPA caused the oxidative degradation through two first-order parallel stages related to the formation of BMIPA-Fe-OOH species and the generation of reactive oxygen species. Regarding the complex with NTP, only the former stage was detected.

Both complexes were then employed to imprint catalytic cavities into molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs). The polymers showed catalytic profiles that were highly dependent on the crosslinking agent employed, with N,N-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAA) being the crosslinker that rendered polymers with optimal oxidative performance. Indeed, a conversion higher than 95% was observed for MBAA cross-linked MIPs (Figure 1b), possibly due to the formation of more hydrophilic and flexible polymers that favour the entrance and accumulation of the dye into the catalytic cavities.

These MBAA MIPs constitute the first examples of highly promising materials that can be used in the search for efficient and low-cost Fenton-like ion-imprinted catalysts, which could be coupled to dye wastewater treatment systems working under synchronous injection of H₂O₂.

Figure 1: a) General strategy followed in this work. b) The MIP catalyses the degradation of methyl orange in water using H_2O_2 .

We are currently undertaking some studies to extend the applicability of the catalytic polymers. We are testing new iron complexes, bearing ligands with different topologies, coordination numbers, geometries, and donor atoms. Besides, we expanded the range of pollutant dyes towards other important industrial examples, such as methylene blue and malachite green. The preliminary results are promising, and show that with some of the complexes there is a 50% decrease in the time needed for a complete dye degradation.

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An antioxidant boehmite amino-nanozyme able to disaggregate Huntington's inclusion bodies

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Huntington disease is known as one of the most devastating neurological pathologies that modern societies faces nowadays. Some of the key issues underlying the generation of such neurological ailment are the formation of Huntingtin aggregates in cerebellum, dyshomeostasis and chelation of Cu^{2+} by the mutant Huntingtin fibrils, and oxidative stress.[1,2] Up to date, very little success has been achieved in the treatment of Huntington disease.

In this work we report a novel amino-nanozyme based on the anchorage of a tetraaza-macrocycle onto the surface of boehmite nanoparticles. By means of potentiometric methods we determine the capacity of the macrocycle to quantitatively subtract Cu^{2+} from medium, while using McCord-Fridovich assays and in vitro mitochondria oxidative stress evaluations we figure out the notably high antioxidant activity of the resulting complexes. Furthermore, we also show the capacity of the amino-nanozymes to significantly reduce the mutant Huntingtin deposits in cells.[3]

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the antioxidant and disaggregating activity of the systems.

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A Simple Tripodal Ligand for Surface Decoration of Carbon-based Materials with Pd(II) Catalytic Centres

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Herein we present our ongoing studies on a novel ligand, HL, featuring a simple tripodal binding unit (N1,N1-bis(pyridin-2-ylmethyl)ethane-1,2-diamine) conjugated to an highly electron-deficient poly-substituted pyrimidine (6-amino-3-methyl-5-nitrosopyrimidin-4(3H)-one).

Polyamines bearing such pendant can be easily immobilized on graphitic sorbents such as activated carbon, carbon nanotubes and graphene [1-3]. This strategy has been successfully employed for the preparation of sorbents materials capable of binding target cations and anions from their aqueous solutions [2,4]. More recently, “Carbon Sorbent-Ligand-Pd(II)”-type materials, featuring graphitic surfaces decorated with Pd(II) complexes, have been investigated as catalysts, especially in cross-coupling reactions (in heterogeneous phase) [1,3] and, later on, as cathode catalysts for oxygen reduction reaction intended for fuel cells [5].

The new ligand L represents a tentative modification of the successful HL1 ligand [2,4] (Figure 1), aimed at a future comparative study, specifically addressing redox phenomena.

L retains most important coordinative features of HL1 (nature, number, spacing, overall disposition of donor atoms) as well as adhesive capabilities on graphitic surfaces thanks to the pyrimidine residue. Yet, since pyridines were previously found to take part in adsorbate-adsorbent interactions with related ligands [3], their insertion should provide further robustness to the hybrid material. Moreover, softer character of pyridines with respect to primary amines might stabilize Pd(II) complexes and/or the +2 oxidation state.

For the time being, we devoted ourselves to the preparation and initial characterization of L in terms of protonation and coordination properties (potentiometry, UV-Vis, XRD).

In solution, L is found significantly less basic than HL1, prompting for competition experiment in order to assess its metal binding properties. At the same time, HL and its complexes are much more inclined towards crystallizing, affording relevant structural data. L1 was initially thought to bind ions such as Cu(II) and Zn(II) resorting to 4 nitrogen atoms [4] (as the parent ligand tren does), yet available crystal structures are coordination polymers in which the ligand binds via 3 amine groups and additional donor atoms belonging to the pyrimidine residue of a second ligand. The more rigid and sterically constrained HL, clearly behaves as a tridentate ligand towards Cu(II), Zn(II) and Pd(II) instead. Moreover, a predominant bent conformation is found, where the pyrimidine residue, which is known for its tendency to establish anion- π interactions, remains closely associated to metal bound chloride ligands. Anion- π interactions and pyridine-pyrimidine stacking are also prominent in salts of the protonated ligand with simple anions (e.g. perchlorate).

Adsorption properties of the ligand on multi-walled carbon nanotubes have been assessed through adsorption isotherms: indeed, the ligand is easily and irreversibly adsorbed, even from relatively diluted aqueous solution (monolayer coverage reached in the sub-mM concentration range) with the final loading of the material depending on HL speciation in solution.

Overall, HL demonstrates great easiness of functionalization of graphitic surfaces and promises the possibility of unveiling more about the redox properties subtending to the complex interface phenomena happening on a Pd-decorated electrode surface.

Figure 1. Left: HL and HL1 ligands. Right: cartoon of a carbon nanotube decorated with a Pd(II)-HL complex (HLPdCl fragment is an actual depiction of single crystal XRD data).

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Effect of functionalization of kojic acid on metal ions complexation

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Kojic acid (5-hydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-4-pyrone, KA) is a natural γ -pyrone derivative, close to maltol, produced by *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* moulds, such as *Aspergillus oryzae* whose Japanese common name is *koji*. Its antibiotic, antibacterial, antifungal properties have long been recognized, as well as the inhibition of the rate of the formation of pigmented products and of oxygen uptake in the phenols oxidation by tyrosinase. In the last decade, KA has been used, in our group, as a building block in the design of new derivatives. The pyrone ring may be functionalized in position 2 or 6 to obtain bis or tris KA derivatives according to a low-cost and easy synthetic strategy [1, 2]. The use of linkers of different length, size and type provides different chelating properties for the complexation of several metal ions such as Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , V^{4+} and recently Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} and provides also different chemical and physical features that determine *in vivo* sequestering ability [3, 4]. The presence of two KA units coordinating with O-donor atoms of carbonyl and vicinal hydroxyl groups ensures that the ligand acts as tetradentate chelator with higher metal binding affinity than KA. Potentiometry, spectrophotometry and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ techniques, were supported by mass spectrometry, X-ray, calorimetry and quantum chemical calculations in the solution studies of protonation and complex formation equilibria and gave evidence of the formation of different stoichiometries of complexes MeL , MeL_2 , MeL_3 , Me_2L_2 and Me_2L_3 (Me = metal; L = ligand) depending on their hard or soft properties.

Figure 1: Kojic acid

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A biphenol tail-tied double scorpiand pyridinophane polyamine for the detection of anions and metal ions

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The receptor (**L**) consisting of two “scorpiand” polyamine subunits connected by a luminescent biphenol spacer has been prepared for the first time [1, 2, 3]. Each polyamine subunit is built up by reacting a tosylated tren moiety with a 2,6-(dibromomethyl)pyridine.

Potentiometric, UV-Vis, fluorescence and NMR titrations were performed to analyse the interaction of **L** with the amino acids L-aspartic and L-glutamic, and the corresponding dicarboxylic acid counterparts, succinic and L-glutaric acid. Furthermore, the interaction with Zn^{2+} was studied by the same methods.

Interestingly, the results revealed that this ligand can selectively recognize L-aspartic acid and L-glutaric acid at basic and acidic pH, respectively, and reveals an intriguing fluorescence response in the presence of Zn^{2+} .

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Thermodynamic, Kinetic and Structural Study of Cu(II) Complex of an Ethylene Cross-bridged Cyclam Ligand with Two Pyridine Pendant Arms

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Copper(II) complexes of tetraazamacrocyclic ligands exhibit both high thermodynamic stability as well as considerable kinetic inertness [1-4]. Therefore, the bifunctional chelating agents of copper radioisotopes can be employed for theranostics (e.g., ⁶⁴Cu with half-life 12.7 h for PET, ⁶⁷Cu with half-life 61.8 h for radio-immunotherapy [1, 2]). In order to find the best macrocyclic bifunctional ligands for possible *in vivo* applications of their Cu(II) complexes, it is necessary to study the thermodynamic and kinetic properties (dissociation/formation rate constants) of metal complexes [1, 3, 4].

Here, thermodynamic and kinetic properties of Cu(II) complex of macrocyclic cross-bridged *cyclam* ligand with two 2-pyridylmethyl pendant arms will be presented. The results will be rationalized as a consequence of molecular structure of Cu(II) complex and they will be compared with analogous cross-bridged *cyclen* and *cyclam* ligands having different pendant arms [5-8]. Results of this study could help in design of new bifunctional chelators for possible *in vivo* applications.

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Thermodynamics of Co(II) Complexation with Nitrate and Chloride in the [C₄mim][Tf₂N] Ionic Liquid

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Room temperature ionic liquids (RTILs) emerged as “green” solvents for numerous applications in the last two decades. RTILs are salts generally composed by an organic cation and an inorganic anion in the liquid state at 25 °C. They present high thermal and chemical stability, non-flammability, wide electrochemical window, low volatility and low toxicity [1]. Moreover, these properties can be finely tuned by systematically altering the structure of cations and anions. Due to these attractive features, RTILs have been used as “green” substitutes of volatile organic solvents in a number of applications related to the energy and environmental fields (e.g. separations, extractions, electrochemistry and catalysis). Among these, the use of RTILs for the separation and recycling of “critical” metals deriving from mining or high-tech waste was proposed in the last decade [2].

The recycling of cobalt assumed a great importance, due to the growing demand related to the use in key technologies, such as Li-ion batteries or motors for electric mobility [3]. The current processes for cobalt recovery in the hydrometallurgical route from aqueous solutions have some advantages such as method flexibility, high purity and low energy consumption [4] and some works on the application of RTILs in such process have appeared in the last years [4,5].

Among the available RTILs, those based on the alkylimidazolium (C_nmim⁺) cation and bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (Tf₂N⁻) anion (Figure 1) have been studied for metal extractions in recent years [6]. However, only few works were focused on the nature of the dissolved metals and their speciation in RTILs [7], despite these are fundamental data to understand the separation processes.

Figure 1. C_nmim⁺ cation (left) and Tf₂N⁻ anion (right).

In this communication, the results on Co(II) complex formation with nitrate and chloride in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([C₄mim][Tf₂N]) are reported. The interest in the Co²⁺ speciation with nitrate and chloride is due to the fact that the liquid samples containing the metal to be recovered usually contain high concentrations of these anions.

The nature of the species formed in dry and water-saturated [C₄mim][Tf₂N] is determined by means of spectrophotometric, calorimetric and theoretical methods. The results evidence the great effect of water on the nature and stability of the species formed.

Figure 2. Molar absorptivity of Co(II)/chloride or nitrate in water-saturated [C₄mim][Tf₂N]

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Investigation of the ligand topology for targeting multimeric G-quadruplex DNA

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DNA can adopt a variety of conformations besides the famous double helical structure B-DNA, such as triplexes, *i*-motifs, three/four-way junctions or G-quadruplexes (G4s). The later one is a supramolecular assembly of two or more tetrads, which arise from the hydrogen bonding network of four coplanar guanines. The stability and topology of G4 structures are mainly controlled by the alkali metal cation employed, the base sequence and the nature of the nucleic acid (DNA or RNA). Strikingly, a large number of putative G-quadruplex forming sequences have been identified in the genomes of human, microorganisms and viruses, and evidence suggest their pivotal role in key biological processes.[1] In particular, telomeres are guanine rich regions with putative G4-forming DNA sequences and have been associated to ageing and cancer. Therefore, G4 structures are currently tested as a therapeutic target to inhibit telomere elongation in cancer cells.[2] Telomere sequences comprise hundreds of TTAGGG repeats which forms a superstructure constituted by multiple G4s, termed as multimeric G4s (multG4s). It is noteworthy that from the vast human genome, telomeric DNA comprises one of the very few regions able to fold into multG4s.

Herein, we present our synthetic efforts to develop new organic molecules [3] able to interact with multG4s. We have prepared a family of linear, macrocyclic and cryptand ligands considering the first generation of G4 binders with triphenylamine moieties.[3] Our initial assessment on the binding abilities of the ligands has been conducted by FRET melting assays. The results of the stabilisation effect on multG4s, monomeric G4s and duplexes indicate the strong stabilisation effect of the cryptand-like ligands of multimeric G-quadruplexes together with a preference for multG4s over monomeric G4s and the double helical DNA structure. Altogether, the analysis of the melting variations highlights the importance of the molecule net charge and the reinforced structure of the ligands to bind strongly multimeric G4s.[4] Currently, we are exploring the application of these ligands as anticancer drugs by targeting the multimeric G4 structures formed in the telomeric regions of cancer cells.

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Anticancer activity and biospeciation of ruthenium(II) polypyridyl complexes

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Most of the ruthenium complexes developed for anticancer therapy over the last decades exert their cytotoxicity by mechanisms of action involving a ligand-exchange process. On the other hand, Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes possess a saturated coordination sphere and they are generally substitutionally inert compounds. This implies that their cytotoxicity arises from the entire complex and not from ligand exchange or covalent interactions with various biotargets. The mechanisms of action of these complexes depend fundamentally on the coordinating ligand set. *Tris*-polypyridyl complexes are mostly designed for photodynamic therapy (PDT). PDT is an emerging perspective for cancer therapy due to its spatial and temporal control [1]. The most promising representative of Ru(II)-based photosensitizers is TLD-1433, which is currently being evaluated in a phase II clinical trial for treating high-risk non-muscle invasive bladder cancer [1,2]. Other complexes with more extended aromatic (N,N) donor ligands can intercalate into the DNA and interfere cell proliferation [1]. Complexes without a polypyridyl ligand in the third position (see green and purple fields in the **figure**) are also known, *e.g.* metal complexes containing 8-hydroxyquinoline ligands (HQ) have shown promising results for the development of small molecule anticancer drugs. Ru(II) complexes containing two 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenantroline ligands and one (variously substituted) HQ ligand displayed sub-micromolar activity on HL60 leukemia cells [3]. Recently, anti-angiogenetic and antitumor effect of complexes $[\text{Ru(II)(bpy)}_2(\text{HQ})]^+$ and $[\text{Ru(II)(phen)}_2(\text{HQ})]^+$ (see **figure** for abbreviations) was reported as well [3].

Binding towards transport proteins *e.g.* to human serum albumin (HSA) may have an important effect on the distribution, metabolism and excretion of a metal complex. Advantage of HSA binding shows up by the enhanced permeability and retention effect of solid tumor tissues resulting in the accumulation of protein bound drugs close to the cancer cells. There is

good evidence that the preferential pharmacological target for a variety of anticancer drugs is DNA, therefore investigation of the interaction of Ru(II)-polypyridyl complexes with DNA is both highly relevant and important in order to get a deeper insight into the underlying mechanism of their action.

Figure: General structure and ligand set of the studied Ru(II)-complexes

The complexes studied in this work possess two identical polypyridyl ligands, and can be classified by the third coordinating ligand (**figure**) into three groups. Complexes in the blue field are developed for PDT and two of them possess a maleimide function on the third ligand, to enhance selective tumor targeting. Complexes bearing pbt, pbi (green field) or HQ (purple field) ligands showed remarkable *in vitro* anticancer activity, although little is known about their biospeciation.

Herein we report the *in vitro* cytotoxicity, aqueous stability, lipophilicity and luminescence properties of a panel of Ru(II)polypyridyl complexes along with their interaction with biomacromolecules such as HSA or DNA. Site-specific binding to these macromolecules was investigated via fluorescent site-marker displacement experiments. Covalent binding of the maleimide-conjugated complexes at the Cys-34 residue of HSA was followed by 2,2'-dithiodipyridine assay. Speciation studies were performed using *n*-octanol/water partition, UV-visible spectrophotometry, steady-state and time-resolved spectrofluorometry and ultrafiltration.

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Reactivity, stability, and biological studies of Pd(II) metallodrugs bearing active groups

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Cisplatin is undoubtedly the most widely known anticancer metallodrug, even though its clinical use comes with serious side-effects. This latter fact has encouraged the research and development of novel metallodrugs using different metals and/or ligands.[1] Palladium(II) complexes are promising candidates, considering the similarity of the metal centre to Pt(II) and the fact that their higher lability is compensated by the chelating effect created by ligands such as α -N-heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones.[2, 3]

In this work, we discuss the reactivity, stability and biological action of Pd(II)-thiosemicarbazone complexes in which the ligands coordinate in one or two different tautomeric forms.[4] The complexes' stability in DMSO (using NMR spectroscopy) and in aqueous solution (using UV-Vis spectroscopy) was monitored at fixed and increasing temperature. These assays are a crucial step to solve and describe the thermodynamics of the complexes in solution, as well as for the determination of the best profile to further analyze their biological interactions with models such as nucleic acids and proteins.

The complexes' interaction with biological models was evaluated with natural DNA and synthetic RNA polynucleotides, as well as with protein models such as bovine serum albumin (BSA) and lysozyme, using a variety of spectrophotometric and biophysical techniques. In addition, their interaction with double-stranded nucleic acid models (DNA and dsRNA) was further evaluated by fluorescence emission quenching assays. The different binding constants with the selected biosubstrates were quantitatively determined using the HypSpec 2014® software (HyperQuad, Leeds, UK). We will discuss the results achieved in the research group at the Autonomous University of Madrid as well as those obtained during the STSM at the University of Pisa.

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Continuous flow syntheses of Metal-NHC complexes with anticancer and photoemissive properties

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Taking advantage of the knowledge concerning the mechanism of formation of Metal-NHC (NHC = *N*-heterocyclic carbene) complexes in the presence of weak and inexpensive bases, we have recently designed simple, efficient and versatile continuous flow reactors for the synthesis of a wide range of metal-NHC derivatives.

More in detail, with the proposed setup (a PTFE tube containing potassium carbonate as a weak base) it is possible to convert the starting azolium salt and the metallic precursor, pre-mixed at room temperature to generate the *-ate* intermediate species, into [Pd(NHC)Cl(R-allyl)], [Au(NHC)Cl] and [Cu(NHC)Cl] complexes (Figure 1) using a sustainable solvent such as technical grade acetone and operating at 40 °C for 2 minutes (residence time). This simple microreactor guarantees high efficiencies for prolonged times and to obtain the final complexes in elevated yields and purity [1].

Based on these encouraging results, we successfully explored the weak-base-driven continuous flow synthesis of carbene-gold-aryls[2], metal-thiolates[3] and carbene-metal-amides[3] (M = Cu, Ag, and Au). Such macro-categories of compounds have received great interest for their application as valuable synthons, anticancer agents and photo-emissive materials (OLED, electrochemiluminescence, etc.), respectively. For these metal complexes a solution of the NHC-M-Cl precursor of interest and the organic substrate to be activated (secondary amines, thiols or arylboronic acids/esters) was injected into the potassium carbonate-based reactor.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of metal-NHC complexes object of this contribution

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New Zn(II) and Cu(II) Schiff base metal complexes based on 8-hydroxyquinoline scaffold designed for efficient cancer therapy

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8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) is considered a privileged scaffold in medicinal chemistry, having a myriad of potential pharmacological applications, due to its antimicrobial, antifungal and anticancer activities.[1, 2] A possible synergistic effect between the 8-HQ scaffold, chelated to a metal ion with potential for involvement in redox processes, is an interesting strategy, and several examples have already been reported.[3, 4]

Our group has been dedicated to the search of prospective metal-based drugs.[5, 6] Within this objective, a series of new Schiff base metal complexes of Zn(II) and Cu(II) based on 8-HQs substituted at position-2 with piperidine/morpholine type moieties were prepared (**Fig. 1A**), aiming to obtain stable, efficient and selective compounds for cancer therapy.

All complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, ESI mass spectrometry, FTIR and UV-Vis absorption spectroscopies, as well as by single-crystal X-ray diffraction, which helped elucidate their chemical structure in solid state and solution. The Zn(II) complexes were also characterized by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR).

All complexes were tested for their aqueous stability, and for their interaction with biologically relevant molecules, namely BSA (bovine serum albumin), through fluorescence quenching experiments and/or circular dichroism. The Zn(II) and Cu(II) complexes showed different behavior in aqueous media, with the Cu(II) complexes being more stable under these conditions, however, both compounds were able to interact with BSA. In fact, for the Zn(II) complexes this interaction enhanced their chemical stability in aqueous media.

A preliminary assessment of the ligands and Zn(II) compounds' biological activity was performed through *in vitro* cell-based assays, following their incubation in a pancreatic tumor cell line (BxPC3) for 48 h. Results showed that the compounds have low IC₅₀ values (between 15-30 μM) while the organic ligand precursors are not cytotoxic, anticipating promising results (**Fig. 1B**).

The next step involves the selection of the most active compounds and their encapsulation in liposomes and polymeric nanoparticles, since their association to these delivery systems is a valuable strategy that may provide improved solubility in water or physiological fluids, efficacy and selectivity for tumor cells.

Figure 1. **A)** Outline of synthetic procedure to obtain the Schiff base metal complexes reported in this work. **B)** Schematic representation of the preliminary biological results showing that the compounds interact with BSA and show promising biological activities.

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The effect of halogenation of salicylaldehyde on antiproliferative activities of $\{\Delta/\Lambda\text{-[Ru(bpy)}_2\text{(X,Y-sal)]BF}_4\}$ complexes

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Halogen atoms are widely used as substitution in medicinal chemistry to enhance bioactivity and bioavailability of drugs [1]. However, the influence of halogens on the biological activity of metal complexes is not always clear. Indeed, halogens seem not to play any role in the anticancer activity of piano stool Ru(II) complexes bearing 8-hydroxyquinoline [2] although conditioning not only the chirality but also the cytotoxicity towards cancer cells in a series of Pd(II) complexes with halogen-substituted Schiff bases and 2-picolyamine [3]. On the other hand, Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes have been widely investigated in cellular imaging, chemotherapy and photodynamic therapy due to their unique photochemical and photophysical properties, which can in turn be controlled by suitable variations of the auxiliary and primary ligands around the Ru(II) metal center [4, 5].

On the basis of these premises, a series of new chiral Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes (**1-5**) with general formula $\{\Delta/\Lambda\text{-[Ru(bpy)}_2\text{(X,Y-sal)]BF}_4\}$ (bpy = 2,2'-bipyridyl; X,Y-sal = 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (**1**), 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde (**2**), 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (**3**), 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde (**4**) and 3-bromo-5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (**5**)) were synthesized and characterized (Figure 1).

X= H; Y= Br

X= Br; Y= Br

X= H; Y= Cl

X= Cl; Y= Cl

X= Br; Y= Cl

BrByRu (**1**): $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{Br-Sal})]\text{BF}_4$

Br₂ByRu (**2**): $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{Br}_2\text{-Sal})]\text{BF}_4$

ClByRu (**3**): $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{Cl-Sal})]\text{BF}_4$

Cl₂ByRu(**4**): $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{Cl}_2\text{-Sal})]\text{BF}_4$

ClBrByRu(**5**): $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{Cl,Br-Sal})]\text{BF}_4$

Scheme 1. $\Delta/\Lambda\text{-[Ru(bpy)}_2\text{(X,Y-sal)]BF}_4$ complexes

NMR and UV-vis stability studies in solution have revealed that these complexes undergo decomposition being the release of the salicylaldehyde ligand faster in dihalogenated than in monohalogenated complexes.

In addition, it has been observed that halogenation is also an important factor in the cytotoxicity of these complexes and in their mechanism of action. The performed MTT antiproliferative assays in human cells revealed that the dihalogenated ligands confer enhanced cytotoxicity to the Ru(II) complexes compared to monohalogenated ligands. Nevertheless, independently of the number of halogens, the type of halogen also plays an important role in the biological activity of this family of complexes. On the one side, complexes bearing chloride are more selective towards cancer cells than complexes bearing bromide. On the other side, bromide as halogen is the best performer in terms of anticancer activity, probably because complexes with Br are more internalized than complexes with Cl. As common features of their mechanism of action, these Ru(II) complexes arrest cell cycle in G0/G1 and induce apoptosis. However, only complexes bearing Br are able to provoke a significant increase in intracellular ROS levels and mitochondrial membrane depolarization. Thus, oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction seem to be the mechanism of action for these salicylaldehyde Ru(II) complexes bearing bromide as halogen.

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Playing with gold(I) aggregates: phosphorescence emission vs singlet oxygen production

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Population of the triplet state in chromophores is an important aspect that plays a key role in many numerous applications such as photodynamic therapy, bioimaging, photocatalysis, light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) and oxygen sensing among others. In particular, singlet oxygen production stays at the forefront of research due to its reactivity as a synthetic reagent, as an intermediate in oxygenation reactions of polymers or as a reactive oxygen species (ROS) for biological purposes. Molecules acting as photosensitizers must have a populated triplet excited state higher in energy but close to the lower excited state of the oxygen, ¹O₂. Thus, molecules with populated triplet excited states are of great relevance in this field and this can be managed by the presence of heavy atoms. Metal complexes containing heavy atoms, such as gold(I) complexes, are scarcely explored in this field and deserve their investigation.[1]

On the other hand, supramolecular chemistry and thus, intermolecular contacts, are of great importance in these studies. This is particularly relevant in gold(I) complexes due to the possibility of establishing Au···Au contacts that may increase the intermolecular contacts and that also play a key role in the population of the triplet state and photophysical properties.[2,3]

In this work, we have explored the photophysical properties of a series of gold(I) complexes and we have managed to get the ideal conditions to modulate phosphorescence emission versus singlet oxygen production playing with aggregation.

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Guanine oxidation catalysed by Schiff base metal complexes: Effects “of” and “on” the DNA structure

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Transition metal complexes of chiral Salen derivatives are well known catalysts for the asymmetric oxidation of olefins [1-3]. In this context, we have recently found that nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of Salphen derivatives, such as those shown in Fig. 1a, have shown surprising catalytic activity for the selective epoxidation of styrene (Fig.1b).

Since analogous transition metal complexes are also effective and selective G-quadruplex DNA binders [4], we are currently investigating the possible catalytic oxidation of guanine DNA bases into 8-oxoguanine, and how this may affect the DNA structure and stability.

Fleming and Burrows [5] have pointed out that guanine oxidation is hampered when guanine is present within the G-quadruplex tetrad (Fig. 1c). However, computational studies support the hypothesis that guanine oxidation does not induce unfolding of a G-quadruplex conformation [6]. Besides the structural consequences of guanine oxidation on the DNA structure and how DNA G-quadruplex folding may affect guanine oxidation, we are interested in deepening the possible biological outcomes of selective guanine oxidation in native DNA catalyzed by our proposed Schiff base metal complexes.

Figure 1: a) Structure of a metal complex with promising catalytic oxidative activity (M = Ni, Cu); b) styrene epoxidation; c) schematic drawing of three guanine tetrads present in a G-quadruplex DNA.

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From direct labelling to the bifunctional chelator approach the story so far: the development of curcumin-based PET-radiotracers.

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Curcumin (CUR), a natural occurring polyphenol extracted from the dried rhizomes of *Curcuma Longa* L., is by far known for its therapeutic properties. Among these, colorectal cancer represents one of its best targets, as reported in cell cultures studies [1,2]. In addition, Curcumin metal complexes are promising metal-based drugs that demonstrated widespread applications in medicine [3] and can be exploited for developing new radiotracers [4]. Herein, an overview on curcumin-based radiotracers studied by our group throughout the last decade is reported, focusing on the synthesis, chemical characterization, radiolabelling, in vitro and in vivo studies.

Curcuminoid precursors were synthesized as reported in literature [5,6]. ⁶⁸Ge/⁶⁸Ga generator was eluted with 5 mL of 0.05 M HCl. The eluted activity was purified through a Bio-Rad AG50W-X8 cartridge. After subsequent elution, aliquots containing 50-80 MBq of [⁶⁸Ga]Ga³⁺ were added to the precursors (10 nmol) and the mixtures were incubated for different times and temperatures in a pH 4 buffered environment. To estimate stability, radiotracers were incubated with PBS (0.2 M, pH = 7.2), human serum (HS), and human blood (HB) at 37 °C for different time points and analyzed by radio-TLC. Lipophilicity was measured by HPLC-based method. Cellular uptake, internalization, blocking and efflux were studied in HT29 colon carcinoma cells line. PET imaging of the most promising radiotracer was determined in mice bearing HT29 subcutaneous tumour model after *i.v.* or *i.p.* injection with 3.7 MBq (1 mL, 0.2 μM solution) of radiopharmaceutical in sterile PBS.

Radiolabelling generally afforded complete (> 95%) and rapid incorporation under a range of mild and harsh conditions (from RT to 95°C) depending on the chelator. Stability of metal complexes in physiological media (PBS, HS, HB) resulted greatly enhanced when the bifunctional approach was followed rather than the direct radiolabelling of the derivatives, and it was generally > 60% after 2 h. The higher stability was also confirmed by mass spectra. Lipophilicity value is strongly affected by the chemical structure, and tends to decrease when hydrophilic chelators are used. In vitro uptake of the best derivative increased continuously in the first 60 min of incubation up to 12 KBq of radiotracer per mg of protein. At 60 min post

incubation, 83% of the total radioactivity was internalized. In vivo, xenograft tumours could be clearly visualized after 1 h ip of the radiotracer (2.27% ID/cc) although high accumulation could be also recorded in kidneys, intestine and lungs.

Curcumin was used both as direct chelator and as targeting vector following the bifunctional chelator approach. According to this latter, curcumin was linked to a series of chelators such as DOTA, NODAGA or AAZTA to improve the stability and potentially the biodistribution of their complexes with gallium-68. Both DOTA- and NODAGA-CUR were successfully labelled and showed interesting uptake in colorectal cancer cells (HT29), almost comparable stability in physiological media and promising lipophilicity. Particularly, [⁶⁸Ga]Ga-NODAGA-CUR showed improved labelling kinetics.

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PULIDORI AWARDS

Clavanins: where minor differences in structure cause major changes in antimicrobial efficiency

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In the last years, antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) attracted interest in the scientific world. One of the main reasons for their popularity is the fact, that in contrast to currently used antibiotics, pathogenic microbes developed very low resistance toward those peptides, even despite millions of years of coexistence [1]. These compounds naturally occur in a variety of organisms and play a key role in their innate immune system. Also, they often show synergistic properties to other drugs [2], which combined with low toxicity towards mammalian cells [3] makes them promising candidates for new therapeutics.

Among over 3300 already classified AMPs [4], six of them belong to the clavanin family. Clavanin A-E and clavaspilin are 23-amino acid, histidine-rich, cationic peptides isolated from the tunicates *Styela clava* [5-7]. In water they form a random-coiled conformation, but in the membrane-mimicking environment (*i.a.* SDS) they show an α -helical structure [8].

In this work, we focus on five peptides (clavanin A-E). According to the literature, at pH 5.5 they inhibit growth of the Gram-positive (*Listeria monocytogenes*, MRSA), Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) bacteria and fungi (*Candida albicans*) [5,9]. In addition, the formation of Zn(II) complex results in decreased MIC (*Minimum Inhibitory Concentration*) value from 64 to 4 μ M, thereby improving the activity of clavanin A 16 times [9].

Knowing that metal ions can boost the antimicrobial activity of peptides by changing their charge or secondary structure [10-12], the above-mentioned results inspired us to further investigate the correlation between coordination ability, structure and antimicrobial activity of Zn(II)- and Cu(II)-clavanin complexes.

All Zn(II) complexes show comparable stabilities and at pH 7.4, coordinated zinc by three imidazole groups, always involving His10 and His11 residues. Among Cu(II) complexes, clavanin C showed much higher affinity for Cu(II), coordinating it in a so-called albumin like binding mode via its ATCUN binding motif. The rest of the investigated clavanins, at pH 7.4, coordinated Cu(II) by three imidazoles and one amide group [13].

In biological activity assays, a clear metal-enhancing trend was visible for clavanin B against *Enterococcus faecalis*, where Zn(II) and Cu(II) complexes have shown 32 times lower MIC value than the peptide alone. Interestingly, despite that clavanin A and B differ only with one residue (K7R), this activity is not observed for clavanin A, emphasizing the crucial role of the Arg7 residue in this process. Among all tested agents, Zn(II)-clavanin C occurred to be the most versatile and the most effective, despite being very similar to Zn(II)-clavanin D [13]. Why? DFT calculations explained that bond lengths for Zn(II)-clavanin C are significantly longer than in the rest of examined Zn(II) complexes. This elongation is caused by the interaction with the neighbouring O=C-N-H group, originating from the peptide backbone. This

group is present directly below the Zn(II) ion, with the H atom ‘repelling’ the metal out of its binding pocket. This different organization of the binding site is most likely caused by the prefolding of clavamin C, which happens before the addition of Zn(II). This small change influences the later Zn(II) complex structure and its antimicrobial properties [13].

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Isoquinoline-based Eu(III) luminescent probes for citrate sensing in complex matrix

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Rationally designed Eu(III) complexes can be exploited as probes in the detection of analytes in biological fluids, by means of luminescence [1]. These complexes must be stable in aqueous solution, absorb and efficiently transfer the UV excitation to the metal ion (antenna effect). We succeeded to obtain this goal by including isoquinoline antenna into the ligand backbone. In fact, the luminescence of [Eu(bisoQcd)]⁺ and Eu(isoQC3A) complexes (Figure 1) significantly increases in the presence of the main analytes which constitute the interstitial extracellular fluid (i.e. hydrogen carbonate, serum albumin (SA) and citrate) [2-4].

Figure 1. Molecular structure of the Eu(III) isoquinoline based complexes

The optical response of our Eu(III)-based probes is selective towards citrate molecule, when a complex matrix is considered. Citrate molecule is a very important bio-analyte and the monitoring of its concentration is crucial in order to identify the presence of a disease [5]. When a simulated interstitial extracellular fluid is employed, the change of the citrate concentration gives rise to an increase of the Eu(III) luminescence emission intensity of [Eu(bisoQcd)]⁺. On the other hand, negligible or no change of the luminescence intensity was detected when the concentration of both hydrogen carbonate and SA is changed. This is due to citrate capacity to displace a higher number of water molecules giving a distinctive increase of the luminescence intensity. Moreover, the Eu(III) intrinsic quantum yield of the adduct is higher.

The obtained results candidate our europium complexes as viable probes for luminescence analysis of biofluids with complex matrix.

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POSTERS

New Pt(IV) complexes with nanomolar anticancer activity

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Research in the field of new platinum anticancer drugs continues to be enriched and upgrades the classical use of cisplatin analogues with the design and evaluation of new non-classical platinum complexes, such as polynuclear Pt(II) complexes [1], Pt(IV) complexes [2], and metallosupramolecular systems [3]. The main goal of all these endeavours is to create a better platinum-based drug for cancer treatment that is free of cisplatin limitations, namely low selectivity and acquired or inherent drug resistance, which lead to limited cisplatin efficacy and severe side effects. Pt(IV) complexes belong to non-classical platinum cytostatics, also known as "prodrugs", as they show their cytotoxic effect only after they are reduced to a Pt(II) complex exhibiting cytotoxic action [4]. One of the cancer cells characteristics is their hypoxic and more strongly reducing environment, which creates favourable conditions for the reduction of Pt(IV) to Pt(II). If this reduction of Pt(IV) to Pt(II) is achieved selectively ONLY in cancer cells, the selectivity of their cytotoxicity would be guaranteed. In addition, the presence of higher levels of biological reducing agents in cancer cells, such as glutathione and glucose, creates additional favourable conditions for selective activation by reduction of Pt(IV) prodrugs [5].

Herein, we report on the synthesis and structural characterization of pyrene-containing complexes of Pt(IV) - analogues of cisplatin and carboplatin with different substituents in the axial position. Their cytotoxicity profile has been studied on a panel of human tumour cell lines, as well as healthy cells. Furthermore, studies on their reactivity with biomolecules relevant to the treatment of cancer has also been performed based on NMR measurements. Proteomic analysis was done on chemosensitive and cisplatin-resistant leukemic cells (HL-60). Platinum uptake by the cells treated with the studied compounds have been evaluated in different cell fractions by means of ICP-MS, applying procedures used in our previous studies on metallosupramolecular capsules [6].

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Catalytic activity of new hybrid materials based on Pd complexes supported on multi-walled carbon nanotubes, graphene and graphene nanoplatelets

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Catalysts are often essentials for the correct course of reactions and to obtain acceptable quantities of products with a reasonable energy consumption. The Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction, which leads to the formation of a C-C bond, has been widely used for the synthesis of a large variety of compounds. By eliminating copper, as a co-catalyst, from this reaction, after demonstrating that Pd alone can be sufficient, the inconvenience of working in a protected atmosphere were remedied. Accordingly, many new Pd catalysts were developed, of both homogeneous and heterogeneous nature [1], and alternative metals were also explored [2-4].

Heterogeneous catalysts appear to be of more practical use, as they can be easily recovered from the reaction environments and can be reused if their stability allows. Various solid supports have been proposed for their assembly, including many carbon-based materials [5].

Here we report the synthesis, characterization and catalytic properties of new catalysts obtained by surface decoration of multi-walled carbon nanotubes, graphene and graphene nanoplatelets with Pd(II) complexes of tetraaza-macrocyclic ligands bearing one or two anchor functionalities (Ar-S-F ligand, Figure 1). Decoration of these carbon surfaces takes place under environmentally friendly condition: water, room temperature, aerobic conditions. All catalysts work very efficiently under mild conditions, giving similar high yield for Sonogashira copper-free reactions. Furthermore, they proved to be reusable for several cycles with good yields, especially in the case of those based on G and GNPT.

Figure 1. General structure of an Ar-S-F Ligand.

Figure 2. TEM micrograph of one of the catalysts based on GNPT after the second cycle. Insets: elements distribution maps.

Fresh and reused catalysts have been characterized by XPS, DRX and TEM (Figure 2). We can conclude that the supramolecular (non-covalent) and environmentally friendly approach used for the functionalization of the graphene supports is confirmed to be very effective for the production of robust and efficient catalysts despite the weak forces involved in the stage of their assembly.

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Macrocyclic compounds with transmembrane capacity and biomedical applications.

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The present study aims to develop macrocyclic compounds with transmembrane capacity and to study their potential biomedical applications to treat brain infections and neurodegenerative diseases. [1] These new ligands consist of a macrocyclic skeleton derived from a pyridinophane called pytren, to which hydrocarbon chains of 8, 16 and 22 carbon atoms have been incorporated with the intention of increasing its hydrophobicity.[2] In addition to that, N-metylation has been explored. The ligands have been characterized using the usual techniques (NMR, elemental analysis, etc.). Said compound has amphiphilic properties and the ability to form micelles. This capacity has been evaluated by fluorimetric titration of pyrene.[3][4] The results show that all the compounds form micelles, but through abiotic medium permeability tests (PAMPA) applied to estimate the permeability of the compounds by passive diffusion through the blood-brain barrier (BBB), it has been determined that PytrenC₈ has low permeability, PytrenC₂₂ shows be very insoluble and PytrenC₁₆ turns out to be the most optimal. Likewise, by means of potentiometric techniques it has been possible to determine the acid-base behavior and by means of X-ray diffraction the crystalline structure of the complex [Cu(PytrenC₈)](ClO₄)₂ has been determined. The next step to be developed in the future will be the study of the ability of said ligand to cross the blood-brain barrier.

Scheme 1. A. Structure of the macrocyclic compound Pytren Carbon 8. B. Macrocyclic compound in micelle form.

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Comparison of the metal binding affinity of the His32 and His329-330 sites of tau protein

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Neurodegenerative tauopathies are characterized by extracellular protein deposits of amyloid- β and intracellular aggregates of hyperphosphorylated tau in the brain [1,2]. Great number of publications supports that otherwise essential metal ions (such as zinc and copper) play an important role in the development of neurodegeneration [3-6].

The histidine imidazole nitrogen donor atoms are frequent metal binding sites in proteins and tau is relatively rich in this moiety. The 12 histidyl residues of the protein are well-separated and found in different chemical environment, hence we can assume that their metal binding properties – at least slightly – differ.

The comparison of the metal binding affinity of the His32 moiety from the N-terminal part of tau and His329-His330 residues derived from the R3 domain revealed that copper(II) binding is more favourable to His32 than metal coordination by the adjacent imidazoles; while the His329-His330 moieties provide a binding site for zinc(II) ions [7-9]. However, these conclusions were drawn from measurements carried out with ligands containing only one of the two binding sites. To compare the metal binding ability of His32 and His329-His330 in a single molecule we studied the complex formation processes of a chimeric peptide (Ac-TMHQDNIHHKP-NH₂) that contains the 30-34 residues (TMHQD) linked to the 327-332 residues (NIHHKP).

The potentiometric and spectroscopic (UV-Vis, CD) studies on the copper(II) complexes of the peptide revealed that in equimolar samples mononuclear complexes with 1:1 stoichiometry are formed with His32 being the main, although not exclusive, anchoring group for copper(II) coordination. In the presence of metal ion excess all histidine residues become independent metal binding sites, resulting in the formation of di- and even trinuclear species. Their coordination modes can be described with the involvement of imidazole-N donor atoms and deprotonated amide functions.

In the presence of zinc(II) ions only mononuclear complexes are formed. In the physiological pH range presumably a tridentate imidazole-N coordinated complex is formed, while in basic solution the formation of amide coordinated zinc(II) species is assumed with one of the adjacent histidine residues being the main anchoring site for the metal ion.

The results obtained for the mixed copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes support that the N-terminal imidazole nitrogen is the main anchoring group for copper(II) ions and zinc(II) ions are accumulated at one of the adjacent histidyl residues if both metal ions are present in the solution.

Our results suggest that the copper(II) binding affinity of the N-terminal His32 residue surpasses that of the adjacent histidine imidazoles of the R3 domain. Moreover, these findings

are in agreement with the hypothesis that Zn(II) coordination to the microtubule binding domains of tau contributes to the aggregation processes of the protein [10-13].

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Thermodynamic protonation parameters of a tryptophan metabolite (8-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid) and its molecular precursors: a potentiometric study at different temperatures

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Tryptophan (Trp) is an essential exogenous amino acid with a variety of physiological functions, playing a fundamental role in the functioning of the immune, gastrointestinal nervous and the central nervous systems, with a significant impact on the intestinal microbiota. Nearly 95% of Trp is metabolised via kynurenine pathway, the center of metabolism of peripheral Trp in most mammalian cells, the products of which belong to the group of 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) derivatives reported as anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-neurodegenerative and anti-cancer agents [1, 2].

Recently, great interest in 8-HQ metal complexes has extensively increased due to their wide range of applications. Furthermore, 8-HQA has been identified as siderophore in the gut of *Noctuid larvae*. This inspired the investigation on the chemical speciation, coordination and sequestering ability of this ligand towards several biologically relevant metal cations such as Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺ and even MoO₄²⁻ [3, 4]

The study of the chemical speciation of 8-HQA in aqueous solutions seems to be a crucial aspect to access the insights about its action. However, taking into consideration the activity of ligand into biological systems, studies carried out at 298.15 K are not sufficient. For that purpose, the dependence of the chemical speciation of 8-HQA and its molecular precursors on temperature is worth of investigation.

Herein, we present some preliminary results on the thermodynamic protonation parameters (protonation constants, enthalpy changes, entropies) of 8-HQA, 8-HQ and QA (see figure) in aqueous

solution determined by ISE-H⁺ (glass electrode) potentiometric titrations in KCl_(aq) at $I = 0.2 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$ and different temperatures ($288.15 \leq T / \text{K} \leq 313.15$).

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The Kinetics and Mechanism of Reaction of a Cubane-type Mo₃S₄ Cluster Hydride with Acids: Activation of Formic Acid

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Nowadays, formic acid (FA) is an attractive storing hydrogen system and the possibility of a direct reversible hydrogenation of CO₂ to FA and vice versa represents a vector for “green” hydrogen storage. Although the first report on FA dehydrogenation appeared in the late sixties, the FA potential as liquid hydrogen carrier was first highlighted in 2008 by Beller and Laurency [1-3], and since then a plethora of homogeneous mononuclear catalyst have emerged based on ruthenium, iridium and rhodium well-defined complexes as well as other in situ generated species. In the past decade, several first row transition metal catalysts have emerged to overcome the limitations and price of noble metals [4], but the use of second row transition metals other than noble metals is almost unexplored [5]. Herein, we present both experimental and computational studies showing that the cubane-type [Mo₃S₄H₃(dmpe)₃]Cl₃ hydride salt liberates hydrogen and carbon dioxide free of carbon monoxide from FA in propylene carbonate with no additives:

In particular, kinetic studies show that the reaction of this hydride with FA

is several orders of magnitude slower than those previously reported for related hydride clusters with acid, although the experimental results for the reaction leading to the formal substitution of coordinated hydrides by the HCOO⁻ anion can be still interpreted in terms of the previously proposed mechanism [6-8], the slower rate being a consequence of the lower acidity of FA with respect to the acids used in previous works. Following the initial reaction of the cluster with FA, there is elimination of CO₂ to regenerate the starting compound, and detailed computational studies show that the overall process can be considered to occur through the mechanism in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Proposed catalytic cycle for the conversion of FA to H₂ and CO₂ in the presence of the molybdenum cluster

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Anti-solvents and crystal growth in ternary copper (II) complexes with N-(benzyl)iminodiacetate(2-) chelator and synthesis of magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles in a robust platform for biomedical applications.

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Herein, we report the synthesis of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NBzIDA})(\text{Him})_2]\cdot 0.5\text{Him}$ [1] by reacting malachite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$), H_2NBzIDA (1 mmol) and Him (molar ratio 0.5:1:10) in 100 mL of water; a highly water-soluble reaction mixture facilitates the reaction. In this regard, a concentrated solution of the previously mentioned precursors was placed on a desiccator to diffuse diethyl ether as anti-solvent, resulting in crystals of optimal size of a dark blue compound (**1**) and a light blue compound (**2**), both suitable for single crystal XRD studies. Compound **1** was identified as $[\text{Cu}(\text{NBzIDA})(\text{Him})_2]$ (monoclinic system, space group $\text{P}2_1/\text{c}$, **Figure 1-left**), whereas compound **2** corresponds to its three hydrate $[\text{Cu}(\text{NBzIDA})(\text{Him})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (triclinic system, space group $\text{P}\bar{1}$, with two complexes and six water molecules in the asymmetric unit, **Figure 1-right**). Recrystallization of both compounds in water only yield crystals of **2**, evidencing that **1** is induced by the diffusion of an undetermined amount of diethyl ether.

Figure 1. Complex molecule of **1** (left). Asymmetric unit of **2** (right).

On the other hand, by a similar synthesis, we have obtained the compound $\{[\text{Cu}(\text{NBzIDA})(\text{heim})]\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (**3**) from its water solution (**Figure 2-up**), whereas diffusion of acetone (ACE) as anti-solvent yields $\{[\text{Cu}(\text{NBzIDA})(\text{heim})]\cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot 0.5(\text{ACE})\}_n$ (**4**) (**Figure 2-down**). Water and ACE are disordered. Interestingly both these compounds have similar

1D-polymeric chains of complex units, built by an anti, syn-carboxylate group of every NBzIDA chelator. They essentially differ from each other in the water content and the absence or presence of the ACE anti-solvent.

Figure 2. Polymeric chains and water in **3** (left). Polymeric chains, water and ACE in **4** (right).

Additionally, we report the synthesis of magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles; these nanoparticles are coated with gold to help oligomeric functionalization using thiol covalent binding. Our goal is to bind different organic molecules to serve as the basis for biosensing by using a proprietary optomagnetic device (Fig. 2); in this regard, we have achieved detection levels as low as 2ng/mL. The detection method is based upon moving and rotating magnetic nanoparticles using switchable magnetic fields at different frequencies to obtain a mobility signature of the nanoparticles; the detection of an analyte will be given by the change of this mobility [2].

Figure 3. Optomagnetic detector diagram (left). Patented optomagnetic device (right).

In summary, the reported structures represent examples of anti-solvent induced and packing (solvation or co-crystallization of anti-solvents) that do not affect the structure, however, they induce a faster crystallization and with notable improvements when it comes to forming crystals with better characteristics to carry out their crystallographic characterization. Our work suggests that transition metals such as copper or iron can potentially be used in the biomedical and pharmaceutical fields; for instance, Cu-based drug delivery systems or nanobiosensors for simple, rapid and low cost recognition of biomolecules or analytes for the food, pharmaceutical, biomedical, agriculture, counter bioterrorism applications.

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Use of biocompatible Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) as nanocarriers of antiretroviral drugs in the HIV treatment

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Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection can trigger profound immune deficits. The virus preferentially infects CD4+T cells, rapidly destroying massive numbers of such cells in the gastrointestinal tract and creating a systemic immunocompromised state [1-3]. This leads to the development of acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) and finally to death. MOFs are crystalline solids constructed from ions (or metal clusters) coordinated by organic ligands (Fig.1) [4,5]. These ions act like gum linking the diverse ligands in order to obtain long-range networks with different internal channels that give rise to specific properties like high porosity, diverse functionality and tunable structure. The size and the morphology of the MOFs also depend on the synthesis method and the working conditions.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of MOF-5

Different biocompatible metal-organic frameworks (BioMOFs) were synthesized to be used as nanocarriers for the administration of triple antiretroviral drugs combined, cART, (bictegravir + tenofovir + emtricitabin), (Fig. 2). Encapsulation and release processes were studied.

The cytotoxicity of the MOFs were evaluated in different non-primary cell lines related to the immune system as well as in Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells (PBMCs), isolated from healthy donors and HIV-infected patients. *In vitro* hemolytic effect and platelet aggregation assays were also performed.

Results demonstrated the capacity of these MOFs to encapsulate cART. The combination of cART could increase the innate immune response against HIV and provide a further effective strategy to decrease the DNA quantity of HIV and clearance of HIV reservoirs in CD4 cells from infected patients.

Figure 2: Chemical structure of cART

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Cu(II) ion selective chelators with therapeutic potentials

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Transition metal ions such as Cu(II), Fe(II), and Zn(II) play an important role in many key biological processes, thus their dysregulation and accumulations are a common pathological hallmark of many neurodegenerative disorders, for instance, Alzheimer's disease and prion disease. The above-mentioned metal ions by coordinating with proteins, including amyloid- β and the human prion, are able to induce their aggregation leading to the formation of senile plaques. Recent studies have also shown that metal-catalysed oxidation (MCO) of proteins is involved in the conformational changes in protein structure, which gives rise to oxidative stress, and consequently misfolded proteins.

As a potential treatment, chelation therapy aims to disrupt possible toxic interactions of metal ions and biomolecules by targeting specific metal ions and promoting redistribution or excretion. Lately, there has been an increasing interest in designing copper-specific small molecule metal chelators (SMMCs) and metal-protein attenuating compounds (MPACs) for the purpose of reducing Cu(II)-protein induced oxidative stress, and the resulting pathogenic consequences [1]. In the present work, the metal-binding ability of aroylhydrazones (MPACs) and salan-based ligands (SMMCs) were studied with both copper(II) and zinc(II) ions. Aroylhydrazones can act as moderate tridentate ligands towards divalent metal ions through the (N,N,O) donor atoms, while the designed salan-based tetradentate ligands, depending on the studied molecule, can coordinate via 3N,O; or 2N,2O donor atoms. In the case of the two aroylhydrazone derivatives, the complex formation was also investigated in the presence of a human prion fragment, namely Hu PrP 103-112 (Ac-SKPKTNMKHM-NH₂). The protecting role of these compounds during the oxidation of the prion protein fragment was also examined. The stability constants of the copper(II) and zinc(II) parent and mixed ligand complexes were determined by pH-potentiometry. Spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, CD) were used to study the speciation and bonding details of copper(II) complexes. The electrochemical parameters of copper(II) complexes were determined on the basis of CV measurements. The oxidation of the above-mentioned prion protein fragment in the Cu(II):peptide system was studied in the presence of the MPACs and chelators in the physiological pH range by the addition of H₂O₂ by HPLC-ESI-MS and MS/MS methods. Furthermore, ascorbate consumption assays were also performed.

The main result of our experiments is that the relevance of the compounds as metal-protein attenuators and chelators is proved. These ligands provide preferred binding sites in the physiological pH range in the case of both copper(II) and zinc(II) ions. They also inhibit the metal-catalysed oxidation of peptides and prevent ROS production [2,3]; therefore, they are promising candidates for further pharmaceutical development of Cu(II) targeting drugs in neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease.

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1*H*- Pyrazole azamacrocyclic ligands as superoxide dismutase mimics

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Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are related to neuronal death processes in neurodegenerative disorders as Alzheimer, Parkinson and Huntington diseases. Against ROS the first biological line of defence is the family of metalloenzymes called superoxide dismutase (SOD). These enzymes contain different metal ions in their active centres depending on the type of organism and on their location at the cellular level. Herein, we propose the design, synthesis [1] and characterization of three different ligands based on azamacrocyclic cores constituted by penta- or hexa-amines attached to an 1*H*-pyrazole aromatic spacer. We study their coordination with Cu²⁺ at different molar ratios and their applications as SOD mimics by using the McCord and Fridovich method [2].

Figure 1: Ligands based on azamacrocyclic cores constituted by penta- or hexa-amines attached to an 1*H*-pyrazole aromatic spacer.

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Iron chelation properties of hydroxypyrazin-2(1*H*)-one compounds and their neuroprotective effects in a cell culture model of Parkinson's disease

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Parkinson's disease (PD) is a debilitating neurodegenerative disorder in which patients experience progressive loss of motor control. Although the exact cause of idiopathic PD is as yet unknown, one of the pathological hallmarks of PD is dysregulation of intracellular and extracellular iron levels, and there is strong evidence indicating that localised iron accumulation occurs in the Substantia Nigra of PD patients [1]. When weakly bound or unbound by intracellular chelators, labile iron is redox active and can lead to an accumulation of free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can eventually overwhelm cellular antioxidant defences causing cellular damage. Due to the crucial role that iron dysregulation plays in the progression of PD, iron chelators endowed with one or more therapeutic modes of action have long been proposed as potential disease-modifying therapies for its treatment [2].

We previously showed that 1-hydroxypyridin-2(1*H*)-ones (1,2-HOPOs) are promising iron chelators in cell culture models of PD *in vitro* [3,4]. 1-hydroxypyrazin-2(1*H*)-ones is a closely related family of chelators to the 1,2-HOPOs but there are no reports on their study as potential iron chelators for the treatment of PD. We present the physicochemical evaluation and iron chelating properties of some novel hydroxypyrazin-2(1*H*)-one, as well as their neuroprotective potential in an *in vitro* cell culture model of PD.

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Coordination chemistry of Pt(II) and Pt(IV) complexes of tetraazapyridinacyclophanes and their interaction with mononucleotides.

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During the last years, research on coordination chemistry of platinum has aroused great interest due to their potential biological applications.^{1,2} Thus, one of the most important platinum complexes is *cis*-platin, which contains leaving groups in *cis* positions and allows it to anchor to the DNA molecule, being used effectively for the treatment of different cancer types. In fact, this complex has served as a starting point for the development of a large number of derivatives compounds with similar properties.³

Herein, we report the interaction of PtCl_4^{2-} with three polyazacyclophanes containing a pyridine unit as aromatic spacer (Figure 1). Different crystal structures have been solved by X-ray diffraction analysis. At acidic pHs, the metal ion is coordinated by the central amino group of the macrocyclic cavity and three chloride or bromide atoms, in a square planar geometry. Formation of $[\text{Pt}(\text{H}_2(\text{PY22}))\text{Br}_3]\text{Br}$ reveals the rapid substitution of chloride ligands in PtCl_4^{2-} by bromide ligands. However, the crystal structures obtained by reaction of these platinum complexes with $\text{KClO}_3/\text{HClO}_4$ show that the metal ion is coordinated through all nitrogen atoms of the macrocyclic cavity and two chloride ligands in *cis* positions that complete the octahedral geometry of the metal ion, indicating that oxidation to Pt(IV) occurs. The size of the macrocyclic cavity determines which of the complexes is oxidized. The UV-Vis and NMR spectroscopy has been employed in order to analyze the interaction of the Pt(IV) complexes towards different mononucleotides at acidic and physiological pH.

Figure 1. Structures of the studied tetraazapyridinacyclophanes ligands.

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Complex formation equilibria of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with a family of kojic acid derivatives. A potentiometric and spectrophotometric study.

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In several countries, the industrialization and urbanization processes have increased the heavy metal input and their accumulation into atmosphere, soil, water, food and humans presents a potentially high environmental risk. Some of them, lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd), widely dispersed in the environment, are considered the most toxic for animals, plants and human being with no biological functions and homeostasis mechanism. Moreover, the heavy metal toxicity depends on contaminated species, specific metal, concentration and pH. In this context, many researchers tried to develop efficient, reliable and cost-effective methods to treat these metal ions [1]. We propose the use of chelating agents obtained by easily joining two kojic acid moieties through linear diamines of variable length (ethylene diamine, propane-1,3-diamine, and butane-1,4-diamine), which react with OH group in position 2 [2]. Potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ at 25°C and 0.1 M ionic strength with the three ligands in Figure 1 allowed us to evaluate the complexation model and the related stability constants.

- n = 2 2,2'-[ethane-1,2-diylbis(iminomethanediyl)]bis(5-hydroxy-4H-pyran-4-one (S2)
n = 3 2,2'-[propane-1,3-diylbis(iminomethanediyl)]bis(5-hydroxy-4H-pyran-4-one (S3)
n = 4 2,2'-[butane-1,4-diylbis(iminomethanediyl)]bis(5-hydroxy-4H-pyran-4-one (S4)

Figure 1: Kojic acid derivatives, S2, S3 and S4.

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Co-encapsulation of iron-saturated lactoferrin and Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes – protection and sustained release

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Lactoferrin (Lf) is a globular protein with a mass of about 80 kDa, belonging to the transferrin family. Due to its biological activity and several bacteriostatic and anti-inflammatory properties, it is of interest to many researchers. This protein is found in many body fluids and mucous secretions of mammals. Lf has two specific binding sites where metal ions can be coordinated, most often Fe³⁺, to which it has a very high affinity. Moreover, other ions such as Mn³⁺, Ga³⁺, Al³⁺, VO²⁺, Co³⁺, Cu²⁺ can be coordinated by Lf; however, little is known about the biological consequences of such modifications.

So far a large number of possible applications of Lf have been proposed in antimicrobial and anticancer therapies as a potent adjuvant [1]. It has been proven that Fe³⁺ ion saturation level influences its biological activity and potential synergistic effect with drugs [2]. Furthermore, Lf saturated with Mn³⁺ ions exhibits prebiotic properties toward bacteria of the *lactobacillus* genus [3]. The prebiotic and anticancer effect of Lf is particularly interesting in the context of its use as a co-agent in colorectal cancer therapy.

Herein, in this work, we will present a study aimed at developing a system for encapsulation of iron-saturated Lf as well as its co-encapsulation with Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes. Our main goal was to prevent protein digestion under simulated gastric conditions. The system based on versatile polymer from the Eudragit family [4] will be presented. The encapsulation protocol, yield, and efficiency for protein encapsulation will be demonstrated. The protective role of the obtained microparticles against Lf proteolysis in simulated fluids (in accordance with European Pharmacopoeia 10) will be discussed. Furthermore, the co-encapsulation of ruthenium(II) polypyridyl complexes of the type [Ru(dip)₂L]Cl₂ (where dip - 4,7-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline, L – a derivative of bipyridyl ligand), whose anti-cancer and antimetastatic properties have been described previously in the literature, will be presented [5]. Financial support for P.G-M. from the National Science Center in Poland is acknowledged (grant no 2019/35/N/NZ7/02202)

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**The Irving-Williams series and 8-hydroxyquinaldic acid (8-HQA):
a thermodynamic study of 8-HQA interaction towards
Mn²⁺, Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺**

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Excluding skin cancers, colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most common cancer diagnosed in the United States,[1] being the second most frequently occurring cancer (after breast cancer) in Europe.[2]

On the permanent chase of more efficient treatment, 8-hydroxyquinaldic acid (or 8-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid, 8-HQA) is rising as an interesting compound to exploit. Recently, K. Walczak and co-workers [3] studied the toxicity of 8-HQA and its effect *in vitro*, reporting its high antiproliferative and anti-migratory activity on colon cancer cells, being not toxic for normal colon cells. Furthermore, research on CRC is also finding increasing evidence that dysbiosis of the intestinal microbiota is closely related to this disease,[4] being microbiome highly dependent on metal homeostasis, having metals as iron, manganese, zinc, and copper playing a relevant role.[5, 6]

Being 8-HQA the end-metabolite of one of the major tryptophan metabolic pathways in the gastrointestinal tract (the kynurenine pathway) and a well-known metal chelator,[7,8] it will be very interesting to understand more about its possible influence on metal homeostasis in the gut, and has being the aim of our resent research. We have been working on characterization of the thermodynamic solution behaviour of Fe²⁺/8-HQA and Fe³⁺/8-HQA systems, for a better understanding of 8-HQA possible action as siderophore.[7]

Distribution diagram of $M_pL_qH_r$ species as a function of pH in the Fe²⁺/8-HQA system. From ref. [7]

Following the same interest, we present herein the study of the binding ability of 8-HQA towards the divalent ions of the first transition series (Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}). The relative stabilities of formed transition metal complexes is discussed in terms of the Irving–Williams series rule. The sequestering ability and selectivity of 8-HQA towards the mentioned metal cations series is also evaluated. 8-HQA/ M^{2+} systems were investigated by different methods being the ISE- H^+ (glass electrode) potentiometric and UV/Vis spectrophotometric results discussed. Data were obtained from experiments performed in $\text{KCl}_{(\text{aq})}$ at $I = 0.2 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$.

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Gold(I) and Silver(I) Carbamates the Most Biological Potent Complexes Between Different Unexplored Transition Metal Carbamates

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Cancer is a public health problem and is one of the main causes of death worldwide.¹ Few platinum complexes have been efficaciously administered against various types of tumours in admixture with other pharmaceuticals. However, the formers are associated to some significant drawbacks such as severe side effects, acquired resistance phenomena and necessity of hospitalization for treatment.² Therefore, many compounds based on the majority of transition metals of the periodic table have been explored as anticancer drug candidates, and a diversity of specific combinations of metals and ligands have shown promise.^{3,4} Metal N,N-dialkylcarbamates constitute a class of molecular compounds of general formula $[M(O_2CNR_2)_n]_m$, due to the simplicity and generality of the preparative methods, metal carbamates have been reported for almost all the transition metals and also main group elements with metallic character.^{5,6} Metal carbamates are traditionally handled and stored under inert (anhydrous) atmosphere, and this “dogma” has prevented the exploration of potential biological applications. Notwithstanding, some platinum(IV) complexes (including mixed Ru-Pt compounds) with an axial carbamato ligand have been recently investigated for biological applications, showing a substantial aqueous stability and an interesting cytotoxicity profile.⁷

In the light of these results, we report a screening study aimed to assess for the first time the air and aqueous stability and the biological potential of a number of carbamato complexes of metals belonging to groups 4-5, 7-9 and 11 and tin.

The air-stable $[Ag(O_2CNEt_2)]$ and $[Au(O_2CNMe_2)(PPh_3)]$ complexes emerged as water-robust, strongly cytotoxic and antimicrobial agents, exerting their action mainly through mitochondrial dysfunction.

Their dual potential as antibacterial and antitumor agents revealed their interest as prophylactic in chemotherapy cancer treatment.⁸

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Cyclodextrins as anticancer drug delivery vehicle

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In recent years, a great research effort has been made to obtain new drugs that reduce the adverse effects and the absence of selectivity of the conventional antineoplastic agents. On the other hand, the hypoxic conditions that occur in solid tumors cause some resistance to treatment by chemotherapy or radiotherapy [1].

This work is part of a research line aimed at obtaining new anticancer drugs. The synthesis of an antineoplastic drug that combines therapeutic and diagnostic properties (theranostics) has been carried out and it has been studied its inclusion in β -cyclodextrins, compounds that are excellent carriers of apolar compounds, due to their ability to form inclusion complexes soluble in aqueous solution because of the hydrophilic nature of the cyclodextrin. Theranostics are prodrugs that release a cytotoxic compound using the characteristic metabolism of cancer cells and, simultaneously, allow its detection [2].

The proposed antineoplastic prodrug, based on a 6-amino-2-naphthoic acid skeleton attached to a disulfide bond, should liberate the cytotoxic compound only within the cancer cell, due to the particular conditions presented by the microenvironment of the tumor: a reducing environment and overexpression of intracellular thiol groups (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cytotoxic compound obtained by reduction of the disulfide bond of the prodrug.

The carbonyl sulfide would be responsible for the destruction of the tumor cell. On the other hand, the change in the fluorescence emission maximum of the fluorophore before and after the disulfide cleavage would cause a modulation of the fluorescence signal that would allow detection of tumor cells.

As a consequence of the apolar character of the synthesized prodrug, its inclusion complex with commercial β -cyclodextrin (CDm) and with a dimer of β -cyclodextrin (CDd) linked by a disulfide bond, prepared by us, has been studied (Figure 2).

We investigated the inclusion complex formation by UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopy of prodrug-CDm, prodrug-CDd and NaftLi-CDm (where NaftLi denote the Li salt of 6-amino-2-naphthoic acid). We maintained constant concentration of guest in all experiments and we worked in such conditions that $[CD]_0 \gg [guest]_0$.

Figure 2. Inclusion complex formation of monomeric and dimeric β -cyclodextrin.

The inclusion constant was calculated according to the Benesi–Hildebrand method [3], considering that the guest fluorescence intensity changes with the cyclodextrin concentration, adjusting the experimental data to the equation valid for 1:1 stoichiometries:

$$\frac{1}{F - F_0} = \frac{1}{(F_\infty - F_0)K[\beta - CD]} + \frac{1}{F_\infty - F_0}$$

where F is the equilibrium fluorescence intensity, and F_0 and F_∞ are fluorescence intensity in absence of cyclodextrin and when all the guest molecules are complexed, respectively.

The fluorescence increases with the concentration of cyclodextrin in both the formation of the prodrug-CDm and in NaftLi-CDm complexes because the cavity of the cyclodextrin protects the guest from quenching. The fluorescence intensity decreases with increasing concentrations of cyclodextrin in the formation of the prodrug-CDD complex due to the Photoinductive Electronic Transfer (PET) between the dimer sulfur atoms and the fluorophore that would act as an electron acceptor. At 25 °C, constant pH (6.5-6.8), $\lambda_{\text{excitation}} = 360$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{emission}} = 420.9$ nm, the values of the binding constants were: 3102 ± 9 M⁻¹ (prodrug-CDD), 691 ± 4 M⁻¹ (prodrug-CDm) and 447 ± 1 M⁻¹ (NaftLi-CDm).

Finally, the cytotoxicity of the inclusion complexes was tested in colon cancer cells (HCT116) and fibroblast healthy cells as control under both normoxia and hypoxia conditions, showing no cytotoxic activity in the cell viability assays.

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- Cyclodextrins are good candidates for transporting and solubilizing apolar drugs such as the compound prepared in this work.
- It has been possible to measure the association constants, showing the formation of very stable complexes, being the complex with the β -cyclodextrin dimer stronger than the commercial β -cyclodextrin one. This stability was also a drawback since it prevented the release of the drug out of the cyclodextrin cavity, which agrees with the biological studies.

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Specific Zn(II) binding sites in Aspf2 zincophore from *Aspergillus fumigatus*

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One of the biggest problems with finding new antifungal drugs is the fact that fungi share basic metabolic pathways and basic cellular mechanisms with their human hosts cells. Consequently, in order to design a highly specific antifungal drug, it is necessary to understand the difference in human and fungal metabolism [1]. One of them is the mechanism of zinc uptake, which is one of the critical aspects of fungal virulence and survival [2,3]. After the invasion of the host cells, *Aspergillus fumigatus* secretes an extracellular zincophore Aspf2. It is a 310 amino acid protein that is able to sequester Zn(II) ions from the host. The secreted Aspf2 zincophore is released into surrounding host cells, where it binds the free Zn(II) or bound to host zinc-binding proteins and delivers it to the fungal pathogen through physical interaction with the ZrfC transporter [5] (Figure 1).

Mass spectrometry, potentiometry, UV-Vis, CD and NMR spectroscopy allowed to determine the stoichiometry, precise stability constants and pH-dependent species distribution diagrams for the studied systems, determine the geometry and binding mode of metal ions, but also give us the information about the secondary structure. Among the studied Aspf2 regions, the most probable Zn(II) binding site in Aspf2 is its unstructured C-terminal region PNCHTHEGGQLHCT. At around pH 7.4, Zn(II) binds to two histidine imidazoles and two cysteine thiols from this sequence with a {2N_{im}, 2S⁻} binding mode.

The C-terminal region of the Aspf2 protein, Ac-PNCHTHEGGQLHCT, has also a high affinity towards another biologically relevant metal ion for microbes, like Ni(II), which could theoretically compete with Zn(II) for the binding sites in its zincophore. At physiological pH (pH 7.4) the coordination of Ni(II) to the C-terminal region of the Aspf2 zincophore also involves two histidine imidazoles and two cysteine thiols with a {2N_{im}, 2S⁻} binding mode, but at higher pH values, the coordination mode changes to a {3N⁻, S⁻} one.

The Aspf2 zincophore strongly prefers to bind Zn(II) over Ni(II) ions, even in a theoretical situation in which equimolar amounts of both metals would be available. The {2N_{im}, 2S⁻} binding mode, typical for zinc fingers [6], seems to be more tempting for Zn(II) than for Ni(II) ions. All the obtained results may suggest that the PNCHTHEGGQLHCT region of the Aspf2 zincophore may probably serve as a targeting molecule that is able to bring an appropriately bound therapeutic to the proximity of *Aspergillus fumigatus*, specifically passing over the Zn(II) ion to the ZrfC transporter, as in the case of the Pra1 zincophore present in *Candida albicans* [7].

Figure 1. Schematic model of *Aspergillus fumigatus* zinc scavenging from host cells. After invasion of the host cell, AspF2 is expressed and secreted. It binds Zn(II), either in the form of free Zn(II) ions or from zinc-binding proteins of the host. Reassociation with the *A. fumigatus* cell surface and Zn(II) transportation into the cell occurs via a AspF2-ZrfC interaction.

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Preparation and characterization of novel BiOI/Graphene material heterostructures with efficient visible-light photocatalytic activity

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Photocatalytic solar energy conversion is considered one of the most promising approaches for solving energy and environmental issues [1, 2]. Recently, bismuth oxyhalides (BiOX, X = Cl, Br, I) have attracted a great deal of attention for their potential application in photocatalysis. BiOX are two-dimensional (2D) semiconductors with a strong light response to boost solar energy conversion. All of them are chemically stable and nontoxic solids with a unique layered structure characterized by $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ slabs interleaved by double slabs of halogen atoms. The generated internal static electric fields between the $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ positive layers and the negative halogen layers seem to induce the separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs, which is favourable for the photocatalytic performance of BiOX. Despite this, the fast recombination of photogenerated charges in BiOX remains the main reason limiting the efficiency of these materials as photocatalysts [3].

To improve the photocatalytic activity of BiOX, it is essential to structure them with other materials capable of hindering the recombination of photogenerated charges in BiOX. In this sense, the combination of BiOX with 2D materials with excellent electron-acceptor/transport properties as graphene materials is an attractive way to prepare heterostructures with enhanced photocatalytic properties. But to obtain efficient photocatalysts an intimate interfacial contact between both structures is necessary.

Here we present the preparation and characterization of composites consisting of BiOI nanostructures ensembled to graphene materials (GM). In order to favour the contact between both nanostructured solids, graphene nanoplatelets and graphene oxide adequately functionalized have been employed as GM. Thus, the GM surface functions can act as nucleation sites for BiOI crystallization. Furthermore, due to the large surface areas of GM, a homogeneous spreading of BiOI nanolayers on GM is observed. The resulting BiOI/GM hybrid materials show morphological changes with respect to BiOI (Figure 1), although the main crystal orientations of BiOI remain unchanged (Figure 2). In addition, an improvement in the photocatalytic activity, under visible light irradiation, for rhodamine B degradation of the hybrids have been observed in relation to that shown by pure BiOI. This fact can be attributed to the excellent conductivity for electron capture and transport of GM, which may effectively suppress the charge recombination of the electron-hole pairs.

Figure 1. SEM images of: a) BiOI and b) BiOI/GM

Figure 2. DRX of BiOI and BiOI/GM

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Microwave-assisted synthesis of tris-heteroleptic polypyridyl Ru(II) complexes with asymmetric ligands and their biological activity

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Polypyridyl Ru(II) complexes have attracted particular attention due to their interesting biological and photophysical properties, which can be modulated by an appropriate selection of ligands. It has been proven that the cytotoxic effect combined with the antimetastatic effect on cancer cells can be properly tuned by changing their structure, both by replacing the entire ligand and by introducing appropriate substituents into the ligand. [1] It is also possible to obtain a specific type of photoreactivity in order to use the complex as a photosensitizer in PDT therapy and shift the absorption of compounds towards longer wavelengths through the appropriate selection of coordinated ligands.

The three new tris-heteroleptic Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes were synthesized. The 4,7-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dip) and 2,2-bipyridine (bpy) ligands were chosen to ensure the appropriate biological properties of the complexes, while 2,3-bis(2-pyridyl)quinoxaline (dpq) and its derivatives were applied to shift the MLCT transition of the compounds to longer wavelengths. The modification of the synthetic protocol with the use of microwave irradiation allowed us to reduce the reaction times and achieve high yields of the desired complexes. During each synthesis, a mixture of isomers was obtained and separated with the use of preparative chromatography.

The prevalent isomers of each synthesized Ru complex were characterized by determination of the molar absorption and octanol/water partition coefficients and subjected to preliminary biological studies. Each of the compounds showed a relatively high value of the photodynamic index (PI). Irradiation with visible light greatly enhanced their antiproliferative properties. The phototoxicity of the compounds was caused by the generation of ¹O₂ and H₂O₂. An additional benefit came from the enhanced activity of the Ru complexes in inhibiting cancer cells detachment upon visible light irradiation. This could provide the basis for exploring a potential combination of PDT and antimetastatic therapy using Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes.

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Effects of subacute cadmium exposure and subsequent deferiprone treatment on cadmium accumulation and essential elements' homeostasis in mouse brain

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Cadmium (Cd) is a multi-organ toxin with long biological half-life in humans [1]. Numerous studies demonstrated that Cd exerts severe neurological disorders [2]. A case control study revealed a possible association between increased serum Cd concentration in female and male patients and Parkinson disease [3]. Recent review highlighted the significance of Cd for the pathogenesis of Alzheimer disease [4]. It has been demonstrated that Cd induces oxidative damage on the brain [5]. Cd is considered to elicit oxidative stress by disturbing the homeostasis of the essential elements [6]. The data about the interactions of Cd and essential elements in brain are scarce and conflicting [6, 7].

Deferiprone (DFP) is an oral chelating agent approved by the U. S. Food and Drug Administration for treatment of iron overload [8]. It has been reported that the intraperitoneal administration of DFP decreases Cd concentration in the kidneys, liver, intestine and heart of Cd-exposed rats compared to untreated controls [9]. To the best of our knowledge, there is no available information about the potential of deferiprone as an oral antidote for treatment of Cd poisoning. Furthermore, there are no available data for the effect of DFP on Cd accumulation in brain and essential elements' homeostasis of Cd-intoxicated animals. In this study we provide the first results about the effect of oral administration of deferiprone on Cd accumulation and essential elements' homeostasis in the brain of Cd-exposed mice. Adult male ICR mice were randomized into four experimental groups: untreated controls – obtained distilled water for 28 days; Cd-exposed group – exposed to 18 mg/kg body weight (b.w.) Cd(II) acetate for 14 days followed by administration of distilled water for two weeks; Cd+DFP (low dose) – obtained Cd(II) acetate for two weeks followed by treatment with 19 mg/kg b.w. DFP for 14 days; Cd+DFP (high dose) – exposed to Cd(II) acetate for 14 days

subsequently treated with high dose DFP (135 mg/kg b.w.) for another 14 days. Brains were subjected to ICP-MS analysis and histological analysis. The results revealed that exposure of mice to Cd for 14 days significantly increased Cd concentration and significantly decreased magnesium (Mg), phosphorus (P) and zinc (Zn) concentrations in the brain compared to untreated controls. This effect was accompanied by necrotic-degenerative alterations in both cerebellum and cerebrum. Oral administration of low dose DFP to Cd-exposed mice decreased the concentration of the toxic metal in the brain by 16.37% and recovered the concentrations of the essential elements to normal control values. In contrast, oral administration of high dose DFP increased Cd content in the brain compared to the Cd-exposed group and significantly decreased selenium (Se) concentration compared to untreated controls. This effect could be explained with the ability of the chelating agent to inhibit iron adsorption in the gastrointestinal tract [8]. Decreased iron adsorption has been associated with up-regulation of the apical divalent metal transporter 1 (DMT1) and iron exporter ferroportin 1 (FPN1), leading to elevated blood concentrations of the toxic metal ions [10]. Histological analysis of brain tissue of Cd-exposed mice obtained high dose DFP confirmed ICP-MS data and revealed a large number of necrotic Purkinje cells in the cerebellum. In contrast, the oral administration of low dose DFP substantially restored cerebellar and cerebral morphologies. The results demonstrated that oral administration of DFP at low dose has a better therapeutic potential for treatment of Cd-induced brain damage compared to the high dose.

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Targeted delivery of hypoxia-sensitive probe by conjugation with iron-saturated transferrin to exploit the transferrin receptor pathway

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Hypoxia is one of the hallmarks of the tumor microenvironment and is caused by the imbalance between the oxygen supply to the cells and its consumption rate. The hypoxic status of solid tumors is considered a fundamental indicator of an adverse prognosis. Consequently, nowadays, there is an immediate need to develop sensors for monitoring hypoxia, which will detect subtle changes in O₂ concentration. Despite widely developed methods for imaging hypoxic tissues, selectivity toward hypoxic-neoplastic tissue is still insufficient. One approach to improve the selectivity is targeted delivery using transferrin receptors, which are often overexpressed in cancer cells [1]. Therefore, TfR is an attractive target for diagnosis and treatment. Its natural ligand, Tf can be conjugated to drugs or diagnostic molecules, that facilitate their internalization and, in this way, improve their efficiency and selectivity towards cancer tissue, while minimizing side effects [2]. A wide variety of therapeutic agents have been used for TfR-targeted cancer therapy, but the transferrin receptor pathway can also be used to image hypoxic cells in tumors.

Figure 1. Transferrin receptor-mediated endocytosis.

In this work, we present applying holo-transferrin to synthesize conjugates with an optical probe sensitive to the nitroreductase (NTR) concentration in cancer cells, as a novel hypoxia-selective sensor which might be delivered to cells by the TfR-mediated endocytosis pathway (Figure 1). Transferrin conjugation with sensors based on nitro-pyrazinotriazapentalene derivatives [3] was optimized and the obtained conjugate was characterized. It was shown that the conjugated probe was efficiently reduced to a highly fluorescent form by NTR. Furthermore, biological studies focused on analysis biodistribution of the tested conjugate using the transferrin receptor pathway and the influence of hypoxia on the level of probe reduction

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Physico-chemical characterization of a highly rigid Gd(III) complex formed with phenanthroline derivative ligand.

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Nowadays, the CAs used in clinical practice are the complexes of paramagnetic Gd(III) ion formed with polyamino-polycarboxylate ligands such as the derivatives of DTPA (diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid) and DOTA (1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane-1,4,7,10-tetraacetic acid). [1] The *in vivo* application of the toxic Gd(III) ($LD_{50} = 0.1-0.3$ mmol/kg) ion was facilitated by the formation of thermodynamically stable and inert complexes which were considered to be safe for years until the appearance of the NSF (nephrogenic systemic fibroses) in the late 90s. [2] This potentially lethal disease was mostly reported for patients having severe renal failure when the urine excretion is slower or stopped, thus the *in vivo* lifetime of the CAs increases significantly. [3] In this condition, the intravenously injected agent can be efficiently attacked by the endogenous metal ions and bioligands promoting the dechelation of that which leads to the liberation and accumulation of the free Gd(III) in different organs. Due to the “NSF-problem”, concerns have been raised over the safety of contrasted MRI investigations, which prompted researchers to find alternatives for the compromised CAs. [4] An obvious solution for preventing the *in vivo* dechelation is to increase the inertness of the complexes by incorporation of aliphatic or aromatic rings into the ligand structures providing a rigid coordination cavity in which the internal motion is extremely limited being an obstacle for decomplexation. [5] A great example for this approach is the Gd(III) complex of CDTA (trans-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid) ligand, the cyclohexyl derivative of EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid), whose k_1 rate constant characterizing the proton-assisted dissociation, is nearly 60 times smaller than that obtained for the parent chelate. [6]

Interestingly, the utilization of another important feature of the lanthanides, i.e. their luminescence, promoted the design and synthesis of several structurally rigid chelators by incorporating aromatic sensitizing moieties into the ligand structure. [7] A representative example for this ligand is the 1,10-phenanthroline-2,9-diyl)bis(methyliminodiacetic acid) (FENTA, Scheme 1) synthesized and published by Lin and coworkers [8] for exploiting luminescence property of Tb(III) in its analytics but the Gd(III) complex of that was never tested as potential candidate for MRI application. Since, this phenanthroline derivative provides a rigid and planar backbone, it is reasonable to assume that its Gd(III) complex may exhibit advantageous physico-chemical features for application as CAs in clinical practice.

In this work, we present the results of the thermodynamic, kinetic, relaxation, and structural study performed on the FENTA ligand and its Gd(III) complex. Our goal was to investigate the physico-chemical features of $[\text{Gd}(\text{FENTA})]^-$ in order to get insight into the potential of this complex and its future derivatives as a platform for MRI CAs. The results show that the $q = 1$ ($q =$ the number of the water molecules directly coordinated to the metal ion in the inner sphere of the complex) $[\text{Gd}(\text{FENTA})]^-$ complex possesses higher conditional stability, relaxivity and inertness than those were determined for the $[\text{Gd}(\text{DTPA})]^{2-}$ chelate routinely used in the clinical practice.

Scheme 1. Schematic structure of FENTA.

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Design, synthesis and evaluation of novel extended triphenylamine derivatives for G-quadruplex detection and visualization in cells

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In the last decade, non-canonical nucleic acid structures have attracted considerable attention of researchers from many science fields, including chemistry, biology, physics, materials and nanotechnology. Non-canonical nucleic acid structures include triplexes, i-motifs, three/four-way junctions or G-quadruplexes (G4). The later one is a supramolecular assembly of two or more tetrads, which arise from the hydrogen bonding network of four coplanar guanines. The stability and topology of G4 structures are mainly controlled by the alkali metal cation employed and the nature of the nucleic acid (DNA or RNA). Strikingly, a large number of putative G-quadruplex forming sequences have been identified in the genomes of human and viruses, and evidences suggest their pivotal role in key biological processes such as ageing and cancer.[1] Therefore, these G4 structures have been proposed as potential targets by small molecules for therapeutic intervention.[2-3] In order to unravel the biological processes in which G4s are involved, several strategies have emerged such as antibodies and small molecules. Currently, there is only an antibody for G4 recognition but the limitations of this technology have arisen some concerning in the field. Such limitations emerged from the high affinity of the antibodies for G4s and the application of a fixation agent which can fold these structures in cells and mask the G4s landscape of any biological process. An alternative strategy to detect and visualise G4s is the use of small probe molecules.

In this line, our team has launched a project of G4 probes based on the triphenylamine scaffold and found two ligands with strong interaction and selectivity for G4 structures.[4-5] This project aims to prepare the second generation of triphenylamine-based molecules with extended aromatic core in order to enhance the photophysical features for bioimaging while maintaining the excellent binding abilities for G4s. Herein, we present our synthetic efforts to develop new organic molecules able to interact with G-quadruplex structures. A range of biophysical assays (FRET melting, fluorescence spectroscopy and molecular modelling) has been used to characterise the binding and mode of action. Our results point out the importance of the organic core, the extended aromatic scaffold and the aliphatic conjugation to obtain strong G4 binders and exhibit high fluorescence quantum yields to be applied as bioimaging G4 probes.

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Metallo-Liposomes derived from [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ as nanocarriers of antiretroviral drugs and TLRs in the HIV treatment

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HIV (human immunodeficiency virus) is a virus that attacks cells that help the body fight infection, making a person more vulnerable to other infections and diseases. To date, the only documented case of a patient cured of HIV-1 is a Berlin and UK Patients, diagnosed with acute myeloid leukemia and Hodgkin's lymphoma respectively, who received allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation from a donor with mutated CCR5 receptor that leaves the CD4⁺ T cells resistant to HIV-1 [1,2]. Several clinical strategies such as targeting the HIV replication cycle, enhancement of the HIV specific immune response and immune modulation have been applied for eliminating latently infected cells in order to allow individuals to stop cART safely; but none of them achieved the HIV cure. Nanocarrier-based drug delivery systems provide an innovative approach for developing higher cART drug-loading capacity that can facilitate a complete eradication of the virion from the reservoir sites [3].

Here, metalloliposomes derived from the trisbipyridyl ruthenium (II) complex (Figure 1) were prepared to be used as nanocarriers of a combination of antiretroviral drugs and/or TLRs. Encapsulation efficiency and the release process of the drugs were studied. The cytotoxicity of these nanostructures were performed in different non-primary cell lines related to the immune system. *In vitro* hemolytic effect and platelet aggregation assays were also performed.

Results demonstrated the capacity of these assemblies to encapsulate cART together Toll-like receptor TLRs. This new combination could increase the innate immune response against HIV and provide a further effective strategy to decrease the DNA quantity of HIV and clearance of HIV reservoirs in CD4 cells from infected patients.

Figure 1: SEM image of Ru-based metalloliposome

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Copper(II) complexes of pyridine-2,6-carboxamide ligands: thermodynamic, spectroscopic and SOD activity features

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Superoxide dismutase enzymes (SODs) are capable to catalyse the decomposition reaction of superoxide anion which is one of the reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the living organisms.[1] The overproduction of ROS can promote the progression of tumours due to the structural alteration of DNA and the inactivation of tumour suppressor genes.[2,3] Thus, drugs for decreasing the concentration of ROS open new avenues for the treatment of cancer. Consequently, a promising approach in clinical medicine is the invention of ROS scavengers (SOD mimics), especially those that target cancer cells.

Pyridine-2,6-carboxamide ligands represent a versatile class of coordination compound and they transition metal complexes have gained significance as bioactive molecules. In a quest for developing novel SOD mimics, we designed novel ligands by conjugating pyridine-2,6-carboxamide with different amino acids (Scheme 1). These ligands and their copper(II) complexes have been studied by equilibrium, spectroscopic, theoretical and kinetic methods.[4]

Scheme 1. Structure of the pyridine-2,6-carboxamide ligands.

The results indicate that these ligands are effective metal binding sites for copper(II). At physiological pH, the deprotonation and coordination of carboxamide functions occur and the coordination sphere of copper(II) accommodates the pyridine-N and two carboxamide functions, and this coordination mode is further supported by the binding of the side chains of

amino acid residues (Figure 1). The complexes exhibit remarkable SOD activity as shown by stopped-flow measurements and xanthine/xanthine-oxidase/NBT assay.

Figure 1. ORTEP view of **pydiAla** (left) and its dinuclear copper(II) complex (right).

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Investigation of Metal-Phthalocyanines as New G-Quadruplex Binders and Potential Photosensitisers

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In the last decades, cancer has been a global leading cause of death and have attracted the major interests of the scientific community. Around 10 million people died of cancer worldwide in 2021 and it is expected that 16.3 million cancer deaths would occur worldwide by 2040. A large effort has been devoted to target nuclear DNA and oncogene proteins in cancer but novel biomolecular targets as well as approaches have been demanding to overcome the appearance of cancer resistance tissues along the treatments. In this line, non-canonical nucleic acid structures such as G-quadruplexes (G4s) have arisen the interest for therapeutic intervention because they have shown to control key biological processes in cancer. [1] In parallel, phototherapy has emerged as an alternative method to treat different types of cancer upon improvement of this technology (light penetration in tissues, photosensitiser targeting tumour tissues...). In this line, we present the interaction of two potential photosensitisers, described as metallo-phthalocyanines containing four ethylammonium substituents, with G-quadruplex structures by using FRET melting and UV-Vis/fluorescence spectroscopies. Interestingly, the square-planar structure of nickel phthalocyanine favours the interaction with G4s but hampers the ability to generate singlet oxygen species *in vitro* and exerts phototoxicity in HeLa, A549 and Raw264.7 cell lines. On the other hand, zinc phthalocyanine shows moderate binding to G-quadruplexes but a high capacity to generate ROS species, showing a large phototoxicity.

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Aqueous solution behaviour of half-sandwich Ru and Rh complexes of an salicylhydroxamic acid derivative

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Hydroxamic acids are excellent metal-chelating compounds with various biological effects (e.g. anticancer, antifungal and antimalarial activity) [1]. Their biological effects are undoubtedly connected to metalloenzyme inhibition through the binding of protein-bound metal centres [1]. There are FDA-approved drugs in this compound family, namely vorinostat (SAHA), belinostat and panobinostat, which target the Zn(II) metal centre in zinc-dependent histone deacetylases [2].

Complexation of metal ions

(Cu(II), Fe(III),

half-sandwich Ru(II) and Rh(III))

Hybridization with estradiol

Salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA) is an antibacterial drug with urease enzyme inhibitory effect, binding to Ni(II) in this metalloenzyme [3]. This molecule can coordinate to the metal ions in two different bidentate ways, since it can form an (O,O) five-membered chelate ring and also a (N,O) six-membered chelate ring [3]. It is an interesting question that the anticancer effect of SHA can be enhanced by a steroidal part or not. Several 2-substituted estrone and estradiol derivatives showed anticancer effect without any hormonal action [4].

Herein we introduce an SHA–estradiol hybrid, in which the estradiol part provides improved lipophilic profile without changing the metal binding site. Since cancer is generally accompanied with weaker immune system, bacterial infections are big threats for patients treated in hospitals. For this reason, maximizing the antibacterial effect of an anticancer drug candidate is also an important goal, focusing on the virulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and the multidrug resistant MRSA bacterial strains.

In the solution equilibrium studies both the SHA and the SHA–estradiol hybrid were investigated. Benzohydroxamic acid was used as a model for the (O,O) coordination mode. The complex formation with essential metal ions (Fe(III) and Cu(II)) was investigated by UV-vis spectrophotometry, cyclic voltammetry and pH-potentiometry. These results may explain the metal ion preference of SHA when it reacts with the components of the cytoplasm in cancer cells. Moreover, we also introduce the complex formation with half-sandwich Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅) and Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene) organometallic cations. The complexation of biologically active compounds with these cations may enhance the anticancer effect and may improve the pharmacokinetic behaviour of them. Since the anticancer effect may be connected to the antioxidant activity of the compounds and their metal complexes, DPPH assay was used to test that property for the complexes and for the ligands.

Based on these results, the SHA and its estradiol hybrid have similar proton dissociation constants and form complexes with a comparable stability. The estradiol hybrid has improved cytotoxicity in three cancer cell lines and complex formation with Cu(II) and half-sandwich Rh(III) and Ru(II) cations also improved the anticancer effect.

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A Multitechnique Approach for Unravelling the Uranium(VI) Solution Speciation with Hydroxamic Acids

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Siderophores are ubiquitous, high-affinity iron(III) chelators excreted by numerous bacteria and yeasts under iron-stress conditions. Their primary biological role is to supply the microorganisms with iron, an essential nutrient and growth factor. As a mean to circumvent the extremely low bioavailability of this element at physiological pH, siderophores react with ferric (oxo)hydroxides to form water-soluble complexes, which are transported across the cell membranes according to an energy-driven mechanism involving specific outer-membrane uptake receptors. Hydroxamates are common bidentate chelating groups found in many siderophores, an emblematic representative being desferrioxamine B.

As the concentration of desferrioxamines in soils is typically in the $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ range, it might significantly increase the solubility, migration rate, and bioavailability of highly toxic actinides in case of environmental contamination. Hence, to evaluate their fate in the environment after accidental release or storage of nuclear wastes in deep geological repositories, develop new remediation strategies of contaminated areas or analytical field monitoring tools, a deep understanding of the coordination chemistry of the 5f-elements with hydroxamic siderochelates is highly desirable [1–3]. Indeed, predicting and modelling the metal speciation in waters and soils require an accurate knowledge of the thermodynamic and kinetic parameters related to the complex formation and dissociation equilibria [1]. Because such data are scarce and often unreliable in the case of actinide cations, considerable research efforts are still required.

By combining potentiometric and spectrophotometric titration techniques with affinity capillary electrophoresis, the speciation of linear and cyclic monohydroxamate binding units, abiotic dihydroxamates, and desferrioxamine B with UO_2^{2+} could be unraveled. X-ray absorption, Raman, and ^{17}O NMR spectroscopies enabled to probe the chemical environment

around the uranium center in the different species prevailing in solution and to ascertain the accuracy of the speciation model at fifty-time higher ligand and metal concentration levels as those used for the spectrophotometric and potentiometric studies. Finally, the proton-assisted step-by-step dissociation mechanism of the $[\text{UO}_2(\text{DFB})\text{H}_2]^+$ complex, as established by stopped-flow spectrophotometry, will be presented too.

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Synthesis, characterization, and application of new silver DNA nanoclusters in the inactivation of microorganisms.

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The spread of resistant bacterial strains is one of the main threats to humanity as recognised by the World Health Organization in its report in 2014 and in its priority list of pathogens published in 2017.[1] The widespread use of antibiotics during the last 30 years resulted in less effective or even, ineffective clinical treatments. Nowadays, antimicrobial infections are treated with drugs developed in the 80s and thus, the pipeline of new drugs has diminished in the last years. Microbial infections have arisen in the last years and are estimated to cause an annual death toll of 10 million worldwide by 2060, which will make many of the medical advances of the 20th century obsolete.

Silver is a non-essential element known for its antibacterial effect used by different civilisations since ancient times. However, the application of silver and silver-based materials is scarce because of the widely use of antibiotics. Nevertheless, the lack of new antibiotics to treat resistant strains has arisen the interest to develop new drugs, targets and therapies of pharmaceutical industry and non-profit organisations. Among silver-based materials, silver nanoclusters have attracted much interest in the last years due to their molecule-like optical properties, in particular, their strong fluorescence. These optical properties of the silver nanoclusters are finely tuned by the capping agents, which are usually chitosan, PEG, PVP or BSA. Recently, DNA has emerged as a new capping agent that can confer additional properties to the material depending on the oligonucleotide sequence used for the material synthesis. [2-3]

In this work, we have developed novel silver DNA nanoclusters showing tunable fluorescence emission depending on the oligonucleotide sequence and characterised them by UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopies, electrophoresis and TEM. Taking into account their photophysical properties, photoactivation of the materials have been used to kill bacteria (*S. Aureus* and *E. Coli*) and the mechanisms of action are currently investigated.

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Solution equilibrium studies of the interaction of *p*-coumaric acid with lanthanides

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p-coumaric acid (4-hydroxycinnamic acid) (*p*-CA) is one of the main representatives of hydroxycinnamic acids. It is synthesized via the phenylpropanoid route, mainly from phenylalanine and tyrosine. *p*-CA is present in plants, both in free and conjugated form - forming derivatives of mono-, oligo- and polysaccharides, organic acids, alkyl alcohols and amines, and it can be found in fruits, vegetables, nuts and grains.[1, 2]. *p*-CA possess anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and antioxidant properties, being therefore, used in the many industrial fields as chemical, food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical.[3]

Scheme 1: Structure of *p*-coumaric acid

The literature survey shows that metal complexes of *p*-CA could exhibit even better activity (*e.g.*, antibacterial and antioxidant) when compared with free ligand. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the interactions of *p*-CA with lanthanides in aqueous solution. In this communication we will present the solution thermodynamic study of *p*-CA and its complexes with Eu(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III). Potentiometric and spectrophotometric titration techniques were used to investigate the acid-base behaviour of *p*-CA and its complexation ability towards selected lanthanides in aqueous solution over a wide range of pH values ($2 \leq \text{pH} \leq 8$), at $I = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KCl}_{(\text{aq})}$ and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$.

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SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASE MIMETIC NANOZYMES WITH OUTSTANDING ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

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Misregulation of free metal ions and oxidative stress have been linked to the progressive neurological misfunction associated with multiple neurodegenerative disorders. For instance, in Alzheimer's disease, accumulation of Fe, Cu and Zn in beta-amyloid plaques have proved responsible for increased oxidative injury in certain brain regions. These transition metals mediate in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) *via* Fenton chemical reactions, among which superoxide radicals play a prevailing role. Finally, the imbalance between the generation and scavenging of ROS derives in oxidative stress. Current therapy research for these disorders is aimed at interfering with responsible metal ions and modifying their detrimental activity. [1]

A tetraaza-pyridinophane macrocycle capable of chelating ROS-producing metal ions has been synthesized and characterized. Potentiometric and UV-vis titrations, as well as electrochemical studies and SOD activity assays, lead to the conclusion that the developed macrocycle can coordinate Cu(II), leading to the formation of complexes with an outstanding superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity. [2]

This macrocycle has been designed with a *para*-carbonyl group in order to be grafted onto boehmite nanoparticles (BNPs). The corresponding amino-nanozyme system has been prepared and characterized. Same studies as with the unbonded Cu(II) complexes showed that being linked to BNPs induces a 30-fold increase in their SOD catalytic constant. This enhancement is probably related with the positive ζ -potential of the functionalised nanoparticles. [2, 3]

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Interligand interactions and polymer dimensionality. Crystal structures of [Cu(NBzIDA)]_n and [Cu(NBzIDA)(Him)]_n with of imidazole (Him) and/or the N-benzyl-iminodiacetate(2-) chelator (NBzIDA)

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The chelator NBzIDA (Scheme 1) has a non-coordinating benzyl substituent with possibilities to be implied in π,π -stacking interactions with themselves or with aromatic moieties of other coligands, as can be observed in its 30 structures available in CSD database. As far as concerns to its copper(II) complexes, examples are known with coligands as Him [1], a large variety of purines, such as deaza-adenine [2] or N-methyl-purine [3] ligands, and some phenanthrolines [4]. Interestingly, the structures of the binary ‘Cu(NBzIDA)’ chelate or of the ternary ‘CuNBzIDA)(Him)’ complex has not reported and define the subject of this work.

The compound [Cu(NBzIDA)]_n (**1**) was obtained by reaction of H₂NBzIDA and [Cu₂(μ -AcO)₄(H₂O)₂] in water (molar ratio 2:1) with HAcO as by-product. Its crystal structure (100 K, monoclinic space group P2₁, R₁ = 0.023) revealed its Cu(II) centre surrounded by an asymmetrically elongated octahedron (type 4+1+1) with donors from three NBzIDA ligands (**Figure 1-left**).

Figure 1. Compound **1**: **left**, Cu(II) coordination and bridging roles of NBzIDA; **right**, 2D-layers interacting by only conventional Van der Waals forces.

The longest bonds Cu1-O7#1 (2.773(3) Å and Cu1-O6#2 (2.138(3) Å define the closest trans-angle (140.3°). The chelating NBzIDA adopts a mer-NO₂ conformation, but also involves both a bridging bidentate (μ_2 -anti,syn-C6,O6,O7) and a tridentate-(C2,O1,O2) carboxylate groups, yielding layers parallel to the *ab* plane. Such 2D-frameworks leaves aromatic moieties from NBzIDA toward its external faces They are pillared along the *c* axis (**Figure 1-right**) by conventional Van der Vaal's interactions (without π -stacking interactions).

The compound [Cu(μ_2 -NBzIDA)(Him)] (**2**) is easily obtained from equimolar amounts of **1** and Him in water, followed by slow evaporation of solvent. In the crystal (273 K, monoclinic, space group P2₁/c, R1 = 0.035) the Cu(II) exhibits an elongated square-planar coordination (type 4+1) and NBzIDA displays both a mer-NO₂ chelating conformation and a bridging role (μ_2 -anti,syn-C7,O8,O9) (**Figure 2-left**). That yields 1D-polymeric chains parallel to the *b* axis. These chains connect by interligand (Him)N-H \cdots O(carboxy) bonds and π -stacking between phenyl rings form NBzIDA (**Figure 2-right**).

Figure 2. Compound **2**: **left**, Cu(II) coordination; **right**, interligand interactions between 1D chains.

In conclusion, crystal structures of both polymers reveals that interligand interactions Him-NBzIDA and between the aromatic moiety from pairs of NBzIDA favour the 1D dimensionality of compound **2** versus the 2D-layers of compound **1**.

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Estradiol-based salicylaldehyde (thio)semicarbazones and their copper complexes with anticancer, antibacterial and antioxidant activities

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Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) possess significant biological activity, which include antibacterial, antimalarial, antiviral, antioxidant and antitumor activities [1,2]. Notably, their activity can be increased by coordination to specific metal ions such as Cu(II), Fe(II/III) and Ni(II).

A tridentate estrone-salicylaldehyde TSC molecule (estrone-TSC) and its Cu(II) complex were developed in our previous work [3], and estrone-TSC was found to be cytotoxic against MCF-7 breast cancer cell lines (IC₅₀: 6.4 μM). Moreover, complexation with Cu(II) ions showed even higher cytotoxicity than the ligand as 1-2 orders of magnitude lower IC₅₀ values were obtained for the complexes against a series of human cancer cell lines [3]. The terminal *N*-mono- and dimethylated derivatives of estrone-TSC and their Cu(II) complexes were also prepared [4], and the *in vitro* cytotoxicity of these Cu(II) complexes was measured in 3D spheroids of human cancer cells which showed fairly low IC₅₀ values (4–17 μM). They were able to reduce tumour growth and activate the caspase-3 and caspase-7 endoproteases [4].

Chart 1. Chemical structures of the investigated ligands

In this work, the estradiol-2-thiosemicarbazone hybrid and its terminal *N*-mono- and dimethylated derivatives (Chart 1) were synthesized in addition to its semicarbazone (SC) analogue in order to fine-tune their water solubility and compare their redox properties, anticancer and antioxidant activities to those of the estrone-TSC and estrone-semicarbazone derivatives.

The stability and structure of the complexes in solution were determined using UV-visible spectrophotometry, electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy. Single crystal X-ray diffraction was applied to determine the solid phase structure of the semicarbazone complex. Due to limited water solubility, UV-visible titrations were performed in 30% (v/v) DMSO/H₂O solvent mixture to determine the proton dissociation constants of the ligands and the stability constants of the complexes formed in the solution. Direct redox reaction of the complexes with physiological reductants such as glutathione and ascorbate was also monitored under anaerobic conditions. Additionally, anticancer and antioxidant properties were studied as well using MTT and DPPH assays, respectively. Moreover, antibacterial activity was also determined.

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Coordination chemistry of natural siderophores and their fragments

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The frequency of infections caused by drug resistant microbes has increased significantly over the past three decades, making it an increasingly serious threat to global public health that requires action across all government sectors and society [1, 2]. Resistant microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi are able to endure the action of antibiotics and antifungal agents, making standard treatment ineffective. Innovative, effective methods of treatment and of their specific delivery to antibiotic-resistant bacteria and drug-resistant invasive mycoses are actively sought. One of the greatest obstacles to finding such effective pathogen-specific therapeutics without serious side effects in patients is the fact that bacteria and fungi share essential metabolic pathways with humans. In order to design a highly specific antimicrobial drug, understanding and pursuing the differences in human and pathogen metabolism is essential. Although pathogen-selective targets are scarce, there is at least one significant difference between the microbial and mammalian cells: the transport system of transition metal ions. This is one of the particular reasons for the growing interest in metal chelating molecules excreted externally of the pathogen to effectively bind a given metal ion and interact with the corresponding metal ions.

Among others, an intricate iron acquisition and trafficking system involving low molecular weight molecules termed siderophores or iron carriers (from greek ‘sidero’ for iron) is the most common way for microorganisms to acquire this nutrient [3-5]. Despite their preference for iron, siderophores have been proved to chelate numerous other metal ions with variable stoichiometry and stability, including both those biologically relevant and those with no known biological function (e.g. toxic to living cells). Binding of certain non-iron, biologically relevant metals may well play a role in their delivery to bacterial cells to counter metal limitations imposed by the growth environment. On the other hand, the concept that siderophores play a role in heavy metal tolerance and protection of bacteria against metal toxicity has been recognized. This aspect might be of importance during nutritional immunity, when the host uses withdrawal of, or poisoning with, metals as defence approaches against microbial invaders [6, 7].

Understanding the mechanisms of metal ion transport by siderophores, as well as designing novel antimicrobial drugs, requires a careful study of the relationship between the structure of a specific siderophore and (i) its ability to chelate metal ions, as well as (ii) the recognition of a given siderophore by an appropriate transporter.

In our research, we focused on determining the coordination properties of natural siderophores and their individual fragments to determine how structural changes affect the stability of the formed complexes with Fe(III), Ga(III), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) ions and which siderophore fragments are responsible for such efficient chelation. Examples of such ligands are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Examples of studied ligands.

The obtained knowledge may in the future allow for the creation of innovative siderophore biomimetics, which may be useful in the search for antimicrobial drugs.

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Sterane-based bidentate ligands with (N,N) donor set: synthesis, biological activity, solution chemistry and interaction with half-sandwich Ru and Rh cations

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The harmful side effects caused by the anticancer drugs in clinical use, prompted the development of novel chemotherapeutic agents as more effective and selective candidates. Platinum(II)-containing drugs have been widely used for decades in cancer therapy against solid tumors due to their effectiveness, although, their use is often accompanied by drawbacks such as the aforementioned side effects, due to the lack of selectivity, and resistance [1]. Half-sandwich organometallic complexes, such as ruthenium(II) or rhodium(III)-based complexes, have shown enormous potential in this field, with a wide spectrum of activity. The piano-stool complexes often contain a bidentate ligand and a chlorido co-ligand as leaving group, and these components affect the solution stability, lipophilicity and ultimately the biological activity.

On the other hand, the sterane backbone is a frequently used pharmacophore subunit for drug development, as semi-synthetic modifications in the substitution pattern often lead to derivatives with altered biological action. In this work, stereoselective reductive amination of estrone with four functionalized primary amines were carried out in good yields. The novel steroidal bidentate ligands thus obtained contain a built-in unit, which makes them suitable for chelating metal ions. Due to the (N,N) donor set, these molecules are able to form highly stable complexes with half-sandwich organoruthenium and organorhodium, since this type of chelating moiety has strong affinity toward these organometallic ions, as it was reported in our previous works [2,3]. Besides the synthesis, investigation of the four novel sterane-based ligands (Scheme 1) in terms of biological activity, solution chemistry and interaction with half-sandwich $[\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ (RuCym) and $[\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ (RhCp*) cations is also reported.

Scheme 1. Chemical structures of the sterane-based ligands and the organometallic triaqua cations.

UV-visible spectrophotometry, spectrofluorimetry and ^1H NMR spectroscopy were utilized to characterize the proton dissociation processes of the ligands in water and in 30% (v/v) DMSO/water. The ligands have three dissociable protons, and according to the determined $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ values, they possess mostly positive charges (+1; +2) at physiological pH, however, they showed significant differences in their solubility in water at $\text{pH} = 7.40$. Ligands containing two aliphatic nitrogen atoms have relatively good water solubility (500 – 600 μM), while the other two with the pyridine moiety can be dissolved in water at much lower concentration (12 – 38 μM), which correlates with their lipophilicity. Complex formation with half-sandwich RuCym and RhCp* cations was followed by UV-visible spectrophotometry, and the results also showed differences between the metal binding ability of the ligands containing aliphatic and aromatic nitrogen atoms, namely, 17-PA-estradiol (PA: picolylamine) and 17-PE-estradiol (PE: pyridinyl ethanamine) formed much higher stability complexes than 17-ED-estradiol (ED: ethylenediamine) and 17-PD-estradiol (PD: propanediamine). Most probably, the dimethylated terminal nitrogen hinders the effective coordination due to steric reasons [2].

Cytotoxicity assay on the ligands and their half-sandwich complexes was performed in hormone-responsive (MCF7); chemosensitive (Colo205) and normal fibroblast cell line (MRC-5). Difference between the two groups of ligands could be observed, namely the aliphatic ligands are more cytotoxic in all tested cell lines compared to the aromatic ones, while complexation resulted in the higher selectivity over MRC-5 cell line. All the ligands are more effective on the Colo205 cell line than on the MCF7 cell line. The complexes showed moderate cytotoxic activity in the cancer cells ($\text{IC}_{50} = 20 - 33 \mu\text{M}$) with some selectivity.

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Investigation of the interaction of a water-soluble 8-hydroxyquinoline amino acid hybrid with essential metal ions

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8-Hydroxyquinolines (HQ) are bidentate chelators that also have antibacterial, neuroprotective and anticancer properties. Additional derivatives of HQs have been synthesized, such as HQNO₂, which is used as an antiseptic and to treat urinary tract infections systemically, and has also been investigated as an antimicrobial, anticancer, and neurodegenerative agent [1]. In addition, HQNO₂ is a reversible inhibitor of cathepsin B endopeptidase, which enzyme involved in the degradation of the extracellular matrix, a process that promotes tumor invasion [2]. It is important to mention that HQ and HQNO₂ are poorly water-soluble ligands, which has encouraged the development of additional ligands with better solubility. For this purpose, the amino acid hybrid HQNO₂-L-Pro was synthesized and tested, which has higher water solubility due to the zwitterionic amino acid moiety. HQNO₂-L-Pro was found to be active on sensitive and multidrug resistant cells lines as well, similarly to other amino acid HQ hybrids and other related Mannich based HQs [3-5].

Interactions with endogenous metal ions play an important role in the anticancer effects of HQs, as their biological effects are related to the *in situ* formation of complexes with metal ions such as Cu(II), Zn(II) and Fe(II/III) ions, since these types of compounds are able to form significantly stable complexes with them [6].

In order to get a closer understanding of the mechanisms of action of HQNO₂-L-Pro, we not only determined the proton dissociation constants of the ligand in pure aqueous medium, but also studied the complex formation of the ligand with the mentioned essential metal ions. Complex formation was investigated using UV-visible spectrophotometric titrations and for Cu(II) ions electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy. For the copper(II) and iron(III) complexes, cyclic voltammetric measurements were performed to monitor the redox properties. The reactions were also followed with two natural reducing agents, namely the ascorbic acid and the glutathione with UV-visible spectrophotometric detection. The cytotoxicity of the ligand in the absence and in the presence of Cu(II), Fe(III) and Zn(II) ions was also assayed to reveal the effect of the complexation on the activity.

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Anion-imprinted polymeric chemosensor for the optical sensing of fluoride

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Anions are ubiquitous in nature, playing important roles in a wide variety of chemical, biological and technological scenarios [1]. In the case of fluoride anion, its dichotomous behavior has especially raised the interest of the scientific community. On the one hand, it is known to be beneficial for dental health and the treatment of osteoporosis. On the other hand, an excess of F⁻ is harmful to human health and the environment. In this context, the detection and quantification of fluoride through convenient and inexpensive methods have emerged as significant analytical targets. Discrete optical sensors, which contain an anion binding site (receptor) attached to a signaling unit (e.g., fluorophore or chromophore), have gained great attention, since they exhibit high sensitivity, very low detection limits and use simple affordable equipment [2, 3]. However, achieving the necessary level of selectivity is not straightforward. The latest advantages point to embedding urea/thiourea optical discrete anion sensors into a polymeric scaffold. However, selectivity issues remain, due to the fact that the colorimetric or fluorometric response is also quenched by other anions such as dihydrogenphosphate. Following the idea of polymer embedding, but focusing on tackling the mentioned selectivity hurdles, we report here the preparation and assessment of a sensitive and selective polymeric chemosensor for the optical sensing of fluoride anion, using the anion-imprinted technique.

We started by preparing a family of polymerizable anion receptors (compounds **1-4**, Figure 1a), bearing a urea-type binding site, a terminal polymerizable C=C group and different signaling units (fluorophores). Our results show that compound **2** exhibits the highest fluorescent emission intensity, and it was then assayed as a fluorimetric chemosensor in the presence of F⁻ and other interferences such as Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, H₂PO₄⁻ and NO₃⁻. This discrete sensor exhibits high optical sensitivity for F⁻ and H₂PO₄⁻, while for the rest of the anions the sensitivity is substantially lower. In this regard, dihydrogenphosphate represents an important analytical interference when sensing fluoride with **2**. The electronic and structural determinants behind the optical response and the anion-chemosensor affinity were elucidated using experimental and computational tools. The results suggest a static quenching for F⁻, Cl⁻ and H₂PO₄⁻ and a predominant collisional-type quenching for the rest of the anions. In the case of F⁻, the deprotonation of **2** also contributes to the optical response.

To enhance the optical sensitivity and selectivity of the discrete sensor, a fluoride-imprinted polymeric optical sensor was prepared starting from **2** (Figure 1b). The fluoride-responsive material (**2-MIP**) was characterized and showed satisfactory optical performance and anion specificity (Figure 1c). Indeed, its emission is significantly switched off only in the presence of fluoride, while for the rest of the anions there was almost no optical response. Besides, the optical sensitivity towards fluoride increases 13 times with respect to chemosensor **2** in solution.

Figure 1: a) Polymerizable anion receptors synthesized in this work. b) Preparation of **2-MIP**, the fluoride-imprinted polymeric optical sensor starting from **2**. c) Optical performance of **2-MIP**.

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Formation and stability of zinc(II)-citrate complex in solutions between pH 3 and 11

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Background Citrate is a tricarboxylic organic ligand involved in essential eco-physiological processes. Higher plants excrete citrate from roots and following the formation of citrate complexes with metals adsorbed on mineral surfaces and the subsequent release of this complex, nutrient metals become available.[1] Citrate is also involved in the plant detoxification process. Indeed, during phytoremediation treatment of polluted soils, an excess of metal ions is accumulated inside the cytosol. To minimize their toxic effects, plants use the complexation of metal ions with ligands as a strategy to reduce their bioavailability inside the plants.[2] Given the importance of citrate in metal regulation in environmental and biological systems, it is imperative to fully characterise the metal citrate complexes at different pH and ionic strengths. Previous work studied the formation of this complex in different electrolytes and different ionic strengths, i.e., in KNO₃, NaNO₃ and NaCl and at I = 0.1, 0.15, 1 mol dm⁻³ in the pH range between 3 and 8. These studies resulted in significant variability of conditional logK values.

Aims and Objectives The present study used potentiometric titrations and mass spectrometry to address significant knowledge gaps concerning the formation of Zn-citrate complexes, i.e., (i) to determine intrinsic logβ by establishing the empirical relationship between logK and I (0.05 ≤ mol dm⁻³ ≤ 1.00 NaCl) and parametrizing the Extended Debye Hückel equation and (ii) to determine Zn speciation at alkaline (pH >8) and acidic pH using different metal:ligand molar ratios (from 1:1 to 1:10) at T= 298.1 ± 0.1 K. The model chemistry tested was chosen based on published solution and structural coordination studies and included 11 species, namely [Zn(H₂Cit)]⁺, [Zn(HCit)], [Zn(Cit)]⁻, [Zn(HCit)₂]²⁻, [Zn(HCit)(Cit)]³⁻, [Zn₂(Cit)₂(OH)₂]⁴⁻, [Zn₂(Cit)₂]²⁻, [Zn(Cit)(OH)]²⁻, [Zn(Cit)(OH)₂]³⁻, [Zn(Cit)(OH)₃]⁴⁻, and [Zn(Cit)₂]⁴⁻. The HySS and Hyperquad software packages were used to determine experimental conditions for the titrations as shown in Figure 1 and to model the titrations.

Result and Discussion From the eleven Zn-Cit species investigated, the inclusion of five species resulted in a model fit with a sigma value below 5. The stability constant we report for specific Zn(II)-L complexes at specific ion strengths is in line with some values proposed by Cigala and co-workers.[3] For example, the logβ for the formation of [Zn(Cit)]⁻, [Zn(HCit)] and [Zn₂(Cit)₂(OH)₂]⁴⁻ in 0.15 mol dm⁻³ NaCl under the same experimental

Coordination of metal ions of environmental interest by macrocyclic polyamines.

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The synthesis, acid–base behaviour and heavy metal (Hg(II), Cd(II), Pb(II)) coordination chemistry of the hexaazacyclophane ligand (14-hydroxy-3,7,11,14,18,22-hexaaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclotricosaphane, L1) have been studied by potentiometric, NMR and UV-Vis techniques. Coordination chemistry studies reveal the formation of mono and binuclear species above pH 5, highlighting the formation of mostly mononuclear species in the case of Cd(II). UV-Vis studies have been carried out for the coordination with Hg(II), and compared with the potentiometric results.

Figure 1: Structure of ligand L1

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Highly stable Nd(III)/Yb(III) complexes as potential NIR imaging agents

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Optical molecular imaging is an increasing demand for biological research and medical diagnosis as it provides a high detection sensitivity [1]. Detection in the near-infrared (NIR) range is currently triggering strong enthusiasm as measurements performed in this spectral domain minimize the contribution of the native fluorescence of biological systems (autofluorescence), leading to enhanced detection sensitivity. Lanthanide(III) ions have advantages in respect to common organic fluorophores, such as: sharp emission bands, large energy differences between excitation and emission bands and long luminescence lifetimes [2,3].

Ln(III) complexes can find application in many areas of medicine for diagnostics or cancer treatment, for example: radioisotopes in nuclear medicine, Gd(III) complexes as MRI contrast agents, Eu(III) or Tb(III) complexes as luminescent probes for sensing and luminescent imaging applications [4-6]. Key requisites of such Ln(III) complexes are the high thermodynamic stability and kinetic inertness which are needed to avoid the release of the toxic metal ion in the organism, as well the loss of function of the complex. As far as luminescent sensing applications are concerned, the design of the ligand is essential to exploit the ligand-to-metal energy transfer mechanism called “antenna effect” [3]. The main energy transfer mechanism starts with the absorption occurring through the aromatic antenna, then, an intersystem crossing leads to a ligand-centered triplet state from which the energy transfer to the Ln ion occurs. A particularly interesting case is when the light emitted by the Ln(III) ion is in the NIR window where the biological matrix is transparent.

To this purpose ligands, such as the derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline, have characteristics to be considered as potential good antennas for sensitizing NIR-emitting Ln(III) ions [6].

Figure 1. Structure of the ligand reported in this work

Figure 2. Speciation plot for Nd complex

In this communication the results of the solution studies of Ln(III)-based NIR-emitting complexes based on a chiral 1,2-diaminocyclohexane (DACH) motif (Figure 1) are reported. The determination of equilibrium (protonation and stability) constants were carried out by means of potentiometric and UV/VIS spectrophotometric titrations (Figure 2). As a comparison, the Eu(III) complex was also studied.

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Molecular recognition of ammonium cations by novel water-soluble prismarene hosts

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Naphthalene-based macrocycles have recently attracted a great deal of attention in supramolecular chemistry because of their structural and conformational features. Recently, a new class of deep-cavity macrocycles, named prism[*n*]arenes (*n* = 5 and 6) [1], and their water-soluble homologous bearing carboxylato groups on both upper and lower rim (PrS[*n*]^{carboxy}), have been synthesized and characterized [2].

As the structural and conformational features of water-soluble hosts play a crucial role in determining their binding affinity for charged guests [3], the complexation properties of this novel class of receptors toward singly and doubly charged ammonium cations have been investigated in aqueous solution at 25 °C and pH 7.6 by combining nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) measurements.

NMR experiments revealed that PrS[*n*]^{carboxy} hosts form 1:1 complexes with all the charged guests regardless of the macrocycle size (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Example of guest inclusion into a prismarene cavity

ITC calorimetric measurements provided key information on both the binding affinities and the energetics of the recognition processes occurring in solution towards guests having different sizes, shapes and charges [4,5]. The stability of the host-guest complexes formed by PrS[5]^{carboxy} with the ammonium cations is significantly affected by the structural features of the differently charged guests, while the affinity values determined for PrS[6]^{carboxy} are quite comparable for all the cations investigated regardless of the properties of the guests.

The determination of the enthalpic and entropic contribution to the Gibbs free energy revealed striking features on the forces driving the encapsulation equilibria in solution. The inclusion of ammonium cations into PrS[5]^{carboxy} is driven by enthalpically favorable attractive forces whilst, in the case of PrS[6]^{carboxy}, the inclusion of monocations is an entropically favored and driven process while enthalpy drives the complexation of the doubly charged guests.

The synthesis of water-soluble prismarenes and the thermodynamic fingerprints of their binding processes in aqueous medium can help the construction of new prismarene-based supramolecular systems with fascinating properties.

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Novel Rivastigmine-based Multitarget Hybrids for Potential Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease: Cu(II) and Fe(III) chelation studies

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most prevalent and severe age-dependent neurodegenerative disorder, with no cure so far. Currently available drugs can only compensate the decline of the choline neurotransmitters providing temporary symptomatic benefits, but they cannot stop AD progression [1]. The multiple factors that contribute to trigger the AD onset and progression are not yet fully understood, but several pathological features have already been recognized, such as protein misfolding (amyloid aggregates and plaque formation), metal dyshomeostasis, oxidative stress and neurotransmitter deficiencies. Thus, there is a widespread recent interest in the development of multitarget-directed ligands (MTDLs) for simultaneous interaction with several pathological targets of AD [2,3].

To pursue the engineering of new MTDLs, templates based on FDA approved drugs, namely ChE inhibitors, have been recently used for hybridization with other bioactive moieties, therefore complementing the required multiactivity [4,5]. Herein, studies on novel hybrids (RIV-BIM, see Fig 1) that conjugate the active moiety of Rivastigmine (RIV), a FDA approved anti-AD drug, with a hydroxyphenylbenzimidazole (BIM) unit are reported. The RIV unit provides the hybrid molecules with the acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) inhibitory capacity, while the BIM moiety endows them with capacity for inhibition of β -amyloid ($A\beta$) aggregation and chelation of specific biometal ions (e.g. Cu, Fe) known to be involved in $A\beta$ aggregation and oxidative stress [6]. In particular, solution equilibrium studies are presented and demonstrate the chelating ability of representative hybrid compounds (**4c** and **5a**) towards copper(II) and iron(III), involving coordination through the phenolic oxygen and the imidazole nitrogen of the BIM moiety.

The effect of these hybrids on the inhibition of self-mediated and Cu-induced $A\beta_{42}$ aggregation, as well as on the $A\beta_{42}$ and Fe/Asc toxicity in neuronal cells, are also discussed in terms of structure-activity relationship, providing indications of the most promising compounds to be further modified in the search for multitarget anti-AD drugs.

Figure 1. RIV-BIM hybrids as multitarget metal chelators for potential therapy of AD

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Proteins involved in the ferrous ions transport in bacteria

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Metals are essential for all kingdoms of life because of their crucial role in functioning of enzymes and proper protein structure. Therefore, pathogens survival in the human host is dependent on appropriate acquisition of nutrients, particularly numerous metal ions [1]. Due to bacterial colonization is dependent on the ability to obtain essential nutrients from surrounding environment, it is very interesting to understand the process at the molecular level [2]. During infection host cells use different defense strategies against infection involving metal ions. The most common are: metal starvation by sequestration and toxicity by the highly concentrated release of metals. More detailed, the host produce proteins which are efficient metal chelators. It leads to the reduction of the essential metal ions availability for the pathogens. Therefore, nutrient limitation by the host with simultaneous nutrient acquisition by bacteria are crucial processes in the pathogenesis of bacterial infections. As a result of this battle, pathogens have evolved sophisticated acquisition systems to scavenge crucial metals from the surrounding [3]. For example, during infection more than 90% of iron is seized within host cells. At the time, serum iron is mostly bound to host proteins that are not easily accessed. To win the competition with the host, bacteria secretes high affinity iron-binding compounds like aureochelin and staphyloferrin during iron starvation [4, 5]. Additionally, upon sensing low concentration of iron, bacteria initiates transcription of an iron acquisition program. It allows to capture of heme and haptoglobin on the cell surface and then, transport of the iron complex across the plasma membrane. The last step in the process is an oxidative degradation of the heme within the cytoplasm [6, 7]. Although, iron is the most abundant transition metal ion in the host, free ferrous iron is rarely present in the organism. Therefore, bacteria live in an environment where iron concentration is much lower than the concentration necessary for their growth. For this reason, bacteria created various type of iron acquisition systems, including the Feo system, which mechanism of Fe²⁺ ion uptake is not fully understood, and protein from the Hmu family belonging to ABC transporters. The Feo transport system is one of the most common systems that is exclusively responsible for importing Fe²⁺ ions. It consists of three proteins: FeoA, FeoB and FeoC. FeoB is a transmembrane protein that is believed to play a key role in the mechanism of Fe²⁺ ion uptake. The other two components are cytoplasmic proteins. Both, FeoA and FeoC, are cytoplasmic proteins resembling the construction of transcription regulators. Under anaerobic-microaerophilic conditions and low pH, bacteria use the FeoB pathway which allows to transport free Fe(II) across the membrane to the cytosol [8]. This system plays an important role in virulence of pathogenic species. As such is an interesting target for the development of new antimicrobial agents [9]. ABC transporters play an equally important role in maintaining iron homeostasis. These include proteins from Hmu family. HmuUV complex catalyses the import of these ions in hem iron form. The structure of this complex consists of TMD dimer

(HmuU) and NBD dimer (HmuV). The HmuU is considered to be a permease - just like the FeoB described earlier while HmuV is the ATP binding protein.

We have shown that these peptides bind iron(II) and/or copper(II) ions and form thermodynamically stable complexes. In the case of ferrous ion coordination, we performed experiments in the presence of mercaptoethanol, DTT and ascorbic acid. We observed that the most convenient one-electron reductant is ascorbic acid (Asc). And therefore, we did the experiments in the 5 molar excess of Asc. We have shown that Asc does not affect the coordination process and without its addition, we calculated the same overall stability constants as in the presence of Asc. But what is very important, we do not have so strictly anaerobic conditions when ascorbic acid is added, because it is able to reduce iron(III) even if a small amount of iron undergoes oxidation. It keeps the second oxidation state. As we can see here (Fig. 1), the most ferrous ion is bound by the studied peptide.

Figure 1. a) Species distribution diagram for Fe(II)–Asc–MKYRI–NH₂ in molar ratio M:Asc:L 1:5:1.1, [Fe(II)] = 1,0 mM; b) The competitive diagram of Fe(II) speciation among Ac–MKYRI–NH₂ and ascorbic acid (Asc) with molar ratios 1:1, [Fe(II)] = 1 mM.

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Investigation of transition metal complexes of biomimetic peptides

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Certain peptides have high metal binding ability, but both the thermodynamic stability and the coordination geometry of peptide complexes are greatly influenced by the amino acid sequence. One field of our present research is the synthesis and investigation of polypeptides containing amino acids with various side chain donor group, in which the coordination of side chain donor atoms comes to the front and their sequences serve as models of different metalloproteins. [1] The imidazole nitrogen containing histidines are frequent side chain donor groups in these metalloproteins and are one of the most important binding sites of transition metal ions. Such metal ion–protein interaction plays an important role in biological processes including the function of Cu,Zn superoxide dismutase enzyme.

The copper(II)ion in the active site of the Cu,Zn superoxide dismutase enzyme binds to three imidazole nitrogens, the zinc(II)ion coordinates to two histidine imidazole nitrogens and the carboxylate group of one aspartic acid. The two metal ions are linked via a deprotonated imidazolato bridging ligand. Previously studied peptides in our research group proved that the binding site of Cu(II) can be described with the tripeptide, "HVVH"; and in the case of Zn(II) with the tetrapeptide "HVGD". [2]

Continuing this work, our aim was to model the active site of the enzyme, to synthesize and investigate terminally protected oligopeptides in which the "HVVH" and "HVGD" moieties were joined, supplemented with the amino acid histidine as a bridging ligand. For this, the peptides Ac-FHVVHAGPHFNGGHVVG-NH₂ and Ac-FHVHEGPHFNGGHVGD-NH₂ were prepared by solid phase peptide synthesis.

Therefore, the solution equilibria, spectroscopic, and electrochemical studies were performed with the Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), and mixed metal complexes of the abovementioned peptides. The stoichiometry, stability constants and structure of complexes were studied using pH-potentiometric, UV-vis, CD spectroscopy and ESI-MS techniques. The electrochemical parameters of copper(II) complexes were determined on the basis of CV measurements.

Figure 1: Expected structure for the Cu(II):Zn(II):Ac-FHVHEGPHFNGGHVGD-NH₂ 1:1:1 system

The results clearly show that the stability of the metal complexes significantly depends on the metal ion and the number and position of histidines in the peptide. However, the metal binding ability of the peptide is also affected by the neighbouring amino acids in the vicinity of the histidines. The results showed that in systems containing both metal ions, the copper(II)ion is coordinated by the “HVH” while the zinc(II)ion by the “HVG(D)” sequence of the peptide. Overall, the obtained results confirm that the main binding for zinc(II) is the “HVGD” sequence (Figure 1).

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Soluble/MOF-Supported Palladium Single Atoms Catalyze the Ligand-, Additive-, and Solvent-Free Aerobic Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohols to Benzoic Acids

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Metal single-atom catalysts (SACs) promise great rewards in terms of metal atom efficiency. However, the requirement of particular conditions and supports for their synthesis, together with the need of solvents and additives for catalytic implementation, often precludes their use under industrially viable conditions [1]. Here, we show that palladium single atoms are spontaneously formed after dissolving tiny amounts of palladium salts in neat benzyl alcohols, to catalyze their direct aerobic oxidation to benzoic acids without ligands, additives, or solvents [2,3].

With this result in hand, the gram-scale preparation and stabilization of Pd SACs within the functional channels of a novel methyl-cysteine-based metal–organic framework (MOF) was accomplished, to give a robust and crystalline solid catalyst fully characterized with the help of single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD). These results illustrate the advantages of metal speciation in ligand-free homogeneous organic reactions and the translation into solid catalysts for potential industrial implementation.

This work: ligand-, additive, solvent-free, supported or not Pd_1 catalyst

Figure 1. Catalytic oxidation of benzyl alcohols to benzoic acids using MOF-supported Pd^0 .

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Iron complex imprinted polymers as heterogeneous catalysts for the green degradation of dye pollutants

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In recent times, there has been a sharp increase in the need for consumer products, leading to a flourishing of industries. This has led to a sustained increase in the pollution of ecosystems, mostly due to the discharge of effluents containing harmful compounds. Among the latter, dyes from textile wastewaters have become a major environmental issue [1]. In the quest for novel green methodologies of effluent treatment, the advanced oxidation processes catalyzed by iron complexes have become a promising technology. Nowadays, the state of the art in this field involves the development of heterogeneous iron-containing catalysts [2], which can be removed and stored after operation, as well as easily coupled to water treatment systems. This has proved to be challenging, though, since some of the catalysts display medium-to-low conversions and/or have high production costs.

In the development of new inexpensive and green effluent treatment alternatives, in this work we aimed to imprint polymers with iron(III) complexes to produce efficient Fenton-like heterogeneous catalysts for the green oxidative degradation of the methyl orange (MO) dye pollutant. Different metal complexes bearing commercial and low-cost ligands were assayed and their catalytic activity levels towards the discoloration of MO by H₂O₂ were assessed (Figure 1a). The best candidates were Fe(III)-BMPPA (BMPPA = di-(2-picolyl)amine) and Fe(III)-NTP (NTP = 3,3',3''-nitrilotripropionic acid), displaying above 70% MO degradation in 3 h. Fe(III)-BMPPA caused the oxidative degradation through two first-order parallel stages related to the formation of BMPPA-Fe-OOH species and the generation of reactive oxygen species. Regarding the complex with NTP, only the former stage was detected.

Both complexes were then employed to imprint catalytic cavities into molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs). The polymers showed catalytic profiles that were highly dependent on the crosslinking agent employed, with N,N-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAA) being the crosslinker that rendered polymers with optimal oxidative performance. Indeed, a conversion higher than 95% was observed for MBAA cross-linked MIPs (Figure 1b), possibly due to the formation of more hydrophilic and flexible polymers that favour the entrance and accumulation of the dye into the catalytic cavities.

These MBAA MIPs constitute the first examples of highly promising materials that can be used in the search for efficient and low-cost Fenton-like ion-imprinted catalysts, which could be coupled to dye wastewater treatment systems working under synchronous injection of H₂O₂.

Figure 1: a) General strategy followed in this work. b) The MIP catalyses the degradation of methyl orange in water using H_2O_2 .

We are currently undertaking some studies to extend the applicability of the catalytic polymers. We are testing new iron complexes, bearing ligands with different topologies, coordination numbers, geometries, and donor atoms. Besides, we expanded the range of pollutant dyes towards other important industrial examples, such as methylene blue and malachite green. The preliminary results are promising, and show that with some of the complexes there is a 50% decrease in the time needed for a complete dye degradation.

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Degradation of S-Nitrosogluthathione by Air-Pollution-Derived Metal Ions in Blood Plasma from Patients with Exacerbation of Heart Failure and Coronary Artery Disease

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One of the consequences of long-term exposure to air pollutants is increased mortality and deterioration of life parameters, especially among people diagnosed with cardiovascular diseases (CVD) or impaired respiratory system. Aqueous soluble inorganic components of airborne particulate matter containing redox-active transition metal ions may affect the stability of S-nitrosothiols and disrupt the balance in the homeostasis of nitric oxide.[1,2] The disturbance in nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability is thought to be one of the key factors common to cardiovascular disease. Uncontrolled elevation of NO concentration may exacerbate inflammation through the damage of the endothelial cells, mediated by superoxide anion and hydroxyl radical, local vasoconstriction, and increased vascular resistance as well as aggregation and growth of platelets.

Blood plasma's protective ability against the decomposition of S-nitrosogluthathione (GSNO) under the influence of aqueous PM extract among patients with exacerbation of heart failure and coronary artery disease was studied and compared with a group of healthy volunteers. In the environment of CVD patients' plasma, NO release from GSNO was facilitated compared to the plasma of healthy controls, and the addition of ascorbic acid boosted this process. Model studies with albumin revealed that the amount of free thiol groups is one of the crucial factors in GSNO decomposition. The correlation between the concentration of NO released and -SH level in blood plasma revealed that the amount of free thiol groups is one of the crucial factors in GSNO decomposition. Complementary studies on gamma-glutamyltranspeptidase activity and ICP-MS multielement analysis of CVD patients' plasma samples in comparison to a healthy control group provide broader insights into the mechanism of cardiovascular risk development induced by air pollution. Redox-active inorganic fraction of urban PM should be considered as one of the environmental factors leading to the progression of cardiovascular disease via uncontrolled GSNO decomposition.

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Inhibitory mechanisms of synthetic curcumin-acridine metal complexes in Alzheimer's disease: A structure-based drug design strategy against the amyloid beta 25-35 fragment

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Well-known amyloid hypothesis, extracellular amyloid beta (A β) peptide deposits that occur in the brain tissue are the main cause of the disease [1-3]. The source of these neuron-damaging A β peptides is the amyloid precursor protein (APP), a type-1 transmembrane glycoprotein that plays an important role in the pathogenesis of AD [4, 5].

In this theoretical molecular docking study, it was aimed to perform docking simulations of two synthetic curcumin-acridine metal complexes (curcumin-9-amino acridine [Fe (III) group] and curcumin-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-acridine-9-carboxylic acid-curcumin [Fe(III) group]) against the A β 25-35 fragment.

Fig1. 1,2,3, 4-tetrahydro-akridin-9-carboxylic acid-curcumin Fe(III) complex

As a result, the biological inhibitory effect of these curcumin-metal complexes on A β 25-35 fragment will be modelled, the intensity of the inhibitory effect (binding free energy, ΔG°) will be calculated, and the non-covalent intermolecular interactions (H-bonds, electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions, Van der Waals contacts) that occur because of the binding between ligands and the receptor will be examined. These data from docking experiments will ultimately provide a molecular-scale characterization of A β 25-35 inhibition of curcumin-acridine metal complexes and will shed light on the rational use of these ligands in AD.

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Complexation of Tetravalent Thorium and Uranium with Dihydroxamic Acids

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Actinides are harmful contaminants for the environments due to their chemical toxicity and radiotoxicity affecting living organisms. The presence of radioelements, such as U, Th, or Pu, as a result of accidental discharges raises the question of their transfer in the environment and the resulting risk of food chain contamination. Their transfer in soils and sediments is not only controlled by geological and physico-chemical parameters (clay and organic matter contents, pH, Eh, etc.) but also by microorganisms. The latter take part in the mobilization/immobilization of trace metals [1].

As natural iron-specific chelators, siderophores have to be considered in this context [2]. These low molecular weight, water-soluble compounds are excreted by bacteria and fungi to overcome the limited bioavailability of iron under aerobic conditions (ca. 10^{-18} M at neutral pH) by dissolving iron oxohydroxides present in the soils. Recently, they have also been recognized as effective actinide(IV) chelators and transporters, promoting the migration of plutonium in contaminated soils [3]. Because of their high affinity for hard Lewis acid cations, like Fe(III), hydroxamic siderophores are also able to effectively bind actinides (U, Th, Pu) [2,4,5]. The development of high affinity chelators for f-elements and the understanding of their coordination chemistry is of fundamental interest for the management and remediation of contaminated fields or the disposal of nuclear wastes in geological repositories [5].

This work is devoted to the complexation study of Th(IV) and U(IV) with dihydroxamic acids (Figure 1). For Th(IV), we used affinity capillary electrophoresis (ACE), which requires only a few μL of solutions, with UV detection. ACE is based on the change in the electrophoretic mobility of the detected species due to the interaction with other species present in the electrolyte. Four sets of runs were performed using (H,Na)ClO₄ mixtures at two different pH values but constant ionic strength. In a first approach, the background electrolyte (BGE) contained varying amounts of Th(IV), while the second approach consisted in analysing solutions containing increasing amounts of ligand in the BGE. The electrophoretic mobility changes with the increasing concentrations of the reagent dissolved in the BGE solution was used to assess the speciation and equilibrium constants.

In contrast to thorium that exists only in the +IV oxidation state, the manipulation of tetravalent uranium in aqueous solution is not an easy task because of its instability to air and

high tendency to hydrolyse. In practice, U(IV) is usually manipulated in glove boxes to keep inert conditions, while highly acidic conditions prevent hydrolysis in aqueous media. However, one advantageous feature of this $5f^2$ cation is its light absorption properties in the visible region, which allows to study the U(IV) complexation equilibria by classical absorption spectrophotometry. Having no wet glove box at our hands, we have developed a reliable experimental protocol for performing spectrophotometric titrations using simple tools, while starting from an air-stable UO_2^{2+} solution. Relying on cyclic voltammetry studies in 1 M $HClO_4$ under an argon atmosphere, the quantitative electrolysis of U(VI) to U(IV) was successfully achieved in a classical electrochemical cell. The progression of the reduction was monitored by UV-Vis spectrophotometry. Finally, the U(IV) solution was transferred in a thermostated gas-tight cell equipped with an argon inlet and outlet and which allows the insertion of a quartz dip probe for the registration of spectra. The entire setup was placed in a typical laboratory fume hood.

The ACE and spectrophotometric methods were successfully applied for studying the Th(IV) and U(IV) complex formation equilibria with various dihydroxamic acids. Both techniques provide valuable information for further modelling of their behaviour under environmental conditions [6].

Figure 1. General structure of the studied dihydroxamic acids

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